

EXTERNAL NOISE INTEGRATION AND MODELLING IN COLLABORATIVE AIRCRAFT DESIGN

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Abstract

Analysis of scenario

The Multidisciplinary Optimization (MDO) is the last frontier of the aircraft design process and this is due to its collaborative trait between several partners involved in it. Any partner will treat a specific discipline autonomously, sharing its data and results with the other partners, in order to reduce working time and costs and to improve designing quality. The noise estimation is one of these disciplines because of the necessity to limit noise emissions of an aircraft (they will influence the local environment near the airport, causing psycho-acoustic damages on people and wildlife). Through the noise estimation, it is possible to act on the aircraft's components, which cause noise emissions (airframe and engine), in order to research all possible improvements on them. This thesis work will improve the AGILE 4.0 project (European MDO project) from the noise estimation point of view and it has been developed with the DAF group of the University of Naples "Federico II".

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The thesis work concerns the integration of a pre-defined estimation noise tool in the AGILE 4.0 MDO project. In particular, the input data management (engine data, trajectory data, aircraft data, control parameters data, microphone data) and the output results management have been automated. Moreover, the trajectory's simplified estimation feature, with the path and time-histories' plotting, has been added, as well as the noise results' footprint showing in a reference area near the airport.

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The integration process is based on the Noise Tool ATTILA++, that is a C++ based software able to estimate noise emissions. The tool has been integrated in the AGILE 4.0 workflow, developed in the RCE collaborative environment, through several Python scripts and classes. The scripts are able to read and write a standard file type (CPACS) that the RCE workflow will exploit too. The scripts, moreover, are able to calculate simplified trajectories, based on normative, and create noise footprints.

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The first results refer to the noise emissions, necessary to certificate the aircraft w.r.t. the regulations CS-25 and CS-23. They define the noise limits, margins and flight test conditions to respect on varying of the reference weight and engine type. The evaluative results, instead, consist in several Footprints, plotted in the area near the reference airport for all test cases (the footprints, moreover, have been overlapped on geo-located images of this area, on varying of the airport chosen from a specific database). The first tested aircraft is the Turbo-Fan AC6-WP8, which refers to CS-25. Moreover, through the AGILE 4.0 collaborative workflow and CPACS3 compatibility, different engines with various BPR are equipped on the aircraft; their influence has been evaluated through correction factors. The second tested aircraft is the Light Turbo-Prop AC3-WP7, tested for both regulations due to its singular reference weight interposed between the previous cited regulations.

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Design**

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List of Symbols

Symbol	Units	Description
g	m/s^2	Gravitational acceleration
ρ	kg/m^3	Air density
V	m/s	Flow velocity
S	m^2	Wing surface
α	Degree	Angle of attack
P	Pascal	Static pressure
T	<i>Kelvin</i>	Temperature
R	<i>Joule/(Kelvin * mol)</i>	Gas constant
F	<i>Newton</i>	Force
St	dimensionless	Strouhal Number
p_∞	<i>Pascal</i>	Free-stream pressure
V_∞	m/s^2	Free-stream velocity
c	m/s	Sound Speed
f	<i>Hertz</i>	Frequency
λ	m	Distance between two consecutive wave-fronts
T_∞	<i>Kelvin</i>	Ambient Temperature
γ	dimensionless	Specific Heats
ω	$rad * sec^{-1}$	Angular Frequency
DI	<i>Decibel</i>	Directivity Index
LE	dimensionless	Leading Edge
AR	dimensionless	Aspect Ratio
$MTOW$	Kg	Maximum Take-Off Weight
C_L	dimensionless	Lift coefficient
C_D	dimensionless	Drag coefficient
Re	dimensionless	Reynolds number
M	dimensionless	Mach number
BPR	dimensionless	By-Pass Ratio
$HBPR$	dimensionless	High By-Pass Ratio
$UHBPR$	dimensionless	Ultra-High By-Pass Ratio
OEI	dimensionless	One Engine Inoperative
$VBNA$	dimensionless	Variable By-Pass Nozzle Area
$avgDS1$	mm	Preliminary average cell edge length
HLD	dimensionless	High Lift Devices
CFD	dimensionless	Computational Fluid Dynamics
OOP	dimensionless	Object-Oriented Programming
FEM	dimensionless	Finite Element Method
DOF	dimensionless	Degree Of Freedom
DOC	€	Direct Operating Cost

Symbol	Units	Description
<i>AGILE</i>	dimensionless	Aircraft 3rd Generation MDO for Innovative Collaboration of Heterogeneous Teams of Experts
<i>ADORNO</i>	dimensionless	Aircraft Design and nOise RatiNgfor regiOnal aircraft
<i>ATTILA</i>	dimensionless	Aircraft noise predicTion InCLuding performAnce
<i>ICAO</i>	dimensionless	International Civil Aviation Organization
<i>EASA</i>	dimensionless	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
<i>DLR</i>	dimensionless	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft-und Raumfahrt
<i>MDO</i>	dimensionless	Multidisciplinary Optimization
<i>MDAO</i>	dimensionless	Multidisciplinary Design Analysis and Optimization
<i>ESDU</i>	dimensionless	Engineering Sciences Data Unit
<i>BRICS</i>	dimensionless	Protocol plus supportive middleware
<i>CSV</i>	dimensionless	Comma Separated Value
<i>CPACS</i>	dimensionless	Common Parametric Aircraft Configuration Schema
<i>N</i>	<i>Noy</i>	Overall Perceived Noisiness
<i>SPL</i>	<i>Decibel</i>	Sound Pressure Level
<i>OASPL</i>	<i>Decibel</i>	Overall Sound Pressure Level
<i>PNL</i>	<i>Decibel</i>	Perceived Noise Level
<i>EPNL</i>	<i>Decibel</i>	Effective Perceived Noise Level

1

Introduction

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1.1 Thesis Objectives and Motivation

The thesis work that's going to be presented has been developed during an intramoenia work spent in the academic structure in collaboration with Design of Aircraft and Flight technologies research group (DAF) of University of Naples Federico II.

This thesis work is mainly focused on the integration procedure of a Noise Tool that's used to evaluate the main Noise regulatory values in different flight phases; these are described and regulated by normative authorities that define procedures and regulation on noise study through some Annexes of regulation; these Annexes describes procedures and limit values with respect to aircraft category: it will be seen that the main driver is the aircraft weight in Take-Off condition (MTOW). Moreover, starting from the integration procedure, this work will improve the interaction with Noise Tool, adding more layers of control through new commands and a "black box" logic algorithm that will simplify tool's practice. Significant improvements will be

the possibility to evaluate in a simplified way the main trajectories performed during these simulated flight tests and the possibility to evaluate and analyse detailed footprints of these tests cases. Moreover, engine parameters editing has been added to unlock the capability of setting engine contribution in function of By-Pass Ratio (BPR) for Turbofan engine. The algorithm developed during this thesis work has been coded in Python environment, with the add of some Matlab functions, which improved the resolution and quality of some output images.

Naturally the main purpose of this integration procedure is to include the stand-alone external noise analyse and certification in a multidisciplinary process based on a collaborative Aircraft Design; the collaborative aspect define the possibility to exploit results and informations of other design processes, performed by other users, to perform high quality and fidelity analyses that are shared in real time with the other operators involved in this collaborative design procedure itself.

The final goal of collaborative aircraft design is to effectively reduce development costs and time, improving the multidisciplinary aspect, and an important project created to this purpose, in which this thesis work has been involved, is the *AGILE Project*.

1.2 Literature Review

1.2.1 Introduction

First of all, it is important to discuss, in a proper way, about theory behind the methodologies and successive applications. Therefore, it will be discussed the certification procedure with a deep overview on *Annex 16*, that's the Annex on Chicago Convention, linked to Noise Certification; so, noise calculations methods and possible noise reduction's solutions will be discussed and finally there will be an overview on *MDO* logic and *AGILE 4.0* project history and development.

1.2.2 Noise Certification

Historical Background

The starting condition, that conducts to necessity to study and evaluate noise emission of an aircraft, is the needing of regulation or rules that have to control noise pollution due to air traffic near the airport, that in last decades has seen a significant increase. This is the reason why the *ICAO* (International Civil Aviation Organization) has released a regulation, defined by the *Volume 1 of Annex 16 on Chicago Convention* [1], in which has been described all procedures to verify noise emissions of a certain aircraft and then the specific noise limit to respect in different flight conditions. Naturally, this annex contains several certification values, which come from practical tests performed to verify noise levels that a certain person is able to tolerate without complaints or worse physical consequences.

Annex 16 of Chicago Convention regulation, generally, deals with every kind of environment pollution and that's why it is divided into three volumes, each of which has been divided in different chapters, function of several drivers:

- **Volume 1:** It deals with Noise Emissions Certification and it is divided in different chapters where each of which deals with a certain type of aircraft in function of the following drivers:
 - **Aircraft Weight.**
 - **Number of Engine.**
 - **Engine Type** (Turbo-Jet, Turbo-Fan and Turbo-Prop).
 - **Aircraft Type** (Fixed Wing or Rotor Wing).
- **Volume 2:** It deals with Engine Emissions Certification.
- **Volume 3:** It deals with CO_2 Certification Requirements.

Difference between CS23 and CS25

Volume 1 of Annex 16 will be the main source of information about this thesis work in terms of test procedures and regulation limits, but, as anticipated previously, this volume is divided in different chapters due to several drivers that distinguish noise certification procedures. First significant distinguish must be done with

respect to engine type, in fact all chapters of Volume 1 refer to a specific type of engine between propeller and jet engines, moreover some chapters can be seen as improvement of older chapters, so they refer to engine types that are the same of other previous chapters; considering this classification, a flow diagram of multi-questions must be followed as shown in Fig.1.1 to better understand what should be the specific chapter to follow in order to perform noise certification of a certain aircraft in function of it's own drivers.

Figure 1.1: ICAO flow diagram scheme.

Naturally, the main chapters, regarding this thesis work, deal with fixed wing

configuration aircraft and they can be schematized as follow:

- **Chapter 3:** "*Subsonic jet aeroplanes — Application for Type Certificate submitted on or after 6 October 1977 and before 1 January 2006*" and "*Propeller-driven aeroplanes over 8 618 kg — Application for Type Certificate submitted on or after 1 January 1985 and before 1 January 2006*". This chapter refers to all Jet Aircraft, without any constrain on weight, and also to Propeller-Driven Aircraft with a MTOW over than 8 618 kg. The main aspect to underline here is that Chapter 3 refers to all aircraft with more consistent dimensions as it can be understood considering the engine type and weight's constrains.
- **Chapter 4:** "*Subsonic jet aeroplanes and propeller-driven aeroplanes with maximum certificated take-off mass 55 000 kg and over — Application for Type Certificate submitted on or after 1 January 2006 and before 31 December 2017*" and "*Subsonic jet aeroplanes with maximum certificated take-off mass less than 55 000 kg — Application for Type Certificate submitted on or after 1 January 2006 and before 31 December 2020*" and "*Propeller-driven aeroplanes with maximum certificated take-off mass over 8 618 kg and less than 55 000 kg — Application for Type Certificate submitted on or after 1 January 2006 and before 31 December 2020*". This chapter, simply, is an improvement of previous chapter due to the fact that certification limits considered in are more stringent and there is a new separation in Jet Aircraft in function of MTOW with the add of a new reference value of 55 000 Kg.
- **Chapter 6:** "*Propeller-driven aeroplanes not exceeding 8618 kg — Application for Type Certificate submitted before 17 November 1988*". This chapter refers only to Propeller-Driven Aircraft with an important constrain about MTOW because chapter, basically, deals with Light Propeller-Driven Aircraft, instead of chapters 3-4 that deal with Heavy-Mid Propeller-Driven Aircraft.
- **Chapter 10:** "*Propeller-driven aeroplanes not exceeding 8 618 kg — Application for Type Certificate or certification of Derived Version submitted on*

or after 17 November 1988". This chapter is, basically, an improvement of chapter 6 in terms of procedures and noise limits.

It is clear that the add of new chapters by the *ICAO* is due to the fact that engine's manufacture has seen, going on in time, important improvements in terms of pollution and emissions of every kind and particularly in the noise emissions field. At the base of this classification, a specification between Certification CS-23 and CS-25 must be done.

The CS-25 regulation deals with Chapter 3 and 4 in Volume 1 because this regulation refers to Jet Aircraft and Heavy Propeller-Driven Aircraft; so, as seen in chapters description, the main discriminating factor is the maximum aircraft weight evaluated in Take-Off condition that must be higher than certification limit (MTOW = 8 618 Kg) for Propeller-Driven Aircraft while for Jet ones it does not find any constrain but on the other side this kind of aircraft can be certified only with respect to this chapters so with respect to this regulation.

The CS-23, instead, deals with Chapter 6 and 10 in Volume 1 because this regulation refers just to Light Propeller-Driven Aircraft, so all Propeller ones with a MTOW under the previous certification limit.

Considering this thesis work, all analyses will be done considering chapter 3 for CS-25 and chapter 10 for CS-23 because of the sudden improvement of engine manufactures' techniques and technical improvements on all components of airframe.

Environmental Charges

The introduction of noise certification is not only based on previous regulation but it is necessary to introduce some economical constrains and charges to encourage use of quieter or lower-emission aircraft by airlines not only with respect to noise emissions but also with respect to other kinds of pollution's emissions. Recent studies [2] together with an analyse of publicly available information revealed that approximately 60% of the busiest *EU28 + EFTA* airports have implemented environmental charges, that are used exclusively to refinance airport infrastructure and the resultant operating expenses; clearly, in line with *ICAO* guidance, these

charges are focused on local noise and also on air quality (NO_X) impacts and global climate change impacts (CO_2). In general the overall proportion of environmental charges relative to total charges of a certain airport is increasing; particularly, noise charges are increasing, even if not so much, but it is clear that this trend will bring airlines to improve their technologies and manufactures to reduce significantly every kind of pollution and emissions.

Nowadays, nevertheless, there is a clear difference between levels of charges of various airports through nations and continents (in Fig.1.5 it is possible to notice charges' difference between the European airports, especially through nations). An example of airport economic charges comes from the ones imposed for the aircraft that take-off and land in the Frankfurt airport [3]; these charges first of all will depend from various aircraft categories that can be distinguished in function of noise certification value for Take-Off and Approach (Fig.1.2 and 1.3); then, considering these categories, it is possible to calculate the amount of noise charge starting from a minimum of 24 hours' charges (Fig.1.4): it is important to highlight how it could be a doubling or tripling of a certain charge if the aircraft should take-offs or lands during night, so during a phase of the day when noise emissions are more annoying and "dangerous" for people who live near the airport; this is the reason why generally an aircraft does not take-offs and lands from 22:00 to 05:59 hrs local time.

However, it is important to underline that the economical charges due to noise emissions are part of the Landing Fees, that are at the same time a contribution of the total DOC of a certain aircraft (in Fig.1.6 is shown the *AEA* method to evaluate DOC). Considering this aspect, the respect of airport's noise limitations becomes really important in terms of DOC reduction. In the end, in order to show a simple estimate's example, it is possible to calculate the noise charges for two different aircraft, belonging respectively to category 2 and 1, considering that they have to conduct all their annual flight take offing and landing in Frankfurt airport. In this way, assuming an average of seven flight per day with a number of operative

days during an year of 360 days, it becomes easy to estimate a coarse noise charge for both aircraft's categories as it can be seen in Table 1.1.

1.2.7					
Zuordnung von nach ICAO Annex 16/3, 16/4 und höher zertifizierten Strahltriebwerken- Luftfahrzeugen sowie von Propellerflugzeugen und Hubschraubern bei Start	Kategorie 1: LAX bis 77,9 dB(A)				
	Category 1: LAX up to 77.9 dB(A)				
	jets mit MTOM < 34 t, soweit nicht ausdrücklich anderen				
	Lärmklassen zugeordnet				
	jets with MTOM ≤ 34 t, as far as not allocated otherwise				
	Alle Propellerflugzeuge mit MTOM ≤ 34 t				
	All propeller-driven aircraft with MTOM ≤ 34 t				
	Alle Hubschrauber				
	All helicopters				
	A320-Neo				
	A321-Neo				
	B712				
	BCS1/BCS3				
	CRJ7/CRJ9				
	CRJX				
E145					
GLF4/GLF5/GLF6					
GLEX/GLST					
HDJT					
Categorization of turbo jet aircraft certified according to ICAO Annex 16/3 and 16/4 and higher, propeller-driven aircraft and helicopters upon take-off	Kategorie 2: LAX 78,0 bis 78,9 dB(A)				
	Category 2: LAX 78.0 to 78.9 dB(A)				
	A148				
	A319-Neo				
	BAe146/Avro Rj				
	F70				
	SSJ100				
	TU204				
	Kategorie 3: LAX 79,0 bis 79,9 dB(A)	Category 3: LAX 79.0 to 79.9 dB(A)			
		A318			
A319/A319V					
B736					
B752					
B762					
B788					
E170					
E75L					
E75S					
F100					
Kategorie 4: LAX 80,0 bis 80,9 dB(A)		Category 4: LAX 80.0 to 80.9 dB(A)			
		A320/A320V			
		A321/A321V			
		A359			
	A35K				
	B735-P				
	B753				
	B737				
	B738Max				
	B789				
	B78X				
	E175				
	E190				
	E195				
	Kategorie 5: LAX 81,0 bis 81,9 dB(A)	Category 5: LAX 81.0 to 81.9 dB(A)			
A310					
B733-P					
B735					
B738					
Kategorie 6: LAX 82,0 bis 82,9 dB(A)		Category 6: LAX 82.0 to 82.9 dB(A)			
		B733			
		B739			
		Kategorie 7: LAX 83,0 bis 83,9 dB(A)	Category 7: LAX 83.0 to 83.9 dB(A)		
			A339		
			B734		
			Kategorie 8: LAX 84,0 bis 84,9 dB(A)	Category 8: LAX 84.0 to 84.9 dB(A)	
				A306/A308	
				B77L	
				B77W	
	Kategorie 9: LAX 85,0 bis 85,9 dB(A)			Category 9: LAX 85.0 to 85.9 dB(A)	
				A332/A333	
				A345/A346	
				B763	
				B772	
B773					
Kategorie 10: LAX 86,0 bis 86,9 dB(A)				Category 10: LAX 86.0 to 86.9 dB(A)	
				A388	
		B748			
		B764			
		MD11			
		Kategorie 11: LAX 87,0 bis 87,9 dB(A)	Category 11: LAX 87.0 to 87.9 dB(A)		
			A342/A343		
			MD87		
			Kategorie 12: LAX 88,0 bis 88,9 dB(A)	Category 12: LAX 88.0 to 88.9 dB(A)	
	MD80-83/MD88				
	B744				
	Kategorie 13: LAX 89,0 bis 89,9 dB(A)			Category 13: LAX 89.0 to 89.9 dB(A)	
				B732 Hushkit	
				Kategorie 14: LAX 90,0 bis 90,9 dB(A)	Category 14: LAX 90.0 to 90.9 dB(A)
					B741-B743
Kategorie 15: ≥LAX 91,0 dB(A)					Category 15: ≥LAX 91.0 dB(A)
					AN124

Figure 1.2: Categorization of Turbo-Jet aircraft, certified according to ICAO Annex 16/3 and 16/4 and higher, Propeller-Driven aircraft and Helicopters upon Take-Off.

<p>Kategorie 1: LAX bis 77,9 dB(A) Category 1: LAX up to 77.9 dB(A)</p> <p><i>Jets mit MTOM < 34 t, soweit nicht ausdrücklich in anderen Lärmklassen zugeordnet</i> <i>Jets with MTOM < 34 t, as far as not allocated otherwise</i></p> <p>Alle Propellerflugzeuge mit MTOM ≤ 34 t All propeller-driven aircraft with MTOM ≤ 34 t</p> <p>Alle Hubschrauber All helicopters</p> <p>B712 BAe146/AvroRJ CRJ7 E145 E170 E175 E75L F70 F100 GLEX/GLST GLF4/GLF5/GLF6 HDJT MD87</p>	<p>Kategorie 5: LAX 81,0 bis 81,9 dB(A) Category 5: LAX 81.0 to 81.9 dB(A)</p> <p>A359 B763 B764 B78X B788 B789 B773 MD80-83/MD88</p>	<p>1.2.6 Zuordnung von nach ICAO Annex 16/3, 16/4 und höher zertifizierten Strahltriebwerken Luftfahrzeugen sowie von Propellerflugzeugen und Hubschraubern bei Landung Categorization of turbo jet aircraft certified according to ICAO Annex 16/3 and 16/4 and higher, propeller-driven aircraft and helicopters upon landing</p>
<p>Kategorie 2: LAX 78,0 bis 78,9 dB(A) Category 2: LAX 78.0 to 78.9 dB(A)</p> <p>A320-Neo A321-Neo A321X A321X B735-P B752 B753 CRJ9 CRJX E755</p>	<p>Kategorie 6: LAX 82,0 bis 82,9 dB(A) Category 6: LAX 82.0 to 82.9 dB(A)</p> <p>A306/A308 A342/A343 A35K B762 B772 B77L B77W</p>	
<p>Kategorie 3: LAX 79,0 bis 79,9 dB(A) Category 3: LAX 79.0 to 79.9 dB(A)</p> <p>A148 A319-Neo A319V A320V A321 B733-P B736 B737 B738 B738 MAX B739 BCS1 E190 E195 SSJ100</p>	<p>Kategorie 7: LAX 83,0 bis 83,9 dB(A) Category 7: LAX 83.0 to 83.9 dB(A)</p> <p>A370 A332/A333 A339 A345/A346 MD-11</p>	
<p>Kategorie 4: LAX 80,0 bis 80,9 dB(A) Category 4: LAX 80.0 to 80.9 dB(A)</p> <p>A318 A319 A320 B732-Hushkit B733 B734 B735 BCS3</p>	<p>Kategorie 8: LAX 84,0 bis 84,9 dB(A) Category 8: LAX 84.0 to 84.9 dB(A)</p> <p>A388 B744</p>	
	<p>Kategorie 9: LAX 85,0 bis 85,9 dB(A) Category 9: LAX 85.0 to 85.9 dB(A)</p> <p>B748</p>	
	<p>Kategorie 10: LAX 86,0 bis 86,9 dB(A) Category 10: LAX 86.0 to 86.9 dB(A)</p> <p>B741-B743</p>	
	<p>Kategorie 11: LAX 87,0 bis 87,9 dB(A) Category 11: LAX 87.0 to 87.9 dB(A)</p> <p>-</p>	
	<p>Kategorie 12: LAX 88,0 bis 88,9 dB(A) Category 12: LAX 88.0 to 88.9 dB(A)</p> <p>-</p>	
	<p>Kategorie 13: LAX 89,0 bis 89,9 dB(A) Category 13: LAX 89.0 to 89.9 dB(A)</p> <p>-</p>	
	<p>Kategorie 14: LAX 90,0 bis 90,9 dB(A) Category 14: LAX 90.0 to 90.9 dB(A)</p> <p>-</p>	
	<p>Kategorie 15: LAX ≥91,0 dB(A) Category 15: LAX ≥91.0 dB(A)</p> <p>AN124</p>	

Figure 1.3: Categorization of Turbo-Jet aircraft, certified according to ICAO Annex 16/3 and 16/4 and higher, Propeller-Driven aircraft and Helicopters upon Landing.

1.2.8

Entgelte für Strahltriebwerke-Luftfahrzeuge sowie für Propellerflugzeuge und Hubschrauber bei Landung und bei Start
Charges for turbo jet aircraft, propeller-driven aircraft and helicopters upon landing and take-off

Lärmkomponente ganztägig pro Bewegung in €

Noise charges during 24 hrs per movement in €

Kategorie															
Category															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
	85,79	106,39	130,14	142,57	212,03	402,60	440,91	604,92	659,69	772,58	833,33	1.383,50	1.720,45	2.851,00	22.783,00

Zusätzliche Lärmkomponente Nachtzeit 1 pro Bewegung in € (22:00 – 22:59 und 05:00 – 05:59 Uhr Ortszeit)

Additional night surplus charge in night time 1 per movement in € (22:00 – 22:59 and 05:00 – 05:59 hrs local time)

Kategorie															
Category															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
	55,76	69,15	84,59	92,67	137,82	261,69	286,59	393,20	428,80	502,18	541,66	899,28	1.118,29	1.853,15	14.808,95

Alternativ: Zusätzliche Lärmkomponente Nachtzeit 2 pro Bewegung in € (23:00 – 04:59 Uhr Ortszeit)

Alternative: Additional night surplus charge in night time 2 per movement in € (23:00 – 04:59 hrs local time)

Kategorie															
Category															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
	257,37	319,17	390,42	427,71	636,09	1.207,80	1.322,73	1.814,76	1.979,07	2.317,74	2.499,99	4.150,50	5.161,35	8.553,15	68.349,00

Figure 1.4: Charges for Turbo-Jet aircraft, Propeller-Driven aircraft and Helicopters upon Landing and Take-Off.

Figure 1.5: Environment related to charging schemes at 100 busiest EU28+EFTA airports in terms of flight movements.

	Category 1	Category 2
Airport Noise Charge	216 190.8 €	268 102.8 €

Table 1.1: Comparison between Category 1 and 2 Frankfurt's airport's noise charges.

Figure 1.6: DOC components for AEA methodology.

1.2.3 Noise Calculation Methods

The compliance with noise regulation can be conducted choosing a certain way to calculate or estimate the certification values, outlined by the regulations. The methodologies adopted to perform these calculations can be classified in function of level of precision and quality that characterizes the methodologies themselves; this is the reason why it is possible to distinguish several approaches for noise estimation methodologies, as it follows:

- **Simple or Analytical Methodologies;**
- **Semi-Empirical Methodologies;**
- **Medium-High Fidelity Methodologies.**

Analytical Methodologies

Naturally, the simplest way to obtain the noise values, that must be certificated, is to perform directly the regulation procedures through field tests. Test procedures correspond with procedures explained in Annex 16 [1] and the corrections and clarifications explained in the *Technical Manual* [4] attached to the Annex itself. As it has been seen in previous sections, test procedure must be divided in function of aircraft type and, then, engine type; successively, Annex 16 shows, for each type of aircraft, the test procedure performed to verify noise emissions during Take-Off and Landing phases, due to the fact that during these phases the aircraft will

interact strongly with civil areas near the airport. The Annex, in this way, will explain how the aircraft has to perform the specific trajectories (Figs.1.7 and 1.8), defining all the regulations constrains in both flight steps cited before; moreover, in the Annex, microphones' positions during tests' procedures are defined and, finally with some tables, all noise values limits in function of the drivers seen previously (example in Fig.1.9).

The auxiliary document of Annex 16 is the *Technical Manual* that basically describes with accurate precision all appendix's aspects. This manual deals with all considerations to do during tests, starting from calibration procedure of microphones and going on with data measurements and transmissions and, again, it defines how to balance and apply meteorological effects and other kinds of effects that could affect noise measurements. In the end the Technical Manual gives more detailed information about tests procedures themselves and about methods to analyse in a stochastic way noise information acquired during tests.

Figure 1.7: Reference aeroplane Take-Off profile characteristics.

Figure 1.8: Reference aeroplane Approach profile characteristics.

M = Maximum take-off mass in 1 000 kg		0	20.2	28.6	35	48.1	280	385	400	
Lateral full-power noise level (EPNdB) All aeroplanes		94		80.87 + 8.51 log M					103	
Approach noise level (EPNdB) All aeroplanes		98		86.03 + 7.75 log M				105		
Flyover noise levels (EPNdB)	2 engines or less	89			66.65 + 13.29 log M				101	
	3 engines	89		69.65 + 13.29 log M					104	
	4 engines or more	89		71.65 + 13.29 log M				106		

Figure 1.9: Certification Noise Limits for Annex 16, Volume 1, Chapter 3.

Semi-Empirical Methodologies

It is clear that an analytical approach could be used only if the aircraft is available to fly: it means that the noise measurements should be done in the final steps of design procedure when, basically, the aircraft is designed and manufactured by the manufacturer company. Naturally, this is a significant limit that must be exceeded to give possibility to perform noise certification test during the preliminary design of the aircraft. A solution is a semi-empirical method where, by means of experimental data acquired by similar aircraft or by the same aircraft's family, it is possible to estimate noise values with the usage of semi-empirical formula or relations.

Basing on this preliminary overview on semi-empirical methods, there are different kinds of models used to estimate and evaluate noise emissions, based on various

semi-empirical relations theorized during last decades; some examples could be the following ones:

- **Stone’s prediction method** (1974) and **Stone and Montegani method** (1980) for Jet noise emissions evaluation;
- **Heidmann’s prediction method** (1975) for Fan noise emissions evaluation;
- **Kontos’ prediction method** (1996) that is an improvement of Heidmann’s method on the accuracy of the prediction method itself;
- **Coles’ prediction method** (1959) for Jet noise emission through Rectangular Slot Nozzles of AR equals to 14 and 100;
- **Gruschka and Schrecker’s prediction method** (1972) for noise radiated by Rectangular Nozzles of AR equals to 30, 60, and 120.
- **Munro and Ahuja’s prediction method** (2003) for Jet noise emitted by Rectangular Slots of AR varying from 60 to 3000;
- **Lummer’s prediction method** (2008) for Shielding of the engine’s fan sound by the airframe.

Basically, all these methods are the theoretical basements on which main noise tools, adopted in the industrial applications, are built and, nowadays, there are various tools on which it is possible to rely on (see Table 1.2).

Tool	Description	Origin
ANoPP	Aircraft Noise Prediction Program	NASA
PANAM	Aircraft system noise modeling for noise prediction of the engines	DLR
SHADOW	Aircraft Noise Prediction Tool to calculate the shielding of the engine’s fan	DLR

Table 1.2: Aircraft noise modelling and prediction tools. [5]

In light of what it has been described in a preliminary way about semi-empirical methods, a semi-empirical approach will be applied in this thesis work; in fact, Noise Tool, developed by collaboration between *University of Naples “Federico*

II" and *MTU Aero Engines*, will be used to estimate noise values on the basis of some semi-empirical relations. As anticipated, these relations will take in input some experimental data to perform noise estimation and, being more precise, this noise tool, that is called *Attila++*, will estimate, mainly, noise contribution due to airframe and engine with the usage of semi-empirical formula that are organized in the *ESDU*, where the ESDU (originally an acronym of Engineering Sciences Data Unit) is an engineering advisory organization which provides validated engineering analysis tools in the fields of aerospace engineering. Introducing more details, the ESDU tool used for airframe estimate is based on a semi-empirical prediction method which has been developed from that proposed by Martin R. Fink (1977); while the ESDU tool used for engine estimate is based on a semi-empirical prediction method which has been developed from the one proposed by Heidmann (1975). Reason why these tools has been classified as semi-empirical methodologies based tools is that they will exploit input data, that are experimental or design data, to estimate noise emissions with an expected level of uncertainty but at same time with the advantage of a fast calculation and, therefore, a low computational weight.

Medium-High Fidelity Methodologies

The classification of all kinds of methodologies, which can be adopted to simulate and perform cumulative noise emission of an aircraft, finds its end with the last level of simulation, where it is reached the highest level of precision for noise emissions' estimation; this is due to the fact that the med-high fidelity methods bases their working way on computational analysis; so it means that experimental data are substituted by computational results that come from high accuracy solvers, like *CFD* software based on numerical models. The main aspect for this approach is that it is not necessary to take in input, directly, noise results obtained by experimental measurements or noise input data to make possible semi-empirical relations resolutions; but rather, it is "sufficient" to model air-flow all around aircraft, far from it and in interaction with engines, being engine air-flow; then, these model can be analysed with great accuracy by numerical solvers, like *CFD* software and,

finally, noise results or emissions have been obtained. In the end, an overview on pro and cons has to be done, resulting from this choose: the main pro is the significant increase of accuracy; while the cons are linked to all problems due to high computational payload, caused by the heavy models that have to be analysed. [6]

1.2.4 Technical Improvements for Noise Emission's Reduction

All methodologies applied to obtain noise emissions during the flight test phases, that must be certified in function of Annex 16 regulation, find their practical applications in the exploiting of output values to verify not only if noise emissions of a certain aircraft respect noise regulation limits, but also to try to find technical solution to reduce these emissions. During last decades, in fact, all aeronautic industries that mainly deal with aircraft's engines manufacturing, but also deal with aircraft components manufacturing, tried to improve their products in function of the goal to reduce significantly noise emissions; naturally, reason why this goal has been set is to avoid every kind of risk linked to regulation limits and possible economic penalties.

In general, it is possible to distinguish two main sources of noise in the aircraft: the stand-alone airframe and the engine that, normally, causes the main contributions in noise emissions; therefore, the portions for these sources have to be defined and studied individually and a preliminary classification of these contributions could be the following one (an example of noise sources classification is shown in Fig.1.10 :

- **Airframe source:** Main and Nose Landing Gears, Flap, Slat, Lifting Surfaces, Airframe shape and geometry;
- **Engine source:** By-Pass-Ratio, Fan geometry, Exhaust Flow behaviour, Nozzles, Nacelles, Chevrons;

Figure 1.10: Main aircraft noise sources' comparison (EPNLdB) in both Take-Off and Approach phases. [7]

Airframe

The first source that can be optimized to reduce noise emissions is the airframe, even if the contribution due to airframe is lower than the one from engines. As anticipated, there are several subcategories on which it is possible to act. Naturally, the single effects due to these subcategories act differently in function of flight phases and type of aircraft (for example high-lift noise is dominant in regard to airframe noise for an Airbus A320, whereas the landing gear noise is more important for an A380). In general noise contribution due to airframe is caused by the interaction between airflow and airframe's surfaces; therefore, the aerodynamic aspect is the dominant one in this discussion and this is the reason why, acting on geometric parameters of various components of the airframe, it is possible to impact clearly on noise emissions (aerodynamic phenomena that mainly act in noise generation are: boundary layer separation, laminar-to-turbulent boundary layer transition, shear layer transition, laminar separation bubble and associated dynamic effects).

First components that act on noise emission phenomenon are landing gears and a possible solution to reduce their noise contribution is to simplify landing gears geometry, making it more smooth, in order to avoid spurious noise sources or interactions and obtaining an improvement, as it is possible to see in Fig.1.11 (practical solutions are: caps used on cavities, for instance on inner and outer hubs, and rims applied on wheels). With these solutions, it is possible to obtain noise reduction of the order of 3-4 dB in Gears contribution and 1 dB in all aircraft emissions.

The other components that give an important contribution in airframe's noise are all high-lift devices, like flaps and slats; unlike landing gears, the HLD show more difficulties to reduce noise emissions due to their complexity and strong dependency to lift generation; in fact, the majority of solutions to optimize HLD noise emissions cause bad behaviours on lift properties. In function of this complexity, the only solutions applied to improve the HLD consist in the gap optimization or suppression for both slats and flaps; moreover, other possible solutions consist in the usage of porous materials, fractal edges or brushed edges. Reason why all these solutions have been applied is to reduce as much as possible all kinds of flow discontinuities, even if these solutions present other collateral negative effects on noise emissions. In general is important to highlight that noise from high lift devices tends to be dominated by the leading edge slats, with the flaps being a significant secondary contributor. To complete the airframe noise contribution's analyse, it is possible to summarize it with the following tables.

Noise reduction measure	Estimated reduction	Implications for the aircraft
Landing gear mesh fairings (add-on device)	3 - 5 dB	Landing gear design, weight, maintenance
Flap-side-edge noise: Porous device at the edge	5 dB	Maintenance
Slats: Setting optimization (overlap, gap)	3-5 dB	Additional complexity/weight with respect to kinematics and tracks

Table 1.3: Noise reduction measurements identified during the workshop. [5]

Noise source	Noise generating mechanism	Relevant parameters	Conditions under which important	Comments	Level of theoretical understanding
Landing gear	Broadband noise due to turbulent flow on various elements of landing gear and tonal noise due to cavities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Length of strut - Diameter of wheels - Number of gears - Gear doors - Number of axles - Number of wheels - Inflow speed 	Low engine setting (final approach)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heavy aircraft deploy landing gear 15 km before touchdown - The noise of the main landing gear is directly influenced by circulation around the wing 	Medium
Flaps	Broadband noise due to turbulence around side edges and gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flap deflection angle - Local inflow velocity - Chord length - Angle of attack - Slat deflection angle - Sweep angle 	Low or idle engine setting (approach)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flap tracks are of importance and produce excess noise - Flap side edge noise is dominant compared to flap noise itself 	Good
Slats	Broadband noise due to turbulence in gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local inflow velocity - Chord length - Sweep angle - Geometry between slat and wing, e.g. gap height and overlap 	Low or idle engine setting (approach)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Laminar flow does not allow slats (therefore future aircraft might have no slats) - Slat tracks are of importance and produce excess noise 	Medium
Lift and control surfaces (e.g. wing)	Broadband noise due to turbulence at the trailing edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Turbulent intensity at the trailing edge - Sweep angle of the wing - geometry /shape of the trailing edge, e.g. bluntness of trailing edge 	Low engine setting, clean configuration (far approach)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited acoustical data available (difficult to measure because of low noise intensity) - Might not be relevant for current vehicles but for future designs (e.g. without slats) 	Medium
Spoilers and speed brakes	Detached flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spoiler geometry - Flight velocity 	Low engine setting (complete approach)	Spoiler noise can be shielded if the gap behind the spoiler and between wing and high-lift system is closed, e.g. with a splitter blade	Low
Krueger (leading edge device)	Not understood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geometry - Inflow velocity - Sweep angle 	Heavy use of spoilers during standard approaches, dominant during low or idle engine setting	Track system might dominate Krueger itself	Low

Table 1.4: Overview on airframe noise sources. [5]

Figure 1.11: Landing Gears before and after optimization corrections. [8]

Engine

The main noise source of an aircraft is the engine system and this is the reason why great attention is given to engine's optimization, in order to improve their emissions not only with respect of noise contributions but, in general, with respect to environmental emissions. As it has been seen for the airframe, the engine contribution has to be split in different terms and for each one it could be done an optimization procedure. Basically, the engine noise sources can be classified in mechanical/structural sources and fluid-dynamic sources [7]: the first category assembles all engine components which, because of their working, will generate noise emissions (rotating parts); instead, the second category deals mainly with structural elements, which, because of their interaction with airflow, cause noise emissions (nacelles, nozzles, etc); but also this category deals with the fluid-dynamic

behaviour of engine's flow both during engine burning and at the ending phase when the exhaust gas interacts with the external airflow. This classification is important because, for first category, main solutions deals with geometry optimizations, while the second category finds important solutions acting directly on airflow properties or applying surfaces' smoothing in order to reduce noisy airflow interactions. A similar classification of engine noise emissions is between fan/compressor noise and the exhaust jet noise, where jet engine noise is the dominant noise. Lastly, Table 1.5 summarizes main aspect dealing with all main engine noise sources.

Noise source	Noise generating mechanism	Relevant parameters	Conditions under which important	Comments	Level of theoretical understanding
Fan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Thickness and loading noise - Interaction rotor-stator - Stator vane - Struts - Fan-intake interaction, e.g. engine inlet or pylons - Tonal noise due to shock cells on blades (harmonic) - Shock cell interaction with nacelle (not a harmonic sequence) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inlet geometry - Number of blades - Number of vanes - Fan pressure ratio - Relative Tip Mach number - Inlet flow distortion, e.g. due to an angle of attack or due to a pylon in front of the engine inlet 	Always	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For current engines both tones and broadband noise important. The broadband contribution becomes more important for future designs - Buzzsaw (tonal) is relevant - Fan noise increases due to increased inflow distortion by engine installation - Fan noise is reduced due to lining - Fan noise can be subject to significant noise shielding due to structural elements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medium for tones - Low for broadband contribution
Jet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Turbulent mixing - Shock noise (only in cruise condition) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Velocity differences between the streams, i.e. free, core, and bypass stream - Temperature - Nozzle diameter - Nozzle type 	Take-off	Jet noise is a distributed source behind engine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good (under subsonic conditions) - Medium (under sonic conditions)
Combustion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mainly broadband noise - Direct contribution due to the expansion of the gas mixture in the combustion chamber - Indirect noise contribution due to the convection of non-uniformities through pressure gradients in the turbine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature - Pressure ratio - Combustor type (lean, rich) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Approach - Departure after thrust cutback - Side-line 	Becomes more important since all other sources are being reduced	Low
Turbine	Tonal and broadband noise (due to same mechanism as fan noise generation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of blades - Number of vanes - Mach number - Shaft speed - axial stage spacing - Number of stages - Exit area - Shaft power 	Mainly approach and then departure after thrust cutback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Becomes more complex due to multi-stage design - Haystacking might be of importance, i.e. a characteristic spectral broadening effect of turbine tones due to the jet shear layer 	Low-Medium
Compressor	Tonal and broadband noise similar to fan	Same as fan	Departure after thrust cutback and approach		Medium

Table 1.5: Overview on engine noise sources. [5]

First of all, engine noise discussion will start with the overview on Fan noise sources and the possibles solutions to improve these emissions. Initially, is important to underline another distinguish in Fan noise between tone noise component and the

broadband noise component [9]. The tone noise is the major noise component and is referred to rotor–stator interaction noise. As the fan rotor blades pass through the gas, the blades leave wake at their trailing edge. The interaction of pressure fields and the wake impacting upon the vane blades generates the tone noise. The broadband noise, instead, is generated when the gas flows over the surface of the blade. Basically, with respect to noise possible solutions are the use of reflective plates and acoustic chambers, where the movement of reflective plates was controlled to adapt to the changes of the fan speeds, reaching an OASPL reduction of 9-10 dB [9]; another solution is the applying of the acoustic liner [9] [8] over the tip of the rotor, where the acoustic liners consist of classical honeycombs, in which the outer plate is perforated and these liners behave like Helmholtz resonators, absorbing noise in a limited frequency range [10] [8] (see Fig.1.12); and in general with the application of advanced inlet design and acoustic treatment, the ‘scarfed’ inlet showed significant noise reduction.

Figure 1.12: A three DOF Honeycomb liner sample (*left*) and a sketch of extended lip treatment (*right*). [8]

Ultimately, there are various modern solutions under development and study to improve these kinds of noise emissions; but, basically, main solutions, that could be applied, are based on engine parameters and geometric dimensions variations; in fact, the main drivers optimized to reduce Fan noise are:

- **Tip Speed** (see Fig.1.13);
- **Blade Numbers** (see Fig.1.14);
- **Rotor–Stator Spacing** (see Fig.1.15).

Figure 1.13: Noise distribution for Fans at different Rotor Tip speeds. It is interesting that the noise is larger at a lower tip speed. [9]

Figure 1.14: SPL distribution for Fans at different Rotor Blade Numbers (*left*) and Noise distribution for Fans at different Rotor Blade Numbers (*right*). The blade number could significantly affect the noise generation and it could be seen that the noise is reduced by about 1.5 dB when the blade number changes from 23 to 15. The SPL distribution shows that the fan with less blade number generates the highest SPL at lower frequency [8]

Figure 1.15: Noise distribution for Fans at different Rotor–Stator spacing (*left*) and SPL distribution for Fans at Different Rotor–Stator spacing (*right*). Generally, Fan noise generation can be suppressed by increasing the Rotor–Stator spacing, in fact a reduction of about 4 dB in the noise generation can be formed between the 100% spacing fan and the 20% spacing one, even if, when the space is large enough, further increase in the rotor–stator spacing will not make any difference for noise production (The curves of the 100% spacing fan and the 200% spacing fan are exactly the same in this study). Moreover only when the frequency is larger than 800 HZ, big difference in the amplitude of the SPL is produced. [8]

Ending Fan Noise’s analyse, it is time to discuss the other engine noise source that is the Jet Noise. The Jet noise is the main engine noise source and, generally, the main solution to improve this noisy behaviour is acting on By-Pass Ratio (BPR) of the engine itself; to be more precise, noise reduction strategies are aimed at increasing the BPR to lower nozzle exit velocities and designing bypass and core flows to improve mixing with each other and the atmosphere [11].

Being more precise about jet noise, generally, it is, mainly, due to high-velocity but also to high-temperature core jet mixing with low-velocity airflow and in the end to low-temperature atmospheric gases; however, the main source is the different temperature airflow’s mixing that produce a broad sound frequency spectrum. Due to the fact that Jet mixing noise is a strong function of jet exhaust velocity, the principal solution applied to reduce significantly engine noise emissions is the increase of BPR and some useful results can be seen in the Fig.3.3.4 and Fig.1.17.

Figure 1.16: Noise distribution for Fans at different BPR (*left*) and SPL distribution for Fans with BPR (*right*). [9]

Figure 1.17: Comparative noise sources of low and HBPR engines. [9]

The BPR increase is probably the main solution adopted to improve noise emissions; but this increase has negative consequences in term of engine thrust, because the airflow speed reduction leads to a reduction of the engine thrust. This is the reason why during last years many other techniques have been studied and applied. First example to cite is the reshaping of nozzles from coaxial to eccentric in order to offset an annular stream with respect to the primary stream; in this way there is a directional attenuation of noise and important results can be achieved

(the eccentric arrangement is 6.5 dB quieter than the mixed-flow arrangement and 5 dB quieter than the coaxial configuration) [11]. Nevertheless, this solution brings to problems linked to noise structure re-designing; for this reason another solution, very adopted in the engine manufacturing, is the application of chevrons on the engine's nozzles(Fig.1.18).

Figure 1.18: Core Chevrons on a A321 (from *pprune.org*) (left) and Fan Chevrons on a B787 (right). [10]

Chevrons are, basically, geometrical corrugations of the cylindrical exhaust of either the primary jet (core chevrons) or the secondary one (fan chevrons) and their impact on exhaust gases is that they generate axial vorticity and, therefore, enhance the mixing of core, fan and ambient air streams [11] [8].As it can be understood, this is a passive solution, making their usage easier; but there are, also in this case, a lot of negative consequences to consider: chevrons installation causes jet asymmetry, jet instability, increase of aircraft overall weight and drag and, finally, they are limited to specific single applications (a certain chevron design brings to positive results just for a certain flight condition and for a specific aircraft category or type).

Because of these reasons, an "evolution" of chevron has been studied and developed, which is the micro-jet device; this is an injection system that impact the main jet, blowing pressurized air into the main jet and that is supposed to act as physical geometrical chevron, reason why it is also called *Virtual Chevron* [8] [11]. The impact of injection on jet noise depends on the injector configuration, injector

operating condition, type of noise source targeted, and number of flow streams (single or dual) in the main jet. The micro-jet velocity (which is proportional to the main jet velocity), the longitudinal distance of injection, and the number of micro-jets are the three parameters that mainly contribute to the optimisation of noise reduction (some results can be seen in Fig.1.19).

Figure 1.19: Overall Noise reduction with additional Micro-Jet flows. [8]

To conclude the engine noise overview, it is important to underline how, during last years, there was an evolution of engines that reached very high levels of improvements; this evolution effected also noise emissions, in fact, nowadays, the Ultra High By-Pass Ratio (UHBPR) technology finds solid application in the Turbo-Jet engine's word. Several studies have been done to certificate this improvement [12] and some results have been shown in Fig.1.20.

Figure 1.20: Directivity and spectrum for four operating points. A conventional BPR = 5 engine, an UHBR = 17, and an UHBR = 17 with VBNA are shown: (a) directivity - operating point N°1, (b) spectrum at 135° - operating point N°1, (c) directivity - operating point N°2, (d) spectrum at 135° - operating point N°2, (e) directivity - operating point N°3, (f) spectrum at 135° - operating point N°3, (g) directivity - operating point N°4, (h) spectrum at 135° - operating point N°4. [12]

Naturally all these technologies, seen to improve engine noise emissions, can be adopted to obtain the best possible Turbo-Jet engine in term of noise emissions; in function of this aspect, an example of one of the best possible solution is the Silent Aircraft that has been envisioned to achieve a step change in airframe and propulsion system noise reduction in the order of 30 EPNdB. [13]

Other Technical Noise Improvements

Engine noise and airframe noise reduction's techniques are, basically, the most used ones, but there are also other solutions, exploited to improve noise emissions of an aircraft. An important solution adopted to reduce noise emissions concerns to take-off and approach's standard trajectories, because, as it has been seen, these are flight phases that deal with noise emissions.

About the Approach case, considering that Fan noise tends to dominate on it, an increase in BPR do not always contribute to reduce noise, but, in addition, the low throttle settings used during this regime have the consequence of increase the relative noise contribution of airframe aerodynamic; so, the noise solution adopted on landing profile is the so called *Steeper approach* [14]. Idea on which it is developed is that acting on approach angle it is possible, not only to vary the distance between the aircraft and the noise measurement point, but also to change the amount of thrust required to maintain approach speed (Fig.1.21) and, generally, an increase of approach angle leads to a general improvement, as it can be seen in Table 1.6; it is clear that the approach angle depends on aircraft's performances and its evaluation is included in a design iterative procedure, trying to find out a right trade-off between all performance's parameters involved in it.

Angle (deg)	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5
Height (ft)	343.9	401.3	458.8	516.5
Throttle (%)	25.9	22.2	18.4	14.7
Noise (EPNdB)	91.6	89.1	86.5	83.9

Table 1.6: Noise reduction due to Steeper Approach. [14]

Figure 1.21: Steeper Approaches at different approach angles. [14]

About Take-Off phase, a variation of take-off profile, that is the *Thrust Cut-Back* between Climb and Fly-Over, has been applied since the early days of the Turbo-Jet as a method to minimize the noise exposure of specific communities. Idea is to reduce engine throttle at a certain altitude to reduce engine noise, having as consequence a change in flight profile, as it can be seen in Fig.1.22. However, with the upper hand of HBPR, the advantage due to Cut-Back has lost effectiveness and, nowadays, the only advantage is to displace the noise to a different location further than the standard one: Cut-Back is ideal at some airports such as *John Wayne Orange County* where the procedure is carried out over the airport neighboring community [14].

Figure 1.22: Thrust Cut-Back on Take-Off. [14]

In terms of numerical results, the extent of the noise reduction as measured at the takeoff point is limited to a few decibels (see Fig.1.23), considering that

changes in noise amplitude have to be significant to impact the time-integrated Effective Perceived Noise Level (EPNdB) unit.

Figure 1.23: Perceived Noise level during simulated Fly-Over of two procedures: without Cut-Back and with 80% throttle Cut-Back at 800 ft. [14]

In the end, another driver that can influence noise emissions of a certain aircraft is the aircraft category itself. It is clear that, talking about aircraft category, it refers to the trade-off between all terms that affect noise contributions, starting from engine noise and ending with the airframe noise. An example in this discussion could be the blended wing configuration that is one of the actual/future design's perspective to reach, not only a noise emissions improvement, but, in general, the best possible aircraft configuration [15]; moreover, talking about aircraft category, it refers to general mission profile of the aircraft considering, for example, not only civilian aircraft but also military ones. In fact, the military aircraft must be designed and manufactured to respect certain noise limitations too, due to their impact on local environment [16]; it must be considered that these aircraft could fly near residential zones, for example during drills.

Conclusions and Results

All technical improvements applied to reduce noise emissions, seen in previous sections, lead to these results that it hopes to achieve and that it is possible to observe in the following graphs studied by *DLR* thanks to several noise analyses performed by it (see Figs.1.24 and 1.25).

Figure 1.24: Typical Take-Off noise source ranking. [5]

Figure 1.25: Typical Approach noise source ranking. [5]

As it can be seen, for Take-Off phase the main reductions deals with Fan noise, considering engine emissions, and with landing gears, considering airframe emissions;

this trend confirms the significant weight of the landing gears in terms of noise emissions. About Approach, the first aspect to underline is the quasi-absence of the BPR effect that, basically, plays a secondary role only for Fan noise because of absence of Jet noise contribution; then, there is the confirmation of the main role played by the landing gears, even if, in this case, the HLD affect significantly noise emissions and the technical improvements, applied to them, have important effects. To conclude the discussion, the main results, achieved with these improvements, are the total noise reductions for Take-Off and Approach phases of, respectively, a term of 10 dB order of magnitude and 5 dB order of magnitude.

1.2.5 MDO Logic and AGILE 4.0 Project

Noise emissions' evaluation is something that is part of a designing procedure, carried on to project an aircraft; as it has been seen, all different technologies applied to reduce noise emissions have collateral effects on other drivers and parameters that characterize the aircraft itself; so it is important to find out an integration solution between all analyses performed to project the aircraft, because in this way becomes easier to find a trade-off between all drivers cited before. In this sense, the main expression of this logic is the so called *MDAO* (Multidisciplinary Design Analysis and Optimization), where all studies and analyses, made on aircraft's projecting, are connected between all of them; naturally, following this logic, there is an improvement in terms of working times, computational weights and general benefits. In general, the MDO working logic consists in providing of specific competences through the release of computer codes and methods regarding fields such as aerodynamics, aircraft weights' estimation, mission analysis, costs, noise evaluation and so on from each partner involved in the MDO project (it is clear that to perform this project logic is necessary to involve different partners in it); then all these knowledge are going to be shared thanks to common file data in a general designing architecture.

Consequently, the MDO logic on which this thesis work is based is the *AGILE 4.0 Project* [17], of which the *University of Naples Federico II* is one of the official

partners involved in (in Fig.1.27 there is a simple scheme that shows all main partners involved in the AGILE project at its beginning); *The AGILE 4.0 project* is built upon the success of its predecessor *H2020 Project AGILE* (Aircraft 3rd Generation MDO for Innovative Collaboration of Heterogeneous Teams of Experts 2015-2018), birth as a project son of *HORIZON2020 Program*, financed by the *European Union (EU)*. As anticipated, AGILE targets multidisciplinary optimization using distributed analysis frameworks and, to be more precise, AGILE implements the 3rd generation of multidisciplinary optimization through efficient international multi-site collaboration in overall design teams. Furthermore, AGILE project finds its peculiarity in the usage of *CPACS file* [18] to store analyses output and to organize tool's inputs, used to perform work of every tool of project; on the other side, the software, used to run the automated executable workflows for each analyse, is *RCE* software [19] [20] with the usage of Brics package, used to load from a remote source the CPACS input file, from one side, and to send to the same source the specific results, on the other side (an interesting video, that shows main RCE software working, can be check at following link: <https://youtu.be/0OfmtIhmozY>). Reason why CPACS file is an important solution about MDO logic is that this approach allows to reduce time and cost in the preliminary and conceptual design phase because of the easy connection among partners that can share and exchange calculations and results using the CPACS file itself; being more precise, this technology allows to reduce the total amount of interconnections among partners (see Fig.1.26). In the end, the described approach can lead to optimized results characterized by a quietly high level of fidelity in a short time interval considering that each partner focuses on his own discipline and, then, results are collected, assembled in "black boxes" and used in automated manners.

Figure 1.26: Reduced number of interconnections among partners thanks to CPACS technology. [21]

Figure 1.27: Initial AGILE competence Map.

1.3 Thesis Outline

This thesis work is mainly focused on the integration procedure of the Noise Tool ATTILA++ [22], developed by the *Design of Aircraft and Flight technologies research group* (DAF) of *University of Naples Federico II*, in the AGILE 4.0 project with the creation of different Python scripts successively used in the RCE workflow to make possible the MDO logic of AGILE 4.0 project itself. The secondary results achieved concurrently to this main work are:

- The possibility to edit certification profiles for both Take-Off and Landing;
- The printing of Noise Footprints for both certification phases at different Noise certification regulations;
- The possibility to edit Engine Noise contribution in function of BPR for a Turbo-Fan engine.

The thesis outline is the following one:

- **Chapter 1:** Extensive overview on the theoretical background of Noise evaluation, Noise certification, Noise emissions' improvements and MDO logic applied to AGILE 4.0 project;
- **Chapter 2:** In the first part, there is a complete discussion on the basic elements of acoustics, applied to the aviation word, and a preliminary overview on the certification regulations used to evaluate Noise emissions; while, in the second part, there is an extensive description of ATTILA++ Noise Tool, starting from calculation method applied for it and going on with the input setting and the output management;
- **Chapter 3:** In the first part, there is the core of this thesis on all scripts made to integrate ATTILA++ Tool in the RCE workflow and, so, in the AGILE 4.0 project. In the secondary part, there is the exhaustive description of Python code on Noise Trajectory evaluation at different input parameters and different certifications. In the end there is the description of the Python code, exploited to print Noise Footprints for every practical condition;

- **Chapter 4:** Showing of Noise results for a Turbo-Fan engine aircraft of 90 passengers at different engine noise emissions, using a variable BPR, and for a Turbo-Prop engine aircraft of 19 passengers, certified for both CS-25 and CS-23 certification regulations.

2

Noise Tool Methodology

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2.1 Introduction

Main core of this thesis work will be the complete description of how Noise Tool will work and how this tool has been integrated in the AGILE 4.0 project with, in addition, several upgrades about test's trajectories setting and output's printing in a graphic way. Being more precise, first of all there will be a summary of the main acoustics' elements that are going to be used in the Noise Tool, in order to evaluate all acoustic emissions of a certain aircraft, and, then, there will be an in-depth analysis about Noise certification procedures, described in the Chapter 4 (Regulation CS-25) and Chapter 10 (Regulation CS-23) of the Annex 16.

Going on, the working way of ATTILA++ Noise Tool will be analysed in detail, focusing on how the input must be set to perform all possible calculations and

analysing the specific calculation method adopted for it; after these, output file and results' plotting will be viewed to better understand the output file scheme and how it is possible to work on it.

2.2 Basic Elements of Aviation Acoustic

2.2.1 Noise Definitions

Noise Tool, that is going to be used and to be integrated, finds its usefulness in the Noise estimation and calculation; for this reason, as first step in this thesis work, it is necessary to define what is "noise". Noise, or in general sound, is a vibration that propagates as an acoustic wave through a transmission medium and, in general, the region in which the wave travels is called *Sound Field*.

Talking about sound or noise, the main driver of them is their frequency, considering that, due to its sinusoidal trend, sound has all the typical characteristics of oscillatory phenomenon. Frequency is the inverse of time spent by the acoustic wave to complete a single cycle, called period, and the measure unit is the *Hertz* (Hz); frequency can be associated to the wavelength of sound itself and sound speed with the equation 2.1:

$$f = \frac{1}{T_p} = \frac{c}{\lambda} \quad (2.1)$$

where the wavelength, λ , is the distance between two consecutive wave-fronts which correspond to the same phase on the wave; instead, the sound speed is function of ambient temperature, T_∞ , the specific gas constant R_a and the specific heats of air γ_a , as shown in the equation 2.2:

$$c = \sqrt{\gamma_a T_\infty R_a} \quad ; \quad where \quad \begin{cases} R_a = 287.05 JKg^{-1}K^{-1} \\ \gamma_a = 1.4 \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

A generic sound or noise has to be analysed as a physical magnitude distributed over a large range of frequencies and this is the reason why it is important to consider in which way this noise signal can be split through the Fourier Transform. So, breaking down a generic noise signal with this procedure, The Fourier series corresponding to the periodic function $f(t)$, which can be obtained as shown below:

$$f(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k \cos\left(\frac{2\pi kt}{T_p}\right) + B_k \sin\left(\frac{2\pi kt}{T_p}\right) \quad (2.3)$$

where the specific components T_p , A_k , B_k can be defined in the following way:

$$A_0 = \frac{1}{T_p} \int_0^{T_p} f(t) dt \quad (2.4)$$

$$A_k = \frac{2}{T_p} \int_0^{T_p} f(t) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi kt}{T_p}\right) dt \quad (2.5)$$

$$B_k = \frac{1}{T_p} \int_0^{T_p} f(t) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi kt}{T_p}\right) dt \quad (2.6)$$

The previous mathematical approach is not sufficient to clarify noise signal study; for this reason, a specific division of frequency range has been theorized to find out a solution to "discretize" frequency domain itself and, nowadays, this division is applied in function of the third octave bands. Bands definition has been made on the hypothesis of constant percentage bandwidth, where the frequency interval increases as the frequency increases, and, to classify an octave band, the center frequency f_i , that is the geometric mean of its limiting frequencies (f_u = upper frequency; f_l = lower frequency), has been used:

$$f_i = \sqrt{f_u f_l} \quad (2.7)$$

Reason why the frequency bandwidth division is called *One-third-octave bands* is due to the fact that the ratio between the two band limits and between two consecutive band centers is equal to one third (see equation 2.8).

$$\frac{\Delta f}{f_i} = 2^{\frac{1}{6}} - 2^{-\frac{1}{6}} \quad (2.8)$$

Following this approach it is possible to calculate all one-third octave bands in the frequency bandwidth between 1 Hz and 20 000 Hz (Fig.2.1), that is the max audible frequency for the human ear (the lower limit is, instead, 20 Hz).

Comparison of 1-octave and $\frac{1}{3}$ -octave bands

1 OCTAVE			$\frac{1}{3}$ OCTAVE			
<i>Lower cutoff frequency (Hz)</i>	<i>Center frequency (Hz)</i>	<i>Upper cutoff frequency (Hz)</i>	<i>Lower cutoff frequency (Hz)</i>	<i>Center frequency (Hz)</i>	<i>Upper cutoff frequency (Hz)</i>	
11	16	22	14.1	16	17.8	
			17.8		20	22.4
			22.4		25	28.2
22	31.5	44	28.2	31.5	35.5	
			35.5		40	44.7
			44.7		50	56.2
44	63	88	56.2	63	70.8	
			70.8		80	89.1
			89.1		100	112
88	125	177	112	125	141	
			141		160	178
			178		200	224
177	250	355	224	250	282	
			282		315	355
			355		400	447
355	500	710	447	500	562	
			562		630	708
			708		800	891
710	1,000	1,420	891	1,000	1,122	
			1,122		1,250	1,413
			1,413		1,600	1,778
1,420	2,000	2,840	1,778	2,000	2,239	
			2,239		2,500	2,818
			2,818		3,150	3,548
2,840	4,000	5,680	3,548	4,000	4,467	
			4,467		5,000	5,623
			5,623		6,300	7,079
5,680	8,000	11,360	7,079	8,000	8,913	
			8,913		10,000	11,220
			11,220		12,220	14,130
11,360	16,000	22,720	14,130	16,000	17,780	
			17,780		20,000	22,390

Figure 2.1: One-third-octave bands in human audible bandwidth.

2.2.2 Principal Sound Metrics

Sound Pressure

A generic sound or noise in a physical meaning is a pressure disturbance caused by the noise source; in function of this aspect, sound can be seen as a fluctuation or vibration of a medium and the main physical magnitude, used to describe a certain sound, is the *Pressure Level*, i.e. the instantaneous value of the fluctuating pressure disturbance on ambient pressure. The theoretical approach to define sound pressure is based on the idea that it is an harmonic function of time t , caused by a specific sound source:

$$p'(t) = \frac{A}{r} \cos \left[\omega \left(t - \frac{r}{c} \right) \right] \quad (2.9)$$

Where A is the wave amplitude at unitary distance from the source, ω is the angular frequency, expressed in $rad * s^{-1}$ and r is the distance between source and receiver; however, this equation is valid only in the free-field condition, i.e. a sound field in which the effects of obstacles are negligible in the space of interest.

Effective Sound Pressure

Even if the conventional definition of sound pressure is the one described in paragraph 2.2.2, normally, the *Effective Sound Pressure* is the most often used measure of the magnitude of a sound signal. Reason why this is the most used one is that it is the root mean square value of the instantaneous sound pressures over one period of time:

$$p = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T_p} \int_0^{T_p} p'(t)^2 dt} \quad (2.10)$$

In addition, if two or more independent sound sources produce pressure disturbances at different frequency and simultaneously, the expression of the resulting effective sound pressure is the root mean-square of each contribution:

$$p = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2} \quad (2.11)$$

Sound Pressure Level

Observing sound pressure and effective sound pressure equations, it is clear that working with them becomes really difficult, not only for the basic complexity of their definition, but mainly for the wide distance of orders of magnitude between different sound disturbances' values; for this reason, it has been established a conventional measure's unit in logarithmic scale, known as *Decibel scale* (dB):

$$SPL = 10 \text{Log} \left(\frac{p^2}{p_{ref}^2} \right) \quad (2.12)$$

where $p_{ref} = 2 * 10^{-5}$ Pa is the reference pressure, corresponding to the sound pressure audible threshold. Usage of logarithmic scale gives different important advantages: a SPL equals to 0 dB indicates the theoretical "absence" of sound, due to the fact that the effective sound pressure is equal to the reference pressure, i.e. the lower audible limit; negative values of SPL mean that not audible sounds have been measured. Probably, the most important advantage due to logarithmic scale is the possibility to better understand sound pressure changes between different sound disturbances; in fact, normally, a change of 1 dB corresponds to the smallest change to be perceptible by the human ear, while a 3 dB change starts to be well discernible and from a mathematical point of view this increase corresponds to a doubling of sound pressure.

As it happens with Sound Pressure, if two or more independent sound sources produce pressure disturbances at the same frequency, the expression of the resulting sound level does not simply consist of the arithmetic sum of the individual SPL values, due to logarithmic laws, but rather it becomes the following one:

$$SPL = 10 \text{Log} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n 10^{\frac{SPL_i}{10}} \right) \quad (2.13)$$

2.2.3 Integral sound metrics

Basic Sound Metrics describe the sound pressure of a certain source in function of the specific reference frequency band, that comes from the one-third octave

discretization, made on the total audible frequency bandwidth; for this reason, the next step, regarding sound pressure measurements, consists in the usage of integral metrics, i.e. a sum of all measurements for every frequency bands.

Overall Sound Pressure Level

Basing on the integral approach, the *Overall Sound Pressure Level* (OASPL) is the first integral sound metrics normally adopted; in fact, it is the logarithmic addition of all discrete spectral sound pressure levels:

$$OASPL = 10 \text{Log} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n 10^{\frac{SPL_i}{10}} \right) \quad (2.14)$$

Where the n number corresponds to all one-third octaves considered to sum; in this way, the OASPL gives the opportunity to have a single figure of merit that summarizes the level of acoustic energy contained by the entire sound signal.

Noisiness Effect and Perceived Noise Level

All previous measurements have been defined in the absolute way, so without considering the human ear's perception; the human ear's perception effect has an important action on the effective SPL, because of the capability of the human ear to perceive a certain noise, and it is important to consider, also, how this effect varies between people, due to the fact that people, ageing, lose capability to perceive sounds at frequencies in the extreme range of human audible sounds (near frequencies of 20 Hz and 20 000 Hz).

In function of this aspect, different studies have been done to find out theoretical relations to explain and estimate this effect and some specific iso-levels curves, called *Equal-Loudness Contours*, which have been estimated by *Kryter* in 1960 [23]; these studies led to the discovery of the curves shown in Fig.2.2.

Figure 2.2: Equal Noisiness curves (K.D. Kryter, 1960).

For these curves the measure's unit is the *noy*, that is the equivalent of decibel unit but applied to noisiness correction; in fact, the idea is that, as it is possible to see in Fig.2.2, a SPL of 40 noys can be eared by the human ear at different frequencies, but it will corresponds to different dB values on varying of frequency value; basically, these curves show how human perception of a certain sound changes in function of reference frequency, even if, in absolute, the dB value should be the

same on varying of the frequency.

In function of this aspect, the relation between noy and SPL can be expressed by the *Overall Perceived Noisiness*, N , that is defined as follows:

$$N = n_{max} + 0.15 \sum_{i=6}^{29} n_i - n_{max} \quad (2.15)$$

Where n_{max} is the greatest noy value and i is the band number (with reference to Fig.2.8). It should be noted that only bands ranging from 50 Hz to 10 000 Hz are considered, due to the fact that they are the bands to which the human ear is sensitive.

In addition, specific weighting functions can be added to measurements of sound pressures, with the purpose to evaluate quantitatively sound level in function of the volume generated by it; these functions are function of frequency and they can be distinguished in three main weighted functions(see Fig.2.3):

- **A-Weighted function;**
- **B-Weighted function;**
- **C-Weighted function;**

In conclusion, the typical parameter used to evaluate noisiness effect on sound pressure level is the *Perceived Noise Level* (PNL) that can be obtained from the overall noy level N , through the following equation:

$$PNL = 40 + \frac{10}{\text{Log}2} \text{Log}N \quad (2.16)$$

Figure 2.3: Weighted functions curves. [24]

Effective Perceived Noise Level

All previous metrics basically depend on time and, for this reason, a possible solution to describe, with a single relevant value, the noise that varies in a range along a period, applied to the PNL, is the *Effective Perceived Noise Level* (EPNL) that is the time integral of the noise function $PNL(t)$ over the noise event duration, normalized to a reference duration of 10 seconds (this expression can be defined in the continuous form and in the "discretized" form):

$$EPNL = 10 \text{ Log} \left(\frac{1}{T_0} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} 10^{\frac{PNL(t)}{10}} dt \right) ; \text{ where } T_0 = 10 \text{ sec} \quad (2.17)$$

$$EPNL = 10 \text{ Log} \left[\frac{1}{T_0} \sum_{i=i_1}^{i_2} 10^{\frac{PNL(t)}{10}} \Delta t \right] ; \text{ where } T_0 = 10 \text{ sec} \quad (2.18)$$

Tone Correction on PNL and EPNL

Sometimes, the discrete frequency components of a sound signal pronounce spectral irregularities and sound perceived by human ears increases; this is the reason why the ICAO developed a procedure to correct this effect, that is called *Tone Correction*; naturally, this procedure has to be applied to PNL and, consequently, this correction will affect the EPNL too. Idea of tone correction procedure is to evaluate the slopes due to the spectral irregularities and, in function of this slopes and the reference frequency one-third octave band, several correction factors must be estimated (see Fig.2.4); in the end, the specific correction factor C_{Max} has to be added to PNL value:

$$PNLT = PNL + C_{Max} \quad (2.19)$$

Frequency f , Hz	Level difference F , dB	Tone correction C , dB
$50 \leq f < 500$	$1\frac{1}{2} \leq F < 3$	$F/3 - \frac{1}{2}$
	$3 \leq F < 20$	$F/6$
	$20 \leq F$	$3\frac{1}{2}$
$500 \leq f \leq 5\,000$	$1\frac{1}{2} \leq F < 3$	$2F/3 - 1$
	$3 \leq F < 20$	$F/3$
	$20 \leq F$	$6\frac{1}{2}$
$5\,000 < f \leq 10\,000$	$1\frac{1}{2} \leq F < 3$	$F/3 - \frac{1}{2}$
	$3 \leq F < 20$	$F/6$
	$20 \leq F$	$3\frac{1}{2}$

Figure 2.4: Tone correction factors (ICAO Annex 16, Volume I). [1]

It is clear that this procedure must be repeated whenever a sound level measurement has been performed.

2.3 Noise Certification Test's Procedures

As it has been anticipated in the paragraph 1.2.2, it is necessary to define specific test's procedures thanks which it is possible to acquire all main noise emissions of a certain aircraft and, then, these results must be compared to the limits that come from the regulations. As anticipated, the main document, where procedures, limits and related aspects have been described, is the Annex 16 Volume 1 [1]; this document, moreover, is divided in different chapters in function of the aircraft's type, the aircraft's weight and the aircraft's engine. About ATTILA++ Noise Tool, the chapters needed to perform tool's working are Chapter 4 (it refers to all aircraft regulated by FAR 25) and Chapter 10 (it refers to all aircraft regulated by FAR 23); moreover, it is important to underline that these chapters are the last updates about FAR 25 and FAR 23 (the older chapters that refers to these regulations are Chapter 3 and Chapter 6).

2.3.1 Chapter 4 CS-25 Aircraft

In Chapter 4 of Annex 16 Volume 1 the tests cases for the Approach condition and the Take-Off condition have been described, highlighting, first of all, the specific flight parameters that have to be assigned to perform the specific regulation profile; then, there is an overview on the related environmental parameters that have to be respected to perform, under the appropriate conditions, the specific test case; in the end, all noise limitations in function of different drivers have been showed.

First of all it is important to define the applicability of this chapter, so there is a classification of the specific aircraft that can be certified following the standards described in the chapter itself; to be more precise, with the exception of those aircraft, which require a runway length of 610 m or less at maximum certificated mass, as established by the airworthiness, or Propeller-Driven aircraft designed and used in agriculture or firefight, the aircraft acceptable for chapter 4 are:

- **All Subsonic Jet Aeroplanes and Propeller-Driven Aeroplanes**, including their derived versions, with a maximum certificated take-off mass of 55 000 kg and over for which the application for a Type Certificate was submitted on or after 1 January 2006 and before 31 December 2017; (citation from [1])
- **All Subsonic Jet Aeroplanes**, including their derived versions, with a maximum certificated take-off mass of less than 55 000 kg for which the application for a Type Certificate was submitted on or after 1 January 2006 and before 31 December 2020; (citation from [1])
- **All Propeller-Driven Aeroplanes**, including their derived versions, with a maximum certificated take-off mass of over 8 618 kg and less than 55 000 kg, for which the application for a Type Certificate was submitted on or after 1 January 2006 and before 31 December 2020; (citation from [1])
- **All Subsonic Jet Aeroplanes and All Propeller-Driven Aeroplanes** certificated originally as satisfying Annex 16, Volume I, Chapter 3 or Chapter 5, for which re-certification to Chapter 4 is requested. (citation from [1])

In addition, in Chapter 4 there is a specification that establishes that, by recognition from a Contracting State, for Jet aeroplanes and Propeller-Driven aeroplanes over 8 618 kg maximum certificated take-off mass on its registry do not require demonstration of compliance with the provisions of the Standards of Annex 16, Volume I if these aircraft are characterized by the following aspects:

- Gear down flight with one or more retractable landing gear down during the entire flight; (citation from [1])
- Spare engine and nacelle carriage external to the skin of the aeroplane (and return of the pylon or other external mount); (citation from [1])
- Time-limited engine and/or nacelle changes, where the change in type design specifies that the aircraft may not be operated for a period of more than 90 days unless compliance with the provisions of Annex 16, Volume I, is shown for that change in type design. This applies only to changes resulting from a required maintenance action. (citation from [1])

Take-Off

The first aspect to underline about noise certification is the assignment of reference noise measurement points and for the Take-Off profile there is a preliminary distinction between the Lateral problem and the Fly-Over problem: the Lateral test case refers to the starting phase of Take-Off profile, so starting from the rolling phase until the climbing phase after the overtaking of the virtual obstacle (that is defined in function of the FAR 25 regulation); instead the Fly-Over test case is the continuation of Lateral case and, for this reason, it starts with the ending of the first Take-Off's Climb and the beginning of the Cut-Back correction (see paragraph 1.2.4).

In function of this classification, chapters 3-4 define the lateral full-power reference noise measurement point that, for Jet aircraft, is on a line parallel to and 450 m from the runway centre line, where the noise level is a maximum during Take-Off, while, for Propeller-Driven aircraft, it is on the extended centre line of the runway 650 m, vertically below the climb-out flight path at full take-off power; instead, about Fly-Over case, chapters 3-4 define the Fly-Over reference noise measurement point that is on the extended centre line of the runway and at a distance of 6.5 km from the start of roll. Clearly, if there is a variation on reference flight paths with respect to test case, the same variations or corrections must be applied to the reference noise measurement points. Moreover, during Lateral case and during a single test, every reference point has to have a symmetrical point with respect to the center line, in order to acquire noise emissions in both sides of the runway and/or Take-Off's profile.

Going on, the regulation defines the limits for noise emissions, expressed in EPNdB, (see Fig.2.5) in function of aircraft's weight through a logarithmic law and in function of the number of engine, regarding the Fly-Over's limits (see Fig.2.6).

M = Maximum take-off mass in 1 000 kg		0	20.2	28.6	35	48.1	280	385	400	
Lateral full-power noise level (EPNdB) All aeroplanes		94		$80.87 + 8.51 \log M$					103	
Flyover noise levels (EPNdB)	2 engines or less	89			$66.65 + 13.29 \log M$				101	
	3 engines	89		$69.65 + 13.29 \log M$					104	
	4 engines or more	89		$71.65 + 13.29 \log M$					106	

Figure 2.5: Take-Off noise emissions limits described in Chapter 4 . [1]

Figure 2.6: Maximum noise levels at Fly-Over reference Noise measurement point in function of number of engines. [1]

The Appendix 2 of Annex 16, Volume 1, describes the relations used to define these limits.

It is important to underline that these limits are not so pressing, rather the regulation defines trade-offs for the overtaking of one or two limit for a single measurement point (naturally, this is valid for both Take-Off and Approach test's cases):

- The sum of excesses shall not be greater than 3 EPNdB (so not greater than double of noise emission limit); (citation from [1])
- Any excess at any single point shall not be greater than 2 EPNdB; (citation from [1])

- Any excess shall be offset by corresponding reductions at the other point or points. (citation from [1])

In conclusion, the Chapters 3-4 define all references procedures to perform the noise's tests in the best possible conditions; moreover, it is possible to distinguish the general conditions and the specific profile conditions.

About general conditions, the regulation confirm the necessity to perform any kind of test respecting airworthiness requirements and the approval of certificating authority and, then, it establishes the reference atmospheric conditions:

- **Atmospheric Pressure at sea level** of 1013.25 hPa, decreasing with altitude at a rate defined by the *ICAO Standard Atmosphere*; (citation from [1])
- **Ambient Air Temperature at sea level** of 25°C, decreasing with altitude at a rate defined by the *ICAO Standard Atmosphere*; (citation from [1])
- **Constant Relative Humidity** of 70 per cent; (citation from [1])
- **Zero Wind**; (citation from [1])
- For the purpose of defining the reference take-off profiles for both take-off and lateral noise measurements, the **Runway Gradient** is zero; (citation from [1])
- **The Reference Atmosphere** in terms of temperature and relative humidity is considered to be homogeneous (i.e. ambient temperature 25°C and relative humidity 70 per cent) for the purpose of calculating the reference sound attenuation rate due to atmospheric absorption and the reference speed of sound used in the calculation of the reference sound propagation geometry. (citation from [1])

Regarding the Take-Off profile definition, the regulation is really accurate to set the flights parameters that the pilot has to follow to perform the Take-Off path; first of all, the mass of the aeroplane at the brake release must be the maximum take-off mass at which the noise certification is requested; then, the average engine take-off thrust or power must be used from the start of Take-Off to a specified point, which altitude above runway is function of number of engines (citation from [1]):

- **Two Engines or Less:** 300 m (984 ft);

- **Three Engines:** 260 m (853 ft);
- **Four Engines or More:** 210 m (689 ft).

Then, after reaching this point, the thrust or power must not be reduced below that one required to maintain a climb gradient of 4% or level flight with one engine inoperative in case of multiple engines (Thrust or Power reduction leads to an engine's throttle reduction causing the so called *Cut-Back Manoeuvre*, that will close the test case). In the end, the regulation sets the speed of the aircraft during all profile path:

- For those aircraft for which the applicable airworthiness requirements define V_2 , the speed should be the all-engines operating take-off climb speed, which should be at least $V_2 + 10$ kt but not greater than $V_2 + 20$ kt and which should be attained as soon as practicable after lift-off and be maintained throughout the take-off noise certification test. (citation from [1])
- For those aeroplanes for which the applicable airworthiness requirements do not define V_2 , the speed should be the take-off speed at 50 ft plus an increment of 10 kt but not greater than 20 kt, or the minimum climb speed, whichever speed is greater. Also in this case, this speed should be attained as soon as practicable after lift-off and be maintained throughout the take-off noise certification test. (citation from [1])

Figure 2.7: Take-Off reference flight path.

In this way, the typical Lateral and Flyover profile can be obtained , as it has been shown in Fig.2.7.

In the end, it is possible to observe some results obtained from several aircraft, tested by *EASA*, in order to understand the typical values' range in function of the aircraft's weight and in function of the various engine's types (it is known how significant is the engine contribution on the total noise emissions). In Fig.2.8 the Lateral case's results for the Turbo-Jet aircraft have been shown; while in Fig.2.9 the Lateral case's results for the Heavy Turbo-Prop aircraft have been shown (in this case and in the Fly-Over one, a single engine's type family has been shown).

Figure 2.8: Lateral test case's noise emissions for several Turbo-Jet EASA-certified aircraft on varying of MTOW and in function of several engine's types with which aircraft are equipped (PW-1000 Series, CF-34 Series, CFM56-7B Series). [25]

The same analyse can be done for the Fly-Over test case and, in particular, in Fig.2.10 the Turbo-Jet's results have been shown; while in Fig.2.11 the Heavy Turbo-Prop's results have been shown.

Figure 2.9: Lateral test case’s noise emissions for several Heavy Turbo-Prop EASA-certified aircraft on varying of MTOW and in function of several engine’s types with which aircraft are equipped (PW-100 Series). [25]

Figure 2.10: Fly-Over test case’s noise emissions for several Turbo-Jet EASA-certified aircraft on varying of MTOW and in function of several engine’s types with which aircraft are equipped (PW-1000 Series, CF-34 Series, CFM56-7B Series). [25]

Figure 2.11: Fly-Over test case's noise emissions for several Heavy Turbo-Prop EASA-certified aircraft on varying of MTOW and in function of several engine's types with which aircraft are equipped (PW-100 Series). [25]

Approach

Regulation scheme about Approach, basically, is the same of the Take-Off test case with the obvious differences in terms of limits and flight parameters. Unlike Take-Off case, where there is the distinction between Lateral and Fly-Over phases, in the Approach case there is no division of flight phases and this is the reason why the approach reference noise measurement point is a single point on the ground, on the extended centre line of the runway, 2 000 m from the threshold [1]. On level ground, this corresponds to a position 120 m vertically below the 3° descent path originating from a point 300 m beyond the threshold (the discussion on test noise measurement points not located at the reference noise measurement points is valid for the Approach case too).

About maximum noise levels, in the Approach case there is the same logarithmic law showed for the Lateral and the Fly-Over cases (see Fig.2.12), but this time

there is no dependency on engine's number; naturally, the Appendix 2 of Annex 16, Volume 1, describes the relations used to define these limits and, as it happens in the Take-Off case, the relaxation of these limits are the same applied before.

Approach noise level (EPNdB) All aeroplanes	98	$86.03 + 7.75 \log M$	105
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Figure 2.12: Approach noise emissions limits described in Chapter 4 . [1]

Also in the Approach case, several Noise certification reference procedures about general conditions and airworthiness requirement have to be respected to perform this test; moreover, there are specific Approach reference procedures related to the flight parameters to set, in order to obtain the right Approach's test path:

- The aeroplane has to be stabilized and following a 3° glide path; (citation from [1])
- A steady approach speed of $V_{REF} + 10$ kt, with thrust or power stabilized, has to be maintained over the measurement point; (citation from [1])
- The mass of the aeroplane at the touchdown shall be the maximum landing mass permitted in the approach configuration; (citation from [1])
- The most critical configuration, in terms of noise emissions, with normal deployment of aerodynamic control surfaces including lift and drag producing devices, has to be used. (citation from [1])

Figure 2.13: Approach reference flight path.

Following all these drivers, the typical Approach flight path, showed in Fig.2.13, can be obtained.

In the end it is possible to observe, also in this test case, some results obtained from several aircraft, tested by EASA, in order to understand the typical values' range in function of the aircraft's weight and in function of the various engine's types. In Fig.2.14 the noise results for the Turbo-Jet aircraft have been shown; while in Fig.2.15 the noise results for the Heavy Turbo-Prop aircraft have been shown (in this case, as it happens for Lateral and Fly-Over cases, a single engine's type family has been shown).

Figure 2.14: Approach test case's noise emissions for several Turbo-Jet EASA-certified aircraft on varying of MTOW and in function of several engine's types with which aircraft are equipped (PW-1000 Series, CF-34 Series, CFM56-7B Series). [25]

Figure 2.15: Approach test case's noise emissions for several Heavy Turbo-Prop EASA-certified aircraft on varying of MTOW and in function of several engine's types with which aircraft are equipped (PW-100 Series). [25]

2.3.2 Chapter 10 CS-23 Aircraft

Referring to a different category of aircraft, Chapter 10 is the update of Chapter 6, where this one describes everything about noise regulation of Light Propeller-Driven aircraft. On the basis of this aspect, it is important to underline that Chapter 10 will follow the same scheme, seen for Chapter 4, with the main difference that there is no necessity to perform the Approach test case; so basically, in Chapter 10 only the Take-Off case will be discussed with in addition the "simplifications" due to the absence of Cut-Back's manoeuvre and Fly-Over phase.

As it happens for Chapter 4, the first section of this chapter is related to the applicability, i.e. a classification of the specific aircraft that can be certified following the standards described in the chapter itself; being more precise, the acceptable aircraft are:

1. **All Propeller-Driven aircraft** with a certificated take-off mass not exceeding 8 618 kg, except those aircraft designed and used for aerobatic purposes, agriculture or firefighting and self-sustaining powered sailplanes; (citation from [1])
2. **Propeller-Driven aircraft** for which the application for the Type Certificate was submitted on or after 17 November 1988; (citation from [1])
3. **Derived Versions** for which the application for certification of the change in type design was submitted on or after 17 November 1988; (citation from [1])
4. **Single-Engined aircraft**, except float planes and amphibians, including their derived versions, for which the application for the Type Certificate was submitted on or after 4 November 1999; (citation from [1])
5. **Derived Versions of Single-Engined aircraft**, except float planes and amphibians, for which the application for the Type Certificate was submitted before 4 November 1999 and for which the application for certification of the change in type design was submitted on or after 4 November 1999; (citation from [1])

The first important difference with respect to Chapter 4 consists in the usage of another type of sound metric, that for Chapter 10 has to be the maximum level of the A-weighted sound pressure with reference to the square of the standard reference sound pressure (p_0) of 20 micropascals (μPa), L_{ASmax} . Going on, this time there is only one reference noise measurement point valid for the entire Take-Off test case; the Take-Off reference noise measurement point is the one on the extended centre line of the runway at a distance of 2 500 m from the start of take-off roll [1] and the noise emissions acquired from this point do not have any relaxation on the certification limit, but the noise levels have to be at the most equal to the maximum noise levels. Also in this case, the maximum noise levels can be calculated in function of aircraft's weight but, in this case, there are two types of logarithmic laws to consider: the a) case (see Fig.2.16) is valid, in fact, just for the aircraft cited in points 1), 2), 3) of previous list; while the b) case (see Fig.2.16) is valid for the aircraft cited in points 4) and 5) of previous list. Naturally, in the Appendix

6 of Annex 16, Volume 1, all relations and mathematical laws used to calculate noise emissions have been described in detail.

10.4 a):

M = Maximum take-off mass in 1 000 kg	0	0.6	1.4	8.618
Noise level in dB(A)	76	$83.23 + 32.67 \log M$		88

10.4 b):

M = Maximum take-off mass in 1 000 kg	0	0.57	1.5	8.618
Noise level in dB(A)	70	$78.71 + 35.70 \log M$		85

Figure 2.16: Take-Off noise emissions limits (dBA) described in Chapter 10 [1].

As it happens for Chapter 4, the regulation confirms the necessity to perform any kind of test respecting airworthiness requirements and the approval of certifying authority and necessity to adjust noise results by the methods outlined in Appendix 6; moreover the reference atmospheric conditions, just discussed for Chapter 4, have to be confirmed to perform tests in the right way. In the end, the flights parameters, that pilot has to follow to perform the Take-Off path, can be described, dividing them in two phases of flight; during the first phase, that basically corresponds to the grounding and lift-off phases, the specific conditions to respect are:

- Take-off power used from the brake release point to the point at which the height of 50 ft above the runway is reached; (citation from [1])
- A constant take-off configuration selected by the applicant; (citation from [1])
- The mass of the aeroplane being the maximum take-off mass at which the noise certification is requested; (citation from [1])
- The length of this first phase corresponding to the length given in the airworthiness data for a take-off on a level paved runway. (citation from [1])

The second phase, instead, corresponds to the climb phase of a typical Take-Off profile and in this case the specific conditions to respect are:

- The beginning of the second phase corresponding to the end of the first phase; (citation from [1])

- The aeroplane in the climb configuration with landing gear up, if retractable, and flap setting corresponding to normal climb; (citation from [1])
- The speed equal to the best rate of climb speed, V_Y ; (citation from [1])
- Take-off power and, for aeroplanes equipped with variable pitch or constant speed propellers, RPM maintained throughout the second phase. If airworthiness limitations do not permit the application of take-off power and RPM up to the reference point, then take-off power and RPM shall be maintained for as long as is permitted by such limitations and thereafter at maximum continuous power and RPM. Limiting of time for which take-off power and RPM shall be used in order to comply with this chapter shall not be permitted. The reference height shall be calculated assuming climb gradients appropriate to each power setting used. (citation from [1])

In this way, the typical Take-Off flight path for Chapter 10's aircraft can be obtained, as it has been shown in Fig.2.17.

Figure 2.17: Take-Off reference flight path for Chapter 10 regulation [1].

In Fig.2.18 it is possible to compare the noise emissions of several Light Turbo-Prop aircraft belonging to the regulation' aircraft's category, in order to better

understand the order of magnitude of the typical noise emissions of the CS-23 regulation's aircraft. It is important to underline that greater attention is given to the MTOW of the aircraft, that is the main driver with which it is possible to make a comparison (there are several engine's type that have been evaluated).

Figure 2.18: Take-Off test case's noise emissions for several Light Turbo-Prop EASA-certified aircraft on varying of MTOW with the add of the linear interpolation trends for the certification limits and the noise emissions. [25]

2.4 Noise Tool ATTILA++ Overview

2.4.1 General Overview

The "instrument", that is going to be integrated in this thesis work, is the Noise Estimation 's Tool *ATTILA++* [22]; the *ATTILA++* Tool is the actual final form of the noise tool developed by the *ADORNO Project* [26] to evaluate the prediction of aircraft noise, where *ADORNO* (*Aircraft Design and nOise RatiNg for regiOnal aircraft*) is an European project that focuses on the development of aircraft models for a regional aircraft engine platform. As anticipated, *ATTILA++*

is the improvement of the first version of this tool, that was ATTILA, acronym of *Aircraft noise predicTion IncLuding performAnce*; this software has been originally developed and coded in MATLAB [27] at UNINA by the Vibro-Acoustics research group [28] and it was designed to evaluate noise emissions of a turbofan civil aircraft, referring on the noise regulation [1], described in the paragraph 2.3.1. Instead, ATTILA++ finds its main improvement in the re-coding in C++ environment, that leads to the implementation of *Object-Oriented Programming* (OOP) paradigms to redesign the software. The general working of ATTILA++ tool is based on the usage of input files in the *.csv* format and on the outputting of *.txt* format files [22]; in this way the software finds an important advantage in the possibility to edit more easily all the input files and data and also in the availability of more user-friendly output files. In general, this tool has to satisfy various requirements that are:

- **The arbitrary definition of flight paths**, as well as microphone locations;
- **The opportunity to choose which contributions** can be included or not in the calculation of the total noise;
- **The possibility to modify parameters** that are usually assumed constant (gas properties, normative);
- **The not overtaking of run-time** for the calculation of SPL for a single noise source with respect to an agreed threshold.

In the next paragraph all methodologies applied to calculation, that come from the *ESDU* logic, will be described.

2.4.2 ATTILA++ Methodologies

The first aspect to consider, talking about methodologies used in the ATTILA++ Tool [22], is that all the semi-empirical methodologies and theoretical knowledge, exploited for any kind of application, come from the *ESDU* documents. The *ESDU* [29], acronym of *Engineering Sciences Data Unit*, is an engineering advisory organization which provides validated engineering analysis tools in the fields of aerospace engineering, process engineering and structural engineering; its work is monitored and validated by technical committees of experts from industry,

academies and government organizations, involved in this organization. So, in this paragraph all the ESDU papers, that contain the semi-empirical methods of interest, are going to be briefly discussed.

Airframe Noise Emissions Evaluation Methodology

The first contribution that is going to be studied, describing the semi-empirical method applied for it, is the airframe's noise contribution. In terms of ESDU, the *ESDU item no. 90023* [30] provides the specific methodology for airframe noise prediction and it is based on the semi-empirical method developed by *Martin R. Fink* (1977) (as seen in paragraph 1.2.3 this is one of the most important method developed to predict noise emissions). This semi-empirical method exploits aircraft's geometry and operating conditions to perform calculation (see Fig.2.19) and the airframe noise can be calculated summing the single contribution from any selected combination of the following airframe components:

- **Wing** (Conventional or Delta);
- **Horizontal Tail**;
- **Vertical Tail**;
- **Flaps**;
- **Slats**;
- **Main Landing Gears**;
- **Nose Landing Gear**;

It is important to underline that most of interaction effect between noise sources can be considered negligible, so the easiest way to calculate any contribution is with the following relation:

$$SPL = 10 \text{ Log}(p^2) + 10 \text{ Log} \left(\frac{\rho_{\infty,s}^2 c_s^4}{p_{Ref}^2} \right) - 20 \text{ Log} \left(\frac{\rho_{\infty,s}}{\rho_{\infty,r}} \right) \quad (2.20)$$

Where, the subscript s indicates the source location, the subscript r indicates the microphone position and p_{Ref} is the reference pressure.

Figure 2.19: Representation of the airplane-microphone geometric configuration for the airframe noise estimation. In this representation, θ is the polar emission angle while ϕ_f is the azimuth angle. [30]

In particular, the non-dimensional mean-square acoustic pressure p^2 , which equation is given by the relation 2.21, is mainly function of the Strouhal Number (Sr), the spectrum function (F) and the directivity index (DI), which distinguish the noise source of which the equation 2.20 is calculating the noise emissions; in the Appendix A of the *ESDU item No. 90023* there are different functions able to calculate these main drivers.

$$p^2 = \frac{P b_w^2 DI(\theta, \phi_f F(Sr))}{4 \phi r^2 (1 - M \cos\theta)^4} \quad (2.21)$$

Ground Reflection Effect Evaluation Methodology

The Ground Reflection is one of the most important propagation effect (effect that causes an alteration of the sound energy level perceived by a receiver, due to the propagation of the waves through a medium and within the surrounding environment) to consider when the noise calculation is going to be performed; basically it is the difference between the measured SPL at a given emission angle and the SPL at the same emission angle which would occur in the free-field. Therefore, the *ESDU item no. 94035* [31] defines a semi-empirical method to estimate this effect; to be more precise, this method establishes that the sound waves propagate through a still, homogeneous atmosphere with a spherically divergent wave front and, naturally, the flat ground surface assumption is confirmed (see Fig.2.20). To evaluate correctly this effect, first of all, it is necessary to define type of soil, to calculate ground impedance, between the possible following ones:

- Snow;
- Grass;
- Sand or Sandy Soil;
- Limestone Chips, Dirt Roadway;
- Wet Compacted Soil;
- Tarmac, Concrete.

Figure 2.20: Representation of source-receiver geometry for *ESDU item no. 94035*. [31]

Then, the calculation of reflection factor, latter effect and spectrum correction can be done following the detail procedure described in the *ESDU* document;

in the end, the effects of air turbulence on sound propagation can be quantified between the following possibilities:

- **Perfectly Still;**
- **Normally Still;**
- **Moderately Still;**
- **Turbulent.**

Atmospheric Attenuation Effect Evaluation Methodology

The Atmospheric Attenuation is another important effect to consider in the noise estimation and, basically, it is the process by which sound energy is absorbed in travelling through the atmosphere. The *ESDU item no. 78002* [32] contains all information to evaluate this effect and, being more precise, it is possible to calculate the reduction of SPL due to atmospheric attenuation (see equation 2.23), that depends on the attenuation over distance ($I(r)$) (see equation 2.22) and on the sound intensity at the origin ($I(0)$).

$$I(r) = I(0) e^{-mr} \text{ where, } m = \text{intensity attenuation coefficient} \quad (2.22)$$

$$\Delta SPL = 10 \text{ Log} \left[\frac{I(0)}{I(r)} \right] = 434.3mr \quad (2.23)$$

Considering this equation, it is possible to obtain the atmospheric attenuation coefficient α_A :

$$\alpha_A = 434.3 (m_O + m_N + m_C) * r \quad (2.24)$$

Where, m_O is the attenuation coefficient due to oxygen, m_N is the attenuation coefficient due to nitrogen and m_C is the attenuation coefficient due to translation and rotation modes.

In conclusion, the absorption due to molecular vibration is dependent on the maximum intensity loss per wavelength and the frequency at which this loss occurs,

i.e. the *Relaxation Frequency* and for this reason the *ESDU item no. 78002* provides empirical formulas for the estimation of relaxation frequencies and the maximum intensity loss per wavelength.

Lateral Attenuation Effect Evaluation Methodology

Another important propagation effect to consider and estimate is the Lateral Attenuation Effect; this effect can be defined as the difference between the one-third-octave band and sideline free-field sound pressure levels and it depends mainly on distance (it increases with distance) and on elevation angle β (it increases with decreasing of the angle) (see Fig.2.21). The *ESDU item no. 82027* [33] provides two sets of lateral attenuation data to perform calculation, based on the typical engines configurations for Jet aircraft:

- Aircraft with engines mounted below the wing;
- Aircraft with engines mounted in the rear fuselage.

Figure 2.21: Relationship between source and observer for *ESDU item no. 82027*. [33]

Engine Noise Emissions Evaluation Methodology

The last but not the least contribution to evaluate is the engine contribution for which the evaluation methodology's discussion is a little more complex. In fact, for the ATTILA++ tool it is not possible to predict directly the engine noise's emissions, but it needs external input, that are tables of SPL provided for different engine throttle values and for the two engine ratings normally analysed (Take-Off and Approach). The working way of ATTILA++ about the engine noise contribution is

based on an interpolation of the input noise data collected in the external input files and in the end these results will be used to evaluate the final results [22]. It is important to precise that there is a semi-empirical method to estimate the noise emissions of fans and compressors, described in the *ESDU item no. 98008* [34], but it is not implemented in the ATTILA++ Software; moreover, it is important to highlight that these external input files can be defined or through experimental campaigns, performed by the engine manufacturers, or through semi-empirical methodologies, like the ones cited before.

2.4.3 Software Architecture of ATTILA++

To complete the overview on the ATTILA++ software, it can be useful to describe how this is structured, focusing mainly on the input and the output organization. First of all, the ATTILA++ architecture is based on the paradigms of object-oriented programming and this is the reason why this software can be divided and classified in classes, of which any single one will perform a specific purpose; naturally, all these classes have been organized in a complex architecture seen in Fig.2.22.

Figure 2.22: Main architecture and typical analysis workflow of ATTILA++ (v0.8.1). [22]

Observing the software's architecture, the first aspect, that stands out, is the input organization; in fact, all kinds of input, that come from different input files, will be processed by the classes designated to work on them. Then, there is the main core of the software where different classes will process the input data acquired in the preliminary part of tool, calculating the noise contribution of every aircraft's components and the effect that will act on the noise estimation itself; in particular, all classes designated to estimate noise contributions refer to the methodologies seen in the previous chapter and every class will process a single method [22]. In the end, all partial estimations will be reworked through the final classes, designated to evaluate the final results in function of the specific sound metrics chosen by the user; finally, thanks to a case manager class, the sound metrics organization is performed and the output files will be written.

Input Files Classification

In this thesis work there will not be any in-depth analysis on the specific classes used in the ATTILA++ software, rather a quite complete description of the input and output files will be done. About the input files, as anticipated, the important aspect to underline is the format used for them, i.e. the *.csv* format; this format is really useful because it organizes data in a tabular scheme where every parameter or key-word is associated to a single cell of a vector, making easier the data acquisition and data loading from an external source.

Considering this aspect, the classification adopted for the ATTILA++ tool is shown in the following table [22]:

- **Control Parameters:** In the control parameters file occurs the storing of all parameters linked to the setting of tool working and calculation: several parameters will set the working case and the other input file for trajectory and receivers' management; moreover, it is possible to assign what kind of contribution have to be calculated or not, with the possibility to add several correction factors for every contribution's results; in the end, the sound metrics choice and the output management can be managed;

- **Engine:** As it has been described in paragraph 2.4.2, the engine file contains several SPL matrices in function of the frequency at which the sound pressure is acquired and the directivity angle of microphone; moreover every matrix is defined for a specific engine throttle and for the Approach or Take-Off case.
- **Input:** The input file, as its name suggests, contains the main geometric data of any airframe component, as listed in paragraph 2.4.2; moreover the engine's parameters and data for ground reflection have been added in it.
- **Normative:** The normative file defines the one-third-octave frequencies bands used to evaluate noise emissions and the atmospheric parameters, like reference pressure and ISA base temperature;
- **Receivers Files:** The receivers files are a totality of *.csv* files used to define the microphones position in the 3D space of noise's virtual flight test; in addition, in this files, it is possible to set the atmospheric parameters at which the microphone refers, otherwise the ATTILA++ tool will automatically set them with respect to ISA Model; and, if necessary, a linear extrapolation calculation is available. It is important to underline that there is a receivers file for every test case on the basis of regulation seen in paragraph 2.3.1 (Approach, Lateral, Fly-Over);
- **Trajectory Files:** Similar structure finds itself in the generic trajectory file; in fact, in this file the trajectory followed by the aircraft during test case is described with the usage of several *.csv* arrays, that define the 3D coordinates of a single position of the aircraft in a time step and other flight parameters for the same time step, that will be discussed more in detail in next chapters. In this way, a discretized trajectory is performed and, as it happens for receivers file, atmospheric parameters can be set or directly managed by ATTILA++ tool; in the end, the trajectory files have to be written for every test case (Approach, Lateral, Fly-Over) as well.

In addition to the classic test cases, the ATTILA++ tool provides for a fourth case that is a User-defined case [22], which is not examined in depth in this thesis work.

Output Files Classification

The output files' management, instead, exploit the *.txt* format due to the fact that this format gives the possibility to get more easily the output data for any purpose. Considering the cases' management, there is a distinction to consider for the output files too; in particular, the output management starts with the initial folder *RESULTS*, inside which there are the other sub-folders for every test case and in addition a log file where all problems occurred during tool's run have been highlighted. Going on, inside every sub-folder, the tool organizes results and others outputs following the scheme listed below (complete output scheme displayed in Fig.2.24) [22]:

1. <CaseName>: First output file displayed is the output file of microphone which records the highest EPNL value and, in function of parameters set in the Control Parameters file, shows noise results of every chosen sound metric for every contribution selected (see Fig.2.26). Moreover, in the initial part of this file, if selected, microphone's information and trajectory's information are displayed (see Fig.2.25); [22]
2. EPNL_MAP: File that contains EPNL values from all microphones analysed and the microphones position's coordinates(see Fig.2.23); [22]
3. Log file: As it happens for the initial folder, the LOG file contains all information about tool's run and possible errors occurred during the execution; [22]
4. <CaseName>_<index>: Similar to the <CaseName> file, this one refers to a single microphone of those that tool has been analysed; the file's architecture, basically, is the same of <CaseName> file. [22]

EPNL FOOTPRINT	=====						
X;	-0.0;	50.0;	100.0;	150.0;	200.0;	250.0;	
Y;	450.0;	450.0;	450.0;	450.0;	450.0;	450.0;	
Z;	1.2;	1.2;	1.2;	1.2;	1.2;	1.2;	1.2;
EPNL;	103.1;	102.7;	102.1;	101.2;	100.0;		98.4;

Figure 2.23: Example of EPNL_MAP file (ATTILA++ v0.8.1). [22]

Figure 2.24: Arrangement of Output files (ATTILA++ v0.8.1). [22]

```

MICROPHONE POSITIONS =====
X;      1450.0
Y;      450.0
Z;      1.2
Temperature; 298.1
Pressure; 101311.1
Density;  1.2
Sound Speed; 346.2
Kin. Viscosity; 1e-005
Heat Ratio; 1.4

=====

LATERAL TRAJECTORY =====
Time;      0.0;      2.2;      3.1;      3.8;      4.4;      4.9;      5.4;
X;      -0.0;      6.1;      12.2;     18.4;     24.5;     30.6;     36.7;
Y;      -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;
Z;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;
Flight Speed; -0.0;     5.6;     7.9;     9.6;     11.1;     12.3;     13.5;
Throttle Rate; 0.1;      1.0;      1.0;      1.0;      1.0;      1.0;      1.0;
Climb Angle; -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;     -0.0;
Temperature; 298.1;     298.1;     298.1;     298.1;     298.1;     298.1;     298.1;
Pressure; 101311.0; 101311.0; 101311.0; 101311.0; 101311.0; 101311.0; 101311.0;
Density;  1.2;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;      1.2;
Sound Speed; 346.2;     346.2;     346.2;     346.2;     346.2;     346.2;     346.2;
Kin. Viscosity; 0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;
Mach Number; -0.0;     0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;
Time Rec.;  4.4;      6.6;      7.5;      8.1;      8.7;      9.2;      9.7;
Distance; 1518.2;     1512.4;     1506.5;     1500.7;     1494.9;     1489.0;     1483.2;
Theta;    17.2;     17.3;     17.4;     17.4;     17.5;     17.6;     17.7;
Phi;      90.0;     90.0;     90.0;     90.0;     90.0;     90.0;     90.0;
Beta;     0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;      0.0;
=====
    
```

Figure 2.25: Information on microphones and trajectory (ATTILA++ v0.8.1). [22]

WING (WITH ATMOSPHERIC ATTENUATION AND GROUND REFLECTION)										
Time (s);	0.0;	2.2;	3.1;	3.8;	4.4;	4.9;	5.4;	5.8;	6.2;	6.6;
Frequency; SPL (dB);										
50 Hz;	nan;	-116.5;	-108.2;	-103.6;	-100.4;	-98.1;	-96.2;	-94.7;	-93.4;	-92.3;
63 Hz;	nan;	-121.0;	-112.5;	-107.6;	-104.3;	-101.7;	-99.7;	-98.0;	-96.5;	-95.3;
80 Hz;	nan;	-128.5;	-119.8;	-114.8;	-111.2;	-108.6;	-106.4;	-104.5;	-103.0;	-101.6;
100 Hz;	nan;	-138.1;	-129.2;	-124.1;	-120.5;	-117.7;	-115.4;	-113.5;	-111.8;	-110.3;
125 Hz;	nan;	-144.9;	-136.0;	-130.8;	-127.1;	-124.3;	-122.0;	-120.0;	-118.3;	-116.9;
160 Hz;	nan;	-146.9;	-137.9;	-132.7;	-129.0;	-126.2;	-123.8;	-121.8;	-120.1;	-118.6;
200 Hz;	nan;	-146.8;	-137.8;	-132.5;	-128.8;	-125.9;	-123.5;	-121.5;	-119.8;	-118.2;
250 Hz;	nan;	-146.3;	-137.3;	-132.0;	-128.3;	-125.3;	-122.9;	-120.9;	-119.1;	-117.6;
315 Hz;	nan;	-146.0;	-137.0;	-131.7;	-127.9;	-124.9;	-122.5;	-120.5;	-118.7;	-117.1;
400 Hz;	nan;	-146.0;	-137.0;	-131.6;	-127.8;	-124.9;	-122.4;	-120.3;	-118.5;	-116.9;
500 Hz;	nan;	-146.3;	-137.2;	-131.9;	-128.1;	-125.1;	-122.6;	-120.5;	-118.7;	-117.1;
630 Hz;	nan;	-146.9;	-137.9;	-132.5;	-128.7;	-125.7;	-123.2;	-121.1;	-119.3;	-117.6;
800 Hz;	nan;	-147.9;	-138.9;	-133.5;	-129.6;	-126.6;	-124.1;	-122.0;	-120.2;	-118.5;
1000 Hz;	nan;	-149.1;	-140.0;	-134.6;	-130.7;	-127.7;	-125.2;	-123.1;	-121.2;	-119.6;
1250 Hz;	nan;	-150.3;	-141.2;	-135.8;	-131.9;	-128.9;	-126.4;	-124.3;	-122.4;	-120.7;
1600 Hz;	nan;	-152.1;	-143.0;	-137.6;	-133.7;	-130.6;	-128.1;	-126.0;	-124.1;	-122.4;
2000 Hz;	nan;	-154.2;	-145.1;	-139.7;	-135.8;	-132.7;	-130.2;	-128.0;	-126.1;	-124.4;
2500 Hz;	nan;	-157.3;	-148.2;	-142.7;	-138.8;	-135.8;	-133.2;	-131.0;	-129.1;	-127.4;
3150 Hz;	nan;	-162.4;	-153.2;	-147.7;	-143.8;	-140.7;	-138.1;	-135.9;	-134.0;	-132.3;
4000 Hz;	nan;	-170.7;	-161.5;	-156.0;	-152.0;	-148.9;	-146.3;	-144.1;	-142.1;	-140.3;
5000 Hz;	nan;	-183.1;	-173.8;	-168.2;	-164.2;	-161.0;	-158.4;	-156.1;	-154.1;	-152.3;
6300 Hz;	nan;	-202.9;	-193.6;	-188.0;	-183.9;	-180.6;	-177.9;	-175.5;	-173.4;	-171.5;
8000 Hz;	nan;	-235.2;	-225.7;	-220.0;	-215.7;	-212.4;	-209.5;	-207.0;	-204.8;	-202.8;
10000 Hz;	nan;	-282.0;	-272.4;	-266.5;	-262.1;	-258.5;	-255.5;	-252.8;	-250.4;	-248.2;
OASPL (dB);	nan;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;
PNL (PNdB);	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;
PNLT (PNdB);	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;	-inf;
(Tone Corr.);	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;	0.0;
EPNLrT (EPNdB);	48.9									

Figure 2.26: Noise results expressed in all available sound metrics from Wing contribution(ATTILA++ v0.8.1). [22]

2.5 Summary

The sound metrics, certification test cases and the ATTILA++ software descriptions represent the fundamental basis of Integration Tool because they give the input information to understand the integration tool working and it defines the starting points for the updates developed in this thesis work.

3

Noise Tool Integration Procedure

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3.1 Introduction

The previous chapters give a complete overview on the theoretical aspect which the main core of this thesis is based on; therefore, in this chapter there will be the main core of thesis work, that is the complete description of all Python scripts, used to integrate Noise Tool: preliminary, the collaborative approach, seen with the usage of *CPACS* input and output files, the *RCE Workflow* and the *BRICS* tool, will be explained in detail; then, the integration tool, developed on the base of various Python codes (Input, Output, Footprint), will be shown. In the end, the updated functions to manage the trajectories' estimation and the parallel Footprint Tool will be explained.

3.2 MDO Logic, Software and Tools

In function of what is going to be seen in this chapter, it is necessary to start with an overview on how the AGILE 4.0 project operates and on the software used to make operative this project, initially introduced in paragraph 1.2.5. The MDO logic is based on the idea that a complex and substantial project can be split in different works, performed by all partners involved in it. The main problem is represented by the necessity to connect the several works and/or analyses, in order to make the total project faster and higher, in terms of fidelity. The working way, that AGILE choose to adopt, is based on the usage of a common format for input/output files, i.e. the CPACS file [35], and the creation of different tools for every analyse which have been managed in an online workflow, developed thanks to the RCE software [36]; moreover, to make possible the usage and exchange of files in CPACS format in the RCE workflows, the BRICS tool [37] is introduced.

3.2.1 CPACS File Architecture

The *CPACS* (Common Parametric Aircraft Configuration Scheme) is an XML-based data format, exploited to describe the aircraft configurations and their corresponding data, and it is an open source project published by the German

Aerospace Center [38]. The great advantage that this file implicates consists in the availability of a standardized file format; in this way a certain user is able to represent an aircraft in an universal language understandable by all the other users and this aspect permit to exploit the CPACS file in a cooperative logic, because anyone should know and could know how a standard CPACS file is structured.

Specifying this discussion, a typical CPACS file presents an header, that gives the file's information, and two main cores in its structure: the fixed part and the editable part (see Fig.3.1).


```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<cpacs>
  <header>
  <vehicles>
  <toolspecific>
</cpacs>
```

Figure 3.1: Example of a typical CPACS file.

The fixed part represents the "idea" of CPACS format, so in this part, that for the AGILE project is normally known as "*vehicles*", there are all the information about the aircraft structure and components on the basis of a sub-levels' logic. It is important to underline that the architecture of these sub-levels is assigned and it cannot be modified, like the majority of key-words used to identify every single parameter or variable; an example can be seen in Fig.3.2.

The secondary part of a typical CPACS file is the so called "*toolspecific*" section and, as its name suggests, in this part there are the "variable" information that come from other users: being more precise, in the *toolspecific* it is possible to add information not present in the main fixed part with the purpose to exchange results or information not known *a priori* between the different users of this file. Probably this is the most important aspect for the MDO logic, because, in this way, all the partners involved in the main project are able to exchange their results, still relying on the CPACS logic and updating the same CPACS file with their contribution.

```

1      <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
2      <cpacs>
3          <header>
10         <vehicles>
11             <aircraft>
12                 <model uID="AircraftModel">
13                     <name>openAD</name>
14                     <description>openAD</description>
15                     <reference>
24                     <fuselages>
7776                    <wings>
9310                    <engines>
9324                    <landingGear>
9404                    <systems>
9436                    <global>
9454                    <analyses>
10013                   </model>
10014                   </aircraft>
10015                   <rotorcraft>
10237                   <engines>
10309                   <profiles>
10406                   <materials>
10417                   <fuels>
10424                   </vehicles>
10425                   <toolspecific>
18879                  </cpacs>

```

Figure 3.2: Example of main core of a generic CPACS file.

In Fig.3.3 it is possible to see how some of the partners involved in the AGILE 4.0 project, and, in particular, the University of Naples Federico II, added the results due to their studies and analyses in a typical CPACS file used to perform the general designing process.

```

1      <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
2      <cpacs>
3          <header>
10         <vehicles>
10425        <toolspecific>
10426            <tool>
17759            <ASTRID>
17987            <UNINA WingAnalysis>
17994            <UNINA modules>
18009            <UNINA HighLift TakeOff>
18019            <UNINA HighLift Landing>
18029            <UNINA DragPolar>
18036            <UNINA Perfo Input>
18129            <UNINA Perfo>
18219            <UNINA RubberEngine and MassUpdate results>
18234            <SFC SENSITIVITY>
18237            <UNINA NoiseTool>
18878            </toolspecific>
18879        </cpacs>

```

Figure 3.3: Example of Toolspecific section of a generic CPACS file.

3.2.2 RCE Architecture and Brics Function

The reason why the CPACS file is the standard file, adopted by the AGILE's partners, consists in the fact that this type of file is the one needed to perform a general workflow in the conventional software adopted by AGILE, in order to integrate all tools developed by the various partners. As it has been anticipated, the software, chosen to create the main workflow of project but also the various secondary workflows, is RCE [36]. *RCE* (Remote Component Environment) is an Open Source distributed, workflow-driven integration environment and it is used to design and simulate simulation-based MDO processes of complex systems by using and integrating design and simulation tools, developed by the users themselves. It is clear the great usefulness of this software to implement the designing project, following the MDO logic. RCE working is really simple and practical, in fact, the basic idea is to integrate in a virtual environment all tools, that the user needs to employ, and to connect all these tools, transferring between them the input/output files, coded in the CPACS format; naturally, in the RCE workflow every tool can be seen as a "black box" that receives in input a certain CPACS file and returns the same CPACS file updated with results achieved by itself. To better understand how a basic RCE workflow operates, the same, developed to integrate the Noise Tool coded in this thesis work, is showed in Fig.3.4; as it can be seen, the workflow starts with the input functions that upload the CPACS input files (the CPACS file from the external users and the "toolspecif" CPACS file written by the internal user) from a specific folder, that is located in the main workflow's folder; then, these files are merged, thanks to the Merger function, and send to the main tool for noise calculation and estimation. As it has been said before, the Noise Tool acts like a "black box" and it gives in output the same CPACS input file with the modifies and additions obtained by the tool's run. In the end, there is another tool that acts apart from the main one, but it will exploit the same CPACS file (this tool will be discussed better in the following chapters).

Figure 3.4: Open-Loop RCE workflow of Noise Tool and Footprint Tool in a standalone case.

The workflow showed in Fig.3.4 is a preliminary version of the final workflow, because of the absence of the most important function, implemented in RCE, that is necessary to the compliance of the MDO logic. This function is the *Brics* (protocol plus supportive middleware) [37] and its purpose consists in the transferring of a generic file from a certain user to the workflow of another one, through the on-line connection: being more clear, the user that owns the CPACS file, that acts like input file for a tool of another user involved in the general workflow, has to send this file and, thanks to the BRICS, this transfer happens in real-time in RCE. The external user, in fact, has to upload its file in the BRICS system and this system will send an e-mail to the user receiver with a security code in it; then, the receiver, after logging in the BRICS system, will insert this security code receiving in real-time the CPACS file, that will be exploited in the successive workflow's run. In Fig.3.5 the update workflow of Noise Tool shows the BRICS block.

Figure 3.5: Closed-Loop RCE workflow of Noise Tool with the add of BRICS Tool.

What has been explained is the basis on which the AGILE project was born from the software point of view and the actual final result in the RCE environment is shown in Fig.3.6. As it is possible to see, the BRICS functions do not appear in the main workflow because they are inside of every tool in possession of any single partner that developed it (every box of the main workflow, basically, refers to a specific workflow for a certain analyse, like the one in Fig.3.5); in this way all rights of property are respected, but, at the same time, it is possible to use indirectly all these tools, completing the design process in the fastest way possible and increasing the quality of process itself.

Figure 3.6: Main RCE workflow of AGILE 4.0 project.

3.3 Noise Tool's Integration Tool's Architecture

The preliminary discussion, made on the MDO logic and tools necessary to perform it, clarifies the main purpose of this thesis work, that consists in the integration of ATTILA++ software in the AGILE 4.0 workflow developed in RCE. With this integration, not only the execution of software in RCE will be made possible, but also the improvement of management of inputs and outputs is achieved. The integration code and all classes to which it refers have been written in the Python code language [39] and the virtual environment on which code works is the *Python 3.5 Environment* [40].

3.3.1 Input CPACS Toolspecific structure

Before starting talking about integration tool, it is important to show the structure of the toolspecific part of a generic CPACS file which is going to be exploited by the integration tool. The architecture of this file, in fact, is function of the classes developed to perform the management of the input and output files (description in paragraph 2.22), necessary to run ATTILA++. In Fig.3.7 the main scheme of the input section of Noise Tool's Toolspecific is shown.

Figure 3.7: Input CPACS Toolspecific developed for the Noise Tool.

Figure shows the main levels within which several parameters, variables and arrays are located and organized; everyone of these plays a role in the execution of functions that deals with the input files creation, moreover there is a successive structure of sub-levels to better organize these parameters in function of the certification procedure to follow and in function of the *.csv* input files scheme. In

the following sections, all sub-levels will be explained with respect to the specific class of functions in function of which they deal with.

3.3.2 Architecture of Integration Tool

The architecture of integration tool is based on the usage of classes and functions written in Python programming language; the advantage due to classes and functions consists in the possibility to simplify the main code, through the division of it in several secondary codes, i.e. classes and functions, which are just re-called in the main core. In this way, debugging procedures are streamlined and code's management is improved. Naturally, this procedure is permitted by the *import* function of Python that, basically, creates a virtual connection between the main code and the secondary one that is imported in it; the only constrain is represented by the necessity to locate the classes and functions or in the same folder of the main code or in library folder of Python environment. In function of this programming logic, the scheme of integration tool is achieved as it is possible to see in Fig.3.8.

Figure 3.8: Block Diagram of the architecture of Noise's Integration Tool.

About this scheme, the first important aspect to highlight is the distinction between the classes before the execution of ATTILA++ and after it; in fact, all classes located before the executable need to update all the input files described in paragraph 2.22 and this is the reason why they act "simultaneously" or, being more precise, they do not need to be run following a precise sequence, due to the fact that they are independent from each other (the only exceptions are the classes *Flap* and

Trajectory Interpolation which deals with, respectively, the *Input* and *Trajectory* classes). Therefore, after running these classes and functions, the executable of ATTILA++ can be run and, after this, there is the output management of results. The output classes are less complex and copious with respect to the input ones, due to the fact that they simply take the most significant results of noise analyses and locate them in the same CPACS file that, in this way, is updated, closing the working cycle of the integration tool.

Remembering the discussion about RCE workflow, it is clear that the integration tool is included between the Input and Output CPACS files and, basically, the scheme in Fig.3.8 represents what is inside the "black box" of the integration tool seen in Fig.3.6. At this point of discussion, all classes' blocks can be assumed as "black box", but in the following sections they will be analysed in detail.

3.3.3 Checks and Cleaning

The first "block" of integration tool is a preliminary part of code that is necessary to verify the availability of CPACS file, from the version point of view. As it is known, the importance of CPACS file is linked to the simplicity to take from it all information and data needed to perform, in this case, noise estimation; and in Python there are two functions, used to upload these data from a generic CPACS file: the *tixi* and *tigl* functions [41]; the *tixi* function is able to export and import information and data of a generic CPACS file through the definition of their path in the CPACS file itself (an example is shown in Fig.3.9); instead, the *tigl* function is able to calculate some structural information, not defined directly in the CPACS file, of an aircraft, thanks to the data present in the file itself.

```
## Certification Regulation Evaluation
tixi.open("./ToolInput/toolInput.xml")
Certification_parameter = tixi.getIntegerElement("/cpacs/toolspecific/UNINA_NoiseTool/INPUT/Control_Parameters/Certification_Type")
```

Figure 3.9: Tixi function working in the main code of the Integration Tool.

These functions have been developed by the *DLR* as consequence of birth of CPACS file; these functions, in fact, works only with a CPACS file but they present two versions in function of CPACS file's version: 2.0 and 3.0 (see Fig.3.10). The

first part of main code has to verify the input CPACS file's version to import the right version of *tixi* and *tigl* functions.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<cpacs xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xsi:noNamespaceSchemaLocation="cpacs_schema.xsd">
```

Figure 3.10: Definition of CPACS file's version.

Moreover, in the preliminary part of the main code there is a "cleaning" section where the presence of residual results and/or output files of previous executions is going to be checked and, if there are some of results, which scheme has been seen in Fig.2.24, code is able to eliminate it, otherwise it will not act; the same procedure is performed for the trajectories' plots. In the end, as it has been seen in Fig.3.9, there is the definition of the regulation case, between the CS-25 and CS-23, to direct the input and output functions' choice.

3.3.4 Engine

The engine function, as its name is able to suggest, has the main aim to modify the standard engine file (*engine.csv*), located in the ATTILA++ Input files' folder; being more precise, this function is able to read the generic engine file in *.csv* format, from an external user, that is located in an independent folder of the Integration Tool's folder and, consequently, it is able to copy the information of this file, pasting them in the standard engine file of ATTILA++ Input files' folder (in Fig.3.11 the Integration Tool's folder and the ATTILA++ Tool's folder have been shown). The advantage due to this files' transition is the higher facility to change engine file: in this way, the loading of the engine file in the specific folder of the integration tool is enough; while, before, it was necessary to take this file, rename it and substitute it in the ATTILA++'s folder; therefore, the ATTILA++ tool becomes a "black box" for the integration tool and for the user.

To perform the copying process, the engine function upload from the *CPACS Toolspecific* some variables, needed to set the code's working, showed in Table.3.1. The engine name is needed to find the engine file's path, while the engine case is an integer data that sets the engine file's correction in function of the desired

engine's BPR (these parameters have been located in the input section of the *CPACS Toolspecific* in a sub-level dedicated to all engine parameters).

Figure 3.11: Integration Tool's folder with all Python's codes, extra folders (Engine contains the loaded engine files) and the ATTLA++ folder (NOISE folder) (*Left*); ATTLA++ Tool's folder [22] (INPUT contains all .csv input files) (*Right*).

Variable Name	Description
Engine_file	Engine File Name chosen to calculate Engines Noise
Engine_case	Engine File Type [0-Default Engine File , 1-Corrected Engine File (UNINA Noise Toolspecific), 2-Corrected Engine File (UNINA Engine Toolspecific)]

Table 3.1: Engine Parameters.

Engine File's BPR Effect Correction

A new feature, introduced in the engine file's definition, is the BPR effect correction; basically, with this feature it is possible to "change" the BPR of the engines from the noise emissions' point of view.

As it is known, the engine file contains several experimental or semi-empirical noise matrices, which values are function of the directivity angle of reference microphone and of the frequencies bands in one-third-octave; these matrices, then, have been associated to a certain engine throttle rate and all of them have been split in the Take-Off case (see Fig.3.12) and the Approach case(see Fig.3.13); this division is due to the necessity to evaluate differently the engine effect during Take-Off and Approach. The structure of the engine file is necessary to perform an interpolation of the matrices values on varying of the engine throttle and the ATTILA++ tool is able to evaluate the engine emissions at the engine throttle, defined in the trajectory files for both Take-Off and Landing cases.

```
TAKEOFF_RATING
DISTANCE, 50.0

RATE, 1.0
ALFA, 50.0, 63.0, 80.0, 100.0, 125.0, 160.0, 200.0, 250.0, 315.0, 400.0, 500.0, 630.0, 800.0, 1000.0, 1250.0, 1600.0, 2000.0, 2500.0, 3150.0, 4000.0, 5000.0, 6300.0, 8000.0, 10000.0
20.0, 57.98, 62.22, 66.67, 70.81, 75.05, 78.12, 81.73, 85.97, 85.44, 86.18, 88.19, 89.72, 89.15, 92.64, 90.1, 90.42, 91.16, 90.42, 90.52, 89.78, 88.83, 87.45, 85.75, 83.74
30.0, 58.94, 63.18, 67.63, 71.87, 76.21, 79.29, 83.0, 87.34, 86.5, 87.03, 89.04, 89.46, 89.57, 92.75, 90.31, 90.52, 91.27, 90.52, 90.52, 89.89, 88.93, 87.56, 85.75, 83.74
40.0, 60.1, 64.24, 68.79, 73.03, 77.38, 80.56, 84.27, 88.72, 87.66, 88.09, 90.1, 90.21, 90.21, 93.07, 90.52, 90.74, 91.37, 90.63, 90.63, 89.89, 89.04, 87.66, 85.86, 83.85
50.0, 59.68, 63.81, 68.37, 72.72, 77.17, 80.24, 84.06, 88.51, 87.34, 87.45, 89.57, 89.46, 89.15, 92.11, 89.15, 89.15, 89.89, 88.93, 89.04, 88.3, 87.24, 85.86, 84.06, 82.04
60.0, 59.36, 63.49, 68.05, 72.4, 76.96, 80.03, 83.85, 88.4, 87.13, 87.03, 89.15, 88.93, 88.3, 91.27, 87.87, 87.77, 88.72, 87.34, 87.56, 86.71, 85.65, 84.16, 82.47, 80.45
70.0, 59.25, 63.49, 67.95, 72.4, 76.96, 79.92, 83.85, 88.4, 87.03, 87.03, 89.15, 88.83, 88.19, 90.95, 87.56, 87.45, 88.72, 87.03, 87.45, 86.5, 85.44, 83.85, 82.04, 80.14
80.0, 57.56, 61.8, 66.25, 70.49, 74.84, 78.02, 81.73, 86.18, 85.22, 85.54, 87.56, 87.87, 87.87, 87.90, 95.88, 3, 88.51, 89.99, 88.4, 89.04, 88.09, 87.03, 85.44, 83.74, 81.73
90.0, 56.39, 60.63, 65.08, 69.11, 73.35, 76.53, 80.03, 84.16, 83.85, 84.69, 86.71, 87.45, 87.98, 91.48, 89.04, 89.36, 91.37, 89.46, 90.31, 89.36, 88.3, 86.6, 84.8, 82.79
100.0, 56.39, 60.74, 65.08, 69.11, 73.14, 76.32, 79.71, 83.63, 83.74, 84.81, 86.81, 87.77, 88.51, 92.11, 89.89, 90.21, 92.22, 90.31, 91.27, 90.31, 89.15, 87.45, 85.75, 83.74
110.0, 56.39, 60.74, 64.98, 69.01, 72.93, 76.11, 79.5, 83.21, 83.63, 85.01, 86.92, 87.98, 88.83, 92.22, 90.31, 90.74, 92.54, 90.84, 91.58, 90.74, 89.57, 87.98, 86.18, 84.16
120.0, 56.6, 60.95, 65.19, 69.11, 72.93, 76.21, 79.39, 83.0, 83.74, 85.33, 87.24, 88.4, 89.46, 92.54, 90.95, 91.37, 92.96, 91.58, 92.22, 91.37, 90.31, 88.72, 86.92, 84.91
130.0, 57.56, 61.8, 66.04, 69.85, 73.56, 76.96, 80.03, 83.32, 84.59, 86.39, 88.19, 89.57, 90.74, 93.39, 92.22, 92.75, 94.02, 92.86, 93.39, 92.64, 91.58, 90.1, 88.3, 86.28
140.0, 54.8, 59.04, 63.39, 67.27, 71.02, 74.31, 77.59, 81.09, 81.94, 83.53, 85.33, 86.6, 87.66, 90.95, 89.15, 89.57, 91.37, 89.78, 90.52, 89.57, 88.51, 86.92, 85.12, 83.1
150.0, 51.52, 55.86, 60.21, 64.13, 68.16, 71.44, 74.84, 78.76, 78.86, 80.03, 81.94, 82.99, 83.74, 87.56, 85.01, 85.44, 87.77, 85.54, 86.6, 85.65, 84.48, 82.68, 80.88, 78.86
160.0, 48.87, 53.11, 57.45, 61.59, 65.83, 69.01, 72.61, 76.85, 76.32, 77.06, 79.08, 79.61, 80.03, 83.74, 80.98, 81.3, 83.74, 81.41, 82.57, 81.51, 80.24, 78.44, 76.74, 74.73

RATE, 0.5
ALFA, 50.0, 63.0, 80.0, 100.0, 125.0, 160.0, 200.0, 250.0, 315.0, 400.0, 500.0, 630.0, 800.0, 1000.0, 1250.0, 1600.0, 2000.0, 2500.0, 3150.0, 4000.0, 5000.0, 6300.0, 8000.0, 10000.0
20.0, 67.31, 71.97, 74.73, 78.76, 83.32, 81.09, 81.62, 83.85, 83.21, 82.57, 82.47, 82.26, 82.15, 82.04, 81.73, 81.41, 80.77, 79.82, 78.44, 76.64, 74.52, 72.08, 69.22, 66.25
30.0, 68.69, 73.46, 76.11, 80.24, 84.91, 82.47, 82.89, 85.12, 84.38, 83.53, 83.21, 82.79, 82.47, 82.36, 81.94, 81.62, 80.88, 79.92, 78.55, 76.74, 74.73, 72.29, 69.43, 66.46
40.0, 70.17, 74.94, 77.59, 81.73, 86.39, 83.95, 84.27, 86.6, 85.65, 84.69, 84.06, 83.42, 83.0, 82.79, 82.26, 81.83, 81.09, 80.14, 78.76, 76.96, 74.94, 72.5, 69.75, 66.89
50.0, 70.07, 74.94, 77.59, 81.62, 86.39, 83.85, 84.06, 86.39, 85.44, 84.16, 83.42, 82.57, 81.94, 81.51, 80.88, 80.35, 79.61, 78.55, 77.17, 75.37, 73.95, 71.02, 68.37, 65.61
60.0, 70.07, 74.84, 77.49, 81.62, 86.39, 83.74, 83.95, 86.28, 85.22, 83.85, 82.89, 81.83, 81.09, 80.56, 79.71, 79.18, 78.23, 77.17, 75.68, 73.99, 71.97, 69.75, 67.1, 64.55
70.0, 70.07, 74.84, 77.49, 81.62, 86.39, 83.74, 83.95, 86.28, 85.12, 83.85, 82.89, 81.73, 80.88, 80.35, 79.5, 78.86, 78.02, 76.85, 75.47, 73.67, 71.76, 69.43, 66.89, 64.34
80.0, 67.63, 72.4, 75.05, 79.08, 83.74, 81.3, 81.73, 83.95, 83.1, 82.15, 81.83, 81.09, 80.77, 80.67, 80.03, 79.82, 78.97, 78.02, 76.53, 74.73, 72.72, 70.28, 67.52, 64.66
90.0, 65.3, 70.07, 72.72, 76.74, 81.3, 79.18, 79.71, 81.94, 81.51, 81.09, 81.51, 80.98, 80.98, 81.3, 80.67, 80.67, 79.92, 78.86, 77.38, 75.58, 73.56, 71.13, 68.16, 65.08
100.0, 64.66, 69.22, 71.97, 75.9, 80.45, 78.55, 79.29, 81.41, 81.2, 81.09, 81.83, 81.51, 81.62, 82.04, 81.51, 81.41, 80.77, 79.71, 78.23, 76.43, 74.41, 71.87, 69.01, 65.83
110.0, 64.02, 68.58, 71.34, 75.15, 79.61, 78.02, 78.86, 80.98, 80.98, 81.09, 82.04, 81.73, 81.94, 82.36, 81.83, 81.83, 81.2, 80.14, 78.76, 76.96, 74.84, 72.4, 69.32, 66.25
120.0, 63.6, 67.95, 70.81, 74.52, 78.86, 77.59, 78.65, 80.67, 80.98, 81.3, 82.36, 82.26, 82.57, 83.0, 82.57, 82.47, 81.83, 80.88, 79.99, 77.59, 75.58, 73.03, 70.07, 66.89
130.0, 63.6, 67.84, 70.74, 74.31, 78.44, 77.8, 78.97, 80.98, 81.62, 82.26, 83.32, 83.42, 83.74, 84.16, 83.85, 83.74, 83.1, 82.15, 80.77, 78.97, 76.85, 74.41, 71.34, 68.16
140.0, 61.59, 66.04, 68.79, 72.61, 76.85, 75.68, 76.74, 78.76, 79.08, 79.5, 80.67, 80.45, 80.67, 81.2, 80.77, 80.77, 80.03, 79.08, 77.59, 75.79, 73.78, 71.23, 68.26, 65.08
150.0, 59.68, 64.24, 66.99, 70.91, 75.47, 73.67, 74.31, 76.53, 76.32, 76.21, 77.17, 77.17, 76.64, 76.74, 77.27, 76.64, 76.64, 75.9, 74.94, 73.46, 71.66, 69.64, 67.1, 64.13, 61.06
160.0, 58.09, 62.86, 65.51, 69.54, 74.09, 71.97, 72.4, 74.62, 73.99, 73.46, 73.88, 73.14, 73.03, 73.46, 72.72, 72.72, 71.87, 70.81, 69.32, 67.52, 65.51, 63.07, 60.1, 57.13
```

Figure 3.12: Example of engine noise matrices on varying of Throttle Rate for the Take-Off.

```

APPROACH_RATING
DISTANCE, 50.0

RATE, 1.0
ALFA, 50.0, 63.0, 80.0, 100.0, 125.0, 160.0, 200.0, 250.0, 315.0, 400.0, 500.0, 630.0, 800.0, 1000.0, 1250.0, 1600.0, 2000.0, 2500.0, 3150.0, 4000.0, 5000.0, 6300.0, 8000.0, 10000.0
20.0, 55.52, 59.58, 63.84, 67.8, 71.86, 74.81, 78.26, 82.32, 81.81, 82.52, 84.45, 84.96, 85.36, 88.71, 86.28, 86.58, 87.29, 86.58, 86.68, 85.97, 85.06, 83.74, 82.11, 80.18
30.0, 56.43, 60.49, 64.76, 68.82, 72.98, 75.92, 79.47, 83.64, 82.82, 83.33, 85.26, 85.67, 85.77, 88.81, 86.48, 86.68, 87.39, 86.68, 86.68, 86.07, 85.16, 83.84, 82.11, 80.18
40.0, 57.55, 61.51, 65.87, 69.93, 74.1, 77.14, 80.69, 84.96, 83.94, 84.35, 86.28, 86.38, 86.38, 89.12, 86.68, 86.88, 87.49, 86.78, 86.78, 86.17, 85.26, 83.94, 82.21, 80.29
50.0, 57.14, 61.1, 65.47, 69.63, 73.89, 76.84, 80.49, 84.75, 83.64, 83.74, 85.77, 85.67, 85.36, 88.2, 85.36, 85.36, 86.07, 85.16, 85.26, 84.55, 83.53, 82.21, 80.49, 78.56
60.0, 56.84, 60.8, 65.16, 69.32, 73.69, 76.63, 80.29, 84.65, 83.43, 83.33, 85.36, 85.16, 84.55, 87.39, 84.14, 84.04, 84.96, 83.64, 83.84, 83.03, 82.01, 80.59, 78.97, 77.04
70.0, 56.74, 60.8, 65.06, 69.32, 73.69, 76.53, 80.29, 84.65, 83.33, 83.33, 85.36, 85.06, 84.45, 87.09, 83.84, 83.74, 84.96, 83.33, 83.74, 82.82, 81.81, 80.29, 78.56, 76.73
80.0, 55.11, 59.17, 63.44, 67.5, 71.66, 74.7, 78.26, 82.52, 81.61, 81.91, 83.84, 84.14, 84.14, 87.09, 84.55, 84.75, 86.17, 84.65, 85.26, 84.35, 83.33, 81.81, 80.18, 78.26
90.0, 54.0, 58.16, 62.32, 66.18, 70.24, 73.28, 76.63, 80.59, 80.29, 81.1, 83.03, 83.74, 84.24, 87.59, 85.26, 85.56, 87.49, 85.67, 86.48, 85.56, 84.55, 82.93, 81.2, 79.27
100.0, 54.0, 58.16, 62.32, 66.18, 70.24, 73.08, 76.33, 80.06, 80.18, 81.3, 83.13, 84.04, 84.75, 88.2, 86.07, 86.38, 88.3, 86.48, 87.39, 86.48, 85.36, 83.74, 82.11, 80.18
110.0, 54.0, 58.16, 62.22, 66.08, 69.83, 72.88, 76.12, 79.68, 80.08, 81.4, 83.23, 84.24, 85.06, 88.3, 86.48, 86.88, 88.61, 86.99, 87.7, 86.88, 85.77, 84.24, 82.52, 80.59
120.0, 54.2, 58.36, 62.42, 66.18, 69.83, 72.98, 76.02, 79.47, 80.18, 81.71, 83.53, 84.65, 85.67, 88.61, 87.09, 87.49, 89.02, 87.7, 88.3, 87.49, 86.48, 84.96, 83.23, 81.3
130.0, 55.11, 59.17, 63.23, 66.89, 70.44, 73.69, 76.63, 79.78, 81.0, 82.72, 84.45, 85.77, 86.88, 89.42, 88.3, 88.81, 90.03, 88.91, 89.42, 88.71, 87.7, 86.28, 84.55, 82.62
140.0, 52.48, 56.54, 60.7, 64.35, 68.0, 71.15, 74.3, 77.65, 78.46, 79.98, 81.71, 82.33, 83.94, 87.09, 85.36, 85.77, 87.49, 85.97, 86.68, 85.77, 84.75, 83.23, 81.5, 79.58
150.0, 49.33, 53.49, 57.65, 61.41, 65.26, 68.41, 71.66, 75.41, 75.52, 76.63, 78.46, 79.37, 80.18, 83.84, 81.4, 81.81, 84.04, 81.91, 82.93, 82.01, 80.9, 79.17, 77.44, 75.52
160.0, 46.78, 50.85, 55.01, 58.97, 63.03, 66.08, 69.53, 73.59, 73.08, 73.79, 75.72, 76.23, 76.63, 80.18, 77.55, 77.85, 80.18, 77.95, 79.07, 78.05, 76.84, 75.11, 73.49, 71.56

RATE, 0.5
ALFA, 50.0, 63.0, 80.0, 100.0, 125.0, 160.0, 200.0, 250.0, 315.0, 400.0, 500.0, 630.0, 800.0, 1000.0, 1250.0, 1600.0, 2000.0, 2500.0, 3150.0, 4000.0, 5000.0, 6300.0, 8000.0, 10000.0
20.0, 64.45, 68.92, 71.56, 75.41, 79.78, 77.65, 78.15, 80.29, 79.68, 79.07, 78.97, 78.76, 78.66, 78.56, 78.26, 77.95, 77.34, 76.43, 75.11, 73.38, 71.35, 69.02, 66.28, 63.44
30.0, 65.77, 70.34, 72.89, 76.84, 81.3, 78.97, 79.37, 81.5, 80.79, 79.99, 79.68, 79.27, 78.97, 78.87, 78.46, 78.15, 77.44, 76.53, 75.21, 73.49, 71.56, 69.22, 66.48, 63.64
40.0, 67.19, 71.76, 74.3, 78.26, 82.72, 80.39, 80.69, 82.93, 82.01, 81.1, 80.49, 79.88, 79.47, 79.27, 78.76, 78.36, 77.65, 76.73, 75.41, 73.69, 71.76, 69.43, 66.79, 64.05
50.0, 67.09, 71.76, 74.3, 78.15, 82.72, 80.29, 80.49, 82.72, 81.81, 81.81, 80.59, 79.88, 79.07, 78.46, 78.05, 77.44, 76.94, 76.23, 75.21, 73.89, 72.17, 70.24, 68.0, 65.47, 62.83
60.0, 67.09, 71.66, 74.2, 78.15, 82.72, 80.18, 80.39, 82.62, 81.61, 80.29, 79.37, 78.36, 77.65, 77.14, 76.33, 75.82, 74.91, 73.89, 72.47, 70.85, 68.92, 66.79, 64.25, 61.81
70.0, 67.09, 71.66, 74.2, 78.15, 82.72, 80.18, 80.39, 82.62, 81.5, 80.29, 79.37, 78.26, 77.44, 76.94, 76.12, 75.52, 74.7, 73.59, 72.27, 70.54, 68.72, 66.48, 64.05, 61.61
80.0, 64.76, 69.32, 71.86, 75.72, 80.18, 77.85, 78.26, 80.39, 79.58, 78.66, 78.36, 77.65, 77.34, 77.24, 76.63, 76.43, 75.62, 74.7, 73.28, 71.56, 69.63, 67.29, 64.66, 61.91
90.0, 62.52, 67.09, 69.63, 72.49, 77.85, 75.82, 76.33, 78.46, 78.05, 77.65, 78.05, 77.55, 77.55, 77.24, 77.24, 76.53, 75.52, 74.1, 72.37, 70.44, 68.11, 65.26, 62.32
100.0, 61.91, 66.28, 68.92, 72.67, 77.04, 75.21, 75.92, 77.95, 77.75, 77.65, 78.36, 78.05, 78.15, 78.56, 78.05, 77.95, 77.34, 76.33, 74.91, 73.18, 71.25, 68.82, 66.08, 63.03
110.0, 61.31, 65.67, 68.31, 71.96, 76.23, 74.7, 75.52, 77.55, 77.55, 77.65, 78.56, 78.26, 78.46, 78.87, 78.36, 78.36, 77.75, 76.73, 75.41, 73.69, 71.66, 69.63, 67.33, 64.44
120.0, 60.9, 65.06, 67.8, 71.35, 75.52, 74.3, 75.31, 77.24, 77.55, 77.85, 78.87, 78.76, 79.07, 79.47, 79.07, 78.97, 78.36, 77.44, 76.02, 74.3, 72.37, 69.93, 67.09, 64.05
130.0, 60.9, 64.96, 67.7, 71.15, 75.11, 74.5, 75.62, 77.55, 78.15, 78.76, 79.78, 79.88, 80.18, 80.59, 80.29, 80.18, 79.58, 78.66, 77.34, 75.62, 73.59, 71.25, 68.31, 65.26
140.0, 58.97, 63.23, 65.87, 69.53, 73.59, 72.47, 73.49, 75.41, 75.72, 76.12, 77.24, 77.04, 77.24, 77.04, 77.34, 77.34, 76.63, 75.72, 74.3, 72.57, 70.64, 68.21, 65.37, 62.32
150.0, 57.14, 61.51, 64.15, 67.9, 72.27, 70.54, 71.15, 73.28, 73.08, 72.98, 73.89, 73.38, 73.49, 73.99, 73.38, 73.38, 72.67, 71.76, 70.34, 68.61, 66.69, 64.25, 61.41, 58.46
160.0, 55.62, 60.19, 62.73, 66.58, 70.95, 68.92, 69.32, 71.46, 70.85, 70.34, 70.75, 70.04, 69.34, 69.63, 69.63, 68.82, 67.8, 66.38, 64.66, 62.73, 60.39, 57.55, 54.71

```

Figure 3.13: Example of engine noise matrices on varying of Throttle Rate for the Approach.

the BPR correction, basically, consists in the multiplication of every matrix's value for a correction factor that has been estimated starting from experimental values. The procedure to estimate these factor has been made using the experimental results achieved during several flight test's campaigns, certified by the EASA [42]. In the EASA files, noise emissions, certified for CS-25 and CS-23, has been classified for all the aircraft tested by the EASA itself; referring to the BPR effect correction, the EASA files, considered to estimate correction factors, are the ones about the Jets and Turbo-Fan engine's aircraft and, for this reason, the reference certification is the CS-25. This is the reason why there are several corrections factors for the Take-Off cases (Lateral and Fly-Over) and the Approach case on varying of BPR value; moreover, in this evaluation, all the aircraft, belonging to the weight category of the thesis test aircraft (MTOW in a range of 40 000 kg-52 000 Kg) and belonging to the engine's types CF34-10E (BPR equals to 5.4) and PW-1000 family (BPR equals to 12), has been chosen.

After defining the data used to estimate correction factors, it is possible to explain the procedure to evaluate them, dividing it in the following steps:

1. **Evaluation of medium values of the noise emissions** for all test cases for the selected type of aircraft in function of the engine types, cited before

(see Fig.3.14);

2. **Calculation with linear regression laws of the interpolation factors** to estimate noise emissions on varying of the BPR and estimation of these results (see Fig.3.15);
3. **Iterative testing of several attempted correction factors** (see Fig.3.16) to find out the correction factors that achieve noise estimated emissions with ATTILA++ Tool as similar as possible to the experimental interpolated results (see Fig.3.17);
4. **Definition of the interpolation factors** to define an interpolation law in function of the BPR value for both Take-Off and Approach cases (see equations 3.1 and 3.2);

The final result of this estimation procedure is the definition of the interpolation laws that make possible the calculation of the correction factors K_{TO} and $K_{Approach}$ in function of the BPR.

$$K_{TO} = 1.11 - 0.0094 * BPR \quad (3.1)$$

$$K_{Approach} = 1.03 - 0.0022 * BPR \quad (3.2)$$

Certified Medium Values from Sperimental Data (Certified Values for Engines with the specified BPR value)					
ENGINE TYPE	BPR	Approach	Fly-Over	Lateral	Cumulative
CF34-10E (MTOW [40000 kg-52000 Kg])	5.4	92.4	81.2	91.9	265.5
PW-1000 (MTOW > 45000)	12	91.5	77.5	86.3	255.3

Figure 3.14: Experimental results for all test cases at BPR = 5.4 and BPR = 12, obtained by the arithmetic medium of all results from aircraft of assigned MTOW range. [25]

BPR	Approach	Fly-Over	Lateral	Cumulative
5	92.45454545	81.42424242	92.23939394	266.1181818
5.4	92.4	81.2	91.9	265.5
9	91.90909091	79.18181818	88.84545455	259.9363636
12	91.5	77.5	86.3	255.3
15	91.09090909	75.81818182	83.75454545	250.6636364

Figure 3.15: Experimental results achieved by the interpolation calculation based on the experimental values seen in Fig.3.14

Several Attempt with different Multiplicative Factors					
Attempt N°	Approach	Fly-Over	Lateral	Cumulative	Multiplicative Engine Factor
1	92.7	80.3	88.0	261.0	1.02
2	92	79.7	87.2	258.9	1.01
3	97.1	84.7	93.1	274.9	1.08
4	96.4	83.9	92.3	272.6	1.07
5	95.6	83.2	91.4	270.2	1.06
6	94.9	82.4	90.6	267.9	1.05
7	93.4	81	88.9	263.3	1.03
8	90.7	78.4	85.5	254.6	0.99
9	90.0	77.8	84.6	252.4	0.98
10	89.4	77.2	83.8	250.4	0.97
11	88.7	76.6	82.9	248.2	0.96
12	88.1	76.1	82.1	246.3	0.95

Figure 3.16: Several attempts to find out the correction factors as similar as possible to experimental results seen in Fig.3.15

BPR	Approach	Fly-Over	Lateral	Cumulative	Take-Off Multiplicative Engine Factor	Approach Multiplicative Engine Factor
5.4	92.5	83.2	91.4	267.1	1.06	1.015
9	92.2	81.1	88.9	262.2	1.03	1.01
12	91.5	79.2	86.3	257	1.00	1.00
15	91.2	77.5	83.8	252.5	0.97	0.995

Figure 3.17: Final correction factors obtained after the estimation procedure.

It is important to underline that this factors work well if applied to the engine file exploited to execute the estimation of themselves; and this one is the engine

file of a Turbo-Fan engine with a BPR equals to 12 similar to the PW-1900 engine family [43] and, in the following pictures (see Fig.3.18), it is possible to observe the high-fidelity level of the ATTILA++ estimated results compared to the experimental data (the only significant difference is a shift of results on the Fly-Over case that is overestimated of 1.5-2 dB but with a constant trend on varying of BPR). Naturally, if this correction procedure is applied to an engine with performance properties similar to the test engine file, the correction can be considered valid.

Figure 3.18: Comparisons between the estimated results with the usage of correction factors and the experimental results from the EASA analyses: Approach Noise Emissions at different BPR (Top-Left); Fly-Over Noise Emissions at different BPR (Top-Right); Lateral Noise Emissions at different BPR (Down-Left); Cumulative Noise Emissions at different BPR (Down-Right).

Engine Function Structure

On the basis of this correction procedure, the engine function is structured so that, if there is no necessity to correct the engine file, the function simply copy the external engine file in the engine input file of ATTILA++, otherwise the correction

factors' application starts. The switching parameter is the *Engine_case* command, seen in Table.3.1; this command can be set on three possible solution:

- **Engine_case = 0:** Engine function does not apply any correction factor;
- **Engine_case = 1:** Engine function applies correction factors, assigned in the engine section of the *CPACS Toolspecific* for the Noise Tool (see Fig.3.19);
- **Engine_case = 2:** Engine function applies correction factors, taken from the *CPACS Toolspecific Engine_retrofit* and calculated with an external engine tool that implements the interpolation laws (equations 3.1 and 3.2).

```

<Engine_Data>
  <Number_engine>2</Number_engine>
  <Engine_file>PW1524G.csv</Engine_file>
  <description>Engine File Name chosen to perform Engines Noise</description>
  <Engine_case>0</Engine_case>
  <description>Engine File Type [0-Default Engine File, 1-Corrected Engine File w.r.t. BPR (UNINA Noise Toolspecific),
  2-Corrected Engine File (UNINA Engine Toolspecific)]. If command has set on 1, it's needed to define correction factors as follows,
  while if command has set on 2, correction factors will be taken from UNINA Engine Toolspecific.</description>
  <Correction_Factors>
    <Multiplicative_Factor_Engine_Approach>0.995</Multiplicative_Factor_Engine_Approach>
    <description>Multiplicative Factor to pass from standard default engine to a different one (different BPR) in Approach</description>
    <Multiplicative_Factor_Engine_TakeOff>0.97</Multiplicative_Factor_Engine_TakeOff>
    <description>Multiplicative Factor to pass from standard default engine to a different one (different BPR) in Take-Off</description>
  </Correction_Factors>
  <Position_engine>1</Position_engine>
  <description>Engine Position index. [0-Rear mounted engines, 1-Engines mounted below the wing (Default)]</description>
</Engine_Data>

```

Figure 3.19: Engine section of the CPACS file's UNINA Noise Toolspecific.

The switching possibilities characterize the function architecture, because with no correction Python code will apply a simple copying procedure as it can be seen in the following script section.

```

1  # CPACS Files Reading
3  open_file(CPACS_path + "toolInput.xml")
   engine_name = tixi_get_element(CPACS_path + "engine_name")
5
   # Files Copy
7  cwd = get_current_working_directory()
   Engine_file_path = cwd + "Engine"
9  Initial_engine_file = Engine_file_path + engine_name
   Final_engine_file =
11      cwd + "NOISE/Attila++v0.8.1/INPUT/Engine.csv"
   copy_file(Initial_engine_file, Final_engine_file)

```

Listing 3.1: Engine File copying pseudo-code.

If the switching parameter activates the engine file's correction (discussion valid for both acquisition sub-levels, i.e. *Engine_retrofit's CPACS Toolspecific* and Noise

Tool's *CPACS Toolspecific*), engine function will follow a specific copying procedure to take from the external engine file all the relevant information and then it will paste them in the final engine file, located in the ATTLA++ folder, maintaining the file's scheme, necessary to make file itself readable for the Noise Tool. In the pseudo-code 3.2 the copying procedure has been explained.

```

1  if (engine_type = 1 or engine_type = 2):
3
4      if (engine_type = 1):
5          mult_approach = tixi_get_element(
6              CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific
7              + "Multiplicative_Factor_Engine_Approach")
8          mult_takeoff = tixi_get_element(
9              CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific
10             + "Multiplicative_Factor_Engine_TakeOff")
11
12     if(engine_type = 2):
13         mult_approach = tixi_get_element(
14             CPACS_path_engine_toolspecific
15             + "Multiplicative_Factor_Engine_Approach")
16         mult_takeoff = tixi_get_element(
17             CPACS_path_engine_toolspecific
18             + "Multiplicative_Factor_Engine_TakeOff")
19
20     ### Noise Matrix extrapolation
21     ## Total Length Calculations
22     open_file(Final_engine_file):
23
24         ##Basic Counters Initialization and Calculation
25         Num_spaced_rows = 0
26         Num_null_rows = 0
27         Num_comment_rows = 0
28         Num_rate = 0
29         Num_line = 0
30
31         for line in engine_file:
32             Num_null_rows = Number_null_rows_calculation()
33             Num_rate = Number_rate_rows_calculation()
34             Num_spaced_rows =
35                 Number_spaced_rows_calculation()
36             Num_comment_rows =
37                 Number_comment_rows_calculation()
38
39         # Noise Matrix's rows

```

```

41     Num_none_rows = Num_null_rows + Num_spaced_rows
42     Num_alpha_rows = Num_line - Num_comment_rows
43                     - Num_none_rows - (Num_rate * 2) - 4
44
45     ## Take-Off Counters Calculation
46     open_file(Final_engine_file):
47
48         ## Counter Initialization
49         Num_spaced_rows_TO = 0
50         Num_null_rows_TO = 0
51         Num_comment_rows_TO = 0
52         Num_rate_TO = 0
53         Num_line_TO = 0
54
55         for line in engine_file:
56             Num_line_TO = Number_line_TO_calculation()
57             Num_null_rows_TO =
58                 Number_null_rows_TO_calculation()
59             Num_rate_TO = Number_rate_TO_calculation()
60             Num_spaced_rows_TO =
61                 Number_spaced_rows_TO_calculation()
62             Num_comment_rows_TO =
63                 Number_comment_rows_TO_calculation()
64
65             # Take-Off Noise Matrix's rows
66             Num_none_rows_TO = Num_null_rows_TO +
67                                 Num_spaced_rows_TO
68             Num_alpha_TO = Num_line_TO - Num_comment_rows_TO -
69                             Num_none_rows_TO - (Num_rate_TO * 2) - 3
70
71             ## Approach Matrix counters
72             Num_alpha_app = Num_alpha - Num_alpha_TO
73             Num_rate_app = Num_rate - Num_rate_TO
74
75             ## Distance vector
76             open_file(Final_engine_file):
77
78                 distance_row_vector =
79                     vector_initialization(number_element = 2)
80             for line in engine_file:
81                 distance_row_vector =
82                     distance_row_vector_definition()
83
84             ## Rate Vector
85             open_file(Final_engine_file):
86
87                 rate_row_vect =
88                     vector_initialization(number_element = Num_rate)

```

```

    for line in engine_file:
89         rate_row_vect = rate_row_vector_definition()

91     ## Alpha vector
    open_file(Final_engine_file):
93
        for line in engine_file:
95             Num_freq = lenght(line)
            alfa_vect = vector_initialization
97                 (number_element = Num_freq)
            alfa_vect = alfa_row_vector_definition()
99
    ## Noise Matrix
101    matrix = matrix_initialization(Num_alpha, Num_freq)
    open_file(Final_engine_file):
103
        for line in engine_file:
105             matrix= matrix_creation()

107    ### Take-Off and Approach Matrixes construction
    TO_matrix = matrix_initialization(Num_alpha_TO, Num_freq)
109    Approach_matrix =
        matrix_initialization(Num_alpha_app, Num_freq)
111
    ## TAKE-OFF
113    TO_matrix = matrix_TO_creation(mult_takeoff)

115    ## APPROACH
    Approach_matrix = matrix_approach_creation(mult_approach)
117

    ### Engine File Writing
119    write_file(Final_engine_file):
        "TAKEOFF_RATING"
121
        "DISTANCE", distance_vect[1]
123    for rate in Num_rate_TO:
        "RATE", rate_vect[rate]
125        alfa_vect
        for rows in (Num_alpha_TO / Num_rate_TO):
127            TO_matrix[rows +
                rate * (Num_alpha_TO / Num_rate_TO)]
129
        "APPROACH_RATING"
131
        "DISTANCE", distance_vect[2]
133
    for rate in Num_rate_app:
135        "RATE", rate_vect[rate + Num_rate_TO]

```

```

137         alfa_vect
         for rows in (Num_alpha_app / Num_rate_app):
             Approach_matrix[rows +
139                 rate * (Num_alpha_app / Num_rate_app)

```

Listing 3.2: Engine file correction pseudo-code.

As the pseudo-code 3.2 shows, the engine function, first of all, acquires from the engine file all the information necessary to correct and re-write the file itself; to make it possible it considers the engine file as a sequence of lines which can be evaluated as vector and, so, divided in cells using the specific separator command (normally it is the ","). In function of this reading's procedure, code will read the engine file with an iterative process, evaluating the following parameters:

- **Num_spaced_rows:** Number of rows where the toolbar input is in the first cell of row;
- **Num_null_rows:** Number of rows where the first cell of row is a null;
- **Num_comment_rows:** Number of rows where there are comments (defined by the %% command);
- **Num_rate:** Number of rows where the rate value is assigned;
- **Num_line:** Total number of rows;
- **Num_none_rows:** Number of rows sum of *Num_spaced_rows* and *Num_null_rows*;
- **Num_alpha:** Number of rows that contain the engine emissions values;

To optimize the iterative lecture of the engine file, the engine function will exploit the first cell of every row to identify it, thanks to several key-words (*TAKEOFF_RATING*, *DISTANCE*, *RATE*, *APPROACH_RATING*); in this way the total noise matrix can be defined and, consequently, it can be split for the test cases and corrected with the correction factors; in the end, the code will re-write the updated engine file.

3.3.5 Receivers Functions' Class

The receivers class contains all functions which update the receiver input files. The architecture of these functions is based on the uploading of the receivers' input data from the *CPACS Toolspecific* and the re-writing of the various *.csv* files with these data. In Table 3.2 all input data, taken from the Toolspecific section, have been described.

The necessity to define several functions, in order to update the receivers file, is due to the regulation procedure's selection and the test case's selection; in function of these drivers, the functions presented in the receivers class are:

- **Approach_CS25**: Receivers function used to update the *Receivers_Approach.csv* input file on the base of CS-25 regulation;
- **Lateral_CS25**: Receivers function used to update the *Receivers_Lateral.csv* input file on the base of CS-25 regulation;
- **Fly-Over_CS25**: Receivers function used to update the *Receivers_Flyover.csv* input file on the base of CS-25 regulation;
- **Lateral_CS23**: Receivers function used to update the *Receivers_Lateral.csv* input file on the base of CS-23 regulation.

Naturally, in the CPACS Toolspecific, the functions distinction has been kept as it is possible to see in Fig.3.20. In the end, the receivers functions, after uploading all data, will re-write the specific receiver file, maintaining the precise scheme, indispensable to be able to run ATTILA++ Tool.

```

<Receivers>
  <Main_Tool>
    <description>Microphones parameters to set the Tool calculation for Certificative Results</description>
    <CS23>
      <description>Microphones parameters to set the Tool calculation for CS23 Certification</description>
      <Lateral>
    </CS23>
    <CS25>
      <description>Microphones parameters to set the Tool calculation for CS25 Certification</description>
      <Approach>
      <Lateral>
      <Flyover>
    </CS25>
  </Main_Tool>

```

Figure 3.20: Receiver section of the CPACS file's UNINA Noise Toolspecific.

Variable Name	Description
Name_Case	Receivers Name (Recommend - MICROPHONE POSITIONS)
Humidity	Relative Humidity at receiver point (%)
X_norm_lenght	Microphone position along X axis from regulations
Y_norm_lenght	Microphone position along Y axis from regulations
Z_norm_lenght	Microphone position along Z axis from regulations
Linear	Use a linear array of receiver positions extrapolated from the first position indicated below (first row under X,Y,Z labels) [1-Extrapolate trajectory; 0-Not required]
Number_Linear	Number of source positions that will be calculated if LINEAR is set to 1.
Delta_Linear	Time interval between two consecutive receiver positions that will be calculated if LINEAR is set to 1.

Table 3.2: Generic Receiver file input data.

in the listing 3.3 the pseudo-code to re-write the receiver file scheme has been shown (the commentary rows, indicated with the `%%`, are not essential to run noise tool, but they describe the scheme itself and all possible commands of the generic receiver file).

```

1 write_file(receiver_file.csv):
3   %% MICROPHONE POSITIONS FOR APPROACH CONDITION FILE

5   %% SOURCE POSITIONS DATA
6   %% POSITIONS
7   %% X: Microphone position along X axis.
8   %% Y: Microphone position along Y axis.
9   %% Z: Microphone position along Z axis.
10  %% ATMOSPHERIC PARAMETERS
11  %% WARNING: THE DEFAULT ATMOSPHERIC VALUES ARE CALCULATED
```

```

    USING THE ISA MODEL %%
13  %% T: Ambient temperature at microphone location.
    %% P: Ambient pressure at microphone location.
15  %% RHO: Ambient density at microphone location.
    %% NU: Ambient kinematic viscosity at microphone location.
17  %% GAMMA: Specific heat ratio of air at
    microphone location.
19  %% C: Ambient sound speed at microphone location.
    %% EXTRA DATA
21  %% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS MUST ALWAYS FOLLOW
    THE PREVIOUS COORDINATE LIST %%
23  %% NAME: Receiver(s) name.
    %% REL_HUM: Relative Humidity at receiver point (%)
25  %% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS ARE USED ONLY
    IF A LINEAR EXTRAPOLATION IS REQUESTED %%
27  %% LINEAR:: Use a linear array of receiver positions
    extrapolated from the first position indicated below
29  (first row under X,Y,Z labels).[1-Extrapolate
    microphones positions; 0-Not required (Default)]
31  %% The parameters for the extrapolation are
    N_LIN and DELTA_LIN.
33  %% The atmospheric conditions are always calculated
    internally if LINEAR is 1.
35  %% N_LIN:: Number of source positions that will be
    calculated if LINEAR is set to 1.
37  %% DELTA_LIN: Time interval between two consecutive source
    positions that will be calculated if LINEAR is set to 1.
39
    %% MICROPHONE POSITIONS DATA
41  X_norm_lenght, Y_norm_lenght, Z_norm_lenght

43  %% EXTRA DATA
    %% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS MUST ALWAYS FOLLOW
45  THE PREVIOUS COORDINATE LIST %%
    NAME, Name_Case
47  REL_HUM, Rel_hum
    LINEAR, Linear
49  N_LIN, Num_Lin
    DELTA_LIN, Delta_lin

```

Listing 3.3: Receiver file updating pseudo-code.

3.3.6 Trajectory Functions Overview

The trajectory class contains all functions used to estimate simplified flight paths in the Take-Off and Approach test cases, in function of the procedures described

and assigned by the reference regulations (see paragraphs 2.3.1 and 2.3.2). The function's structure will be explained in detail in the following pages (see paragraph 3.4), but the general workflow has been structured on the basis of the following steps:

1. **Data acquisition from the CPACS file's Toolspecific section:** all driving parameters, that are based on the regulation procedures, have been uploaded;
2. **Flight Path calculation:** the simplified trajectory will be estimated by means of the flight performances' equation, based on the regulation's constraints;
3. **Trajectory files' update:** the equations' results will be used to update the trajectory input file of the specific flight path estimated;
4. **Trajectory's plots:** the same results will be exploited to represent several plots of the flight path itself and the time histories of the main flight's parameters (velocity, throttle rate, climb angle).

3.3.7 Control Parameters Functions

The final class, that belongs to the input classes, is, exactly, the Input class that contains all functions used to update the *Input.csv* file and the *ControlParameters.csv* file; in this paragraph the control parameters file updating is going to be explained. The working way of the update function is similar to the one of the receivers function seen in paragraph 3.3.5, i.e. there is a preliminary part where all data will be taken from the *Toolspecific section* of the CPACS input file; then, the *.csv* file will be updated with these data. In Tables 3.3 - 3.12 all data present in the *Toolspecific section* have been described in detail, but, introducing their main aims, the control parameters are needed to set the noise tool working in terms of the test cases to analyse, in terms of the contributions to evaluate, in terms of the sound metrics and correction factors to apply, and in terms of the results management (see Fig.3.21); moreover, the switching parameter, exploited to define the certification regulation, is in the control parameters file.

Variable Name	Description
Unit_System	Unit reference system [1-SI (Default); 2-British]
Certification_Type	Certification Regulation for Noise Certification w.r.t. Aircraft Weight. [0-Noise Certification CS25, 1-Noise Certification CS23]
Approach_Case	Run Approach case [1-Perform calculation ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Lateral_Case	Run Lateral case [1-Perform calculation ; 0-Not required (Default)]
FlyOver_Case	Run Fly-Over case [1-Perform calculation ; 0-Not required (Default)]
User_Case	Run User-Defined case [1-Perform calculation ; 0-Not required (Default)]

Table 3.3: Initial control and cases parameters description.

Variable Name	Description
UD_Traj_File	Trajectory User-Defined File Name
App_Traj_File	Trajectory Approach File Name
FO_Traj_File	Trajectory FlyOver File Name
Lat_Traj_File	Trajectory Lateral File Name
UD_Rec_File	Receivers User-Defined File Name
App_Rec_File	Receivers Approach File Name
FO_Rec_File	Receivers FlyOver File Name
Lat_Rec_File	Receivers Lateral File Name

Table 3.4: Trajectory and Receivers Control Parameters.

Variable Name	Description
Wing_contr	Include wing contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Horiz_contr	Include horizontal tail contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Vert_contr	Include vertical tail contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
LEslat_contr	Include leading edge slat contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Flap_contr	Include flap contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
MainGear_contr	Include main landing gears contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
NoseGear_contr	Include nose landing gears contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Airframe_contr	Include airframe contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Engine_contr	Include engine contribution [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Atm_contr	Include atmospheric attenuation effect [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Refl_contr	Include ground reflection effect [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Lat_contr	Include lateral attenuation effect [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]

Table 3.5: Control Parameters to include the several noise sources, contributions and effects.

Variable Name	Description
SPL	Calculate Sound pressure level (SPL) at all receiver locations [1-Include ;0-Not required (Default)]
Overall_SPL	Calculate overall Sound pressure level (OASPL) at all receiver locations [1-Include ;0-Not required (Default)]
SEL	Calculate Sound exposure level (SEL) at all receiver locations [1-Include ;0-Not required (Default)]
PNL	Calculate Perceived noise level (PNL) at all receiver locations [1-Include ;0-Not required (Default)]
Tone_PNL	Calculate Tone corrected Perceived noise level (PNLT) at all receiver locations [1-Include ;0-Not required (Default)]
Effective_PNL	Calculate Effective Perceived noise level (EPNL) at all receiver locations [1-Include ;0-Not required (Default)]
Tone_Eff_PNL	Calculate Tone corrected Effective Perceived noise level (EPNLT) at all receiver locations [1-Include ;0-Not required (Default)]
Weighted_SPL	Calculate Weighted Sound pressure level.If WBA is not 0, the weighting filter is applied to all metrics which depend on the SPL. [0-dB (Default) ;1-dBA] If Certification_Type is set on 1, Weighted_SPL will be set on 1.

Table 3.6: Sound Metrics evaluation Control Parameters.

Variable Name	Description
Multi_SPL_wing	Multiplicative correction factor for the SPL produced by wing.
Multi_SPL_horiz	Multiplicative correction factor for the SPL produced by horizontal tail(s).
Multi_SPL_vert	Multiplicative correction factor for the SPL produced by vertical tail(s).
Multi_SPL_slat	Multiplicative correction factor for the SPL produced by leading edge slats.
Multi_SPL_flap	Multiplicative correction factor for the SPL produced by flaps.
Multi_SPL_MG	Multiplicative correction factor for the SPL produced by main landing gear.
Multi_SPL_NG	Multiplicative correction factor for the SPL produced by nose landing gear.
Multi_SPL_engine	Multiplicative correction factor(s) for the SPL produced by engine(s).

Table 3.7: Multiplicative Correction Factors' Control Parameters

Variable Name	Description
Add_SPL_wing	Additive correction factor for the SPL produced by wing.
Add_SPL_horiz	Additive correction factor for the SPL produced by horizontal tail(s).
Add_SPL_vert	Additive correction factor for the SPL produced by vertical tail(s).
Add_SPL_slat	Additive correction factor for the SPL produced by leading edge slats.
Add_SPL_flap	Additive correction factor for the SPL produced by flaps.
Add_SPL_MG	Additive correction factor for the SPL produced by main landing gear.
Add_SPL_NG	Additive correction factor for the SPL produced by nose landing gear.
Add_SPL_engine	Additive correction factor(s) for the SPL produced by engine(s).

Table 3.8: Additive Correction Factors' Control Parameters

Variable Name	Description
CSV_control_output	Control parameter to generate an output file in .csv format. It directly sets IOTIME=0, IOSEP=0 and FILLER=','. For a different separator see FILLER [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Critical_Res_control_output	Control parameter for Printing the most Critical Result in a separate file [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Res_control_output	Control parameter for Printing the Results in all the multiple files will be generated [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Info_control_output	Control parameter for Printing all the Information of interest. When IOALL = 1, further commands are ignored. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Frames_control_output	Control parameter for Printing Frames [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Titles_control_output	Control parameter for Printing Titles [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Time_control_output	Output control parameter for Printing an array containing calculation Times at the beginning of each block of results. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]

Table 3.9: First part of the Output Control Parameters.

Variable Name	Description
Print_Eff_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing each component Contribution and Propagation Effect. When IOPART = 0, further commands are ignored [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Traj_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Trajectory details.[1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Mic_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Microphone details.[1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Tone_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing the Tone correction of the the calculated PNLT. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Wing_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Wing contribution separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Horiz_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Horizontal tail contribution separately. [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Vert_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Vertical tail contribution separately. [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Slat_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Leading Edge Slat contribution separately. [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]

Table 3.10: Second part of the Output Control Parameters.

Variable Name	Description
Print_Flap_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Flap contribution separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_MainGear_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Main landing Gears contribution separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_NoseGear_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Nose landing Gears contribution separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Airframe_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Airframe contribution separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Engine_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Engine contribution separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_ATM_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Atmospheric attenuation effect separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Refl_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Ground Reflection effect separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Print_Lat_ control_output	Control parameter for Printing Lateral attenuation effect separately. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]

Table 3.11: Third part of the Output Control Parameters.

Variable Name	Description
Write_ WarningsReading_ control_output	Control parameter for Writing Warnings about Input data Reading. [1-Include; 0-Not required (Default)]
Write_ WarningsICorrectness_ control_output	Control parameter for Writing Warnings about Input data Correctness. [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Write_ WarningsCalc_ control_output	Control parameter for Writing generated during Calculation. [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Write_ WarningsOCorrectness_ control_output	Control parameter for Writing Warnings about Output data Correctness. [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Write_ AllWarnings_ control_output	Control parameter for Writing All Warnings. [1-Include ; 0-Not required (Default)]
Significant_Digits	Number of Significant Digits after the comma.
Width_number	Number of characters to be used as field width for Numbers.
Width_titles	Number of characters to be used as field width for Titles.
Filler	Optional symbol for separating values.

Table 3.12: Fourth part of the Output Control Parameters.

```

<Control_Parameters>
  <Unit_System></Unit_System>
  <description>Unit reference system [1-SI (Default);2-British]</description>
  <Certification_Type>0</Certification_Type>
  <description>Certification Regulation for Noise Certification w.r.t. Aircraft Weight. [0-Noise Certification CS25, 1-Noise Certification CS23]</description>
  <Cases>
  <Trajectory Files>
  <Receivers Files>
  <Contributions>
  <Sound Metrics>
  <Correction_Factors>
    <Multiplicative_Factors>
    <Additive_Factors>
  </Correction_Factors>
  </Outputs>
</Control_Parameters>

```

Figure 3.21: Main parameters' groups of the Control Parameters section in CPACS Noise Toolspecific.

The update of data, taken from the *CPACS Toolspecific* has to be made respecting the precise scheme of the control parameters file (as it happens for the receiver one) and in the listing 3.4 this scheme is shown (this listing has to be applied, following the same pseudo-code of receiver file, seen in listing 3.3). The most important aspect to underline, regarding control parameters' functions, is that there is not a single control parameters function but, in the Input class, this function presents two version due to the certification's choice; the reason why it is necessary to distinguish these function consists in the computational reason and regulation reason: in the CS-25 function all parameters can be modified in function of the values given in the *CPACS Toolspecific*; instead, in the CS-23 function some parameters have been imposed, in order to respect the CS-23 regulation. Basically, in the CS-23 function the only case to run is the Lateral case (this case is going to be defined like Take-Off case) and all sound metrics have to be measured in the *dba* unit (in Table 3.13 all fixed parameters have been shown).

Variable Name	Fixed Value
Approach_Case	0
Lateral_Case	1
FlyOver_Case	0
User_Case	0
Weighted_SPL	1

Table 3.13: Fixed Parameters in the CS-23 control parameters function.

```

Control Parameters file
2
   %%% INPUT DATA
4   %%% UNIT SYSTEM
   U: Unit reference system [1 - SI (Default)  2 - British]
6   %%%%%%%% CASES
   %% ICAPP: Run Approach case
8   %% ICLAT: Run Lateral case
   %% ICFLY: Run Flyover case
10  %% ICUD : Run User-defined case
   %%%%%%%% TRAJECTORY FILES
12  %% UD_T_FILE: User defined trajectory filename
   %% APPROACH_T_FILE: Approach trajectory filename
14  %% FLYOVER_T_FILE: Flyover trajectory filename
   %% LATERAL_T_FILE : Lateral trajectory filename
16  %%%%%%%% RECEIVERS FILES
   %% UD_R_FILE: User defined receiver coordinates filename
18  %% APPROACH_R_FILE: Approach receiver coordinates filename
   %% FLYOVER_R_FILE: Flyover receiver coordinates filename
20  %% LATERAL_R_FILE: Lateral receiver coordinates filename
   %%%%%%%% CONTRIBUTIONS
22  %% IA1: Include wing contribution
   %% IA2: Include horizontal tail contribution
24  %% IA3: Include vertical tail contribution
   %% IA4: Include leading edge slat contribution
26  %% IA5: Include flap contribution
   %% IA6: Include main landing gear contribution
28  %% IA7: Include nose landing gear contribution
   %% IAIR: Include airframe contribution
30  %% IENG: Include engine contribution
   %% IATM: Include atmospheric attenuation effect
32  %% IREFL: Include ground reflection effect
   %% ILAT: Include lateral attenuation effect
34  %%%%%%%% SOUND METRICS
   %% ISPL: Calculate Sound pressure level (SPL) at all
36  receiver locations.
   %% IOASPL: Calculate Overall sound pressure level
38  (SPL) at all receiver locations.
   %% ISEL: Calculate sound exposure level (SEL) at all
40  receiver locations.
   %% IPNL: Calculate Perceived noise level (PNL) at all
42  receiver locations.
   %% IPNLT: Calculate Tone corrected Perceived
44  noise level (PNLT) at all receiver locations.
   %% IEPNL_NT: Calculate Effective Perceived noise level (EPNL)
46  at all receiver locations.
   %% IEPNL: Calculate Tone corrected Effective
48  Perceived noise level (EPNLT) at all receiver locations.

```

```

    %% WdB: Calculate Weighted Sound pressure level.
50 %%%%%% CORRECTION FACTORS
    %% K_SPL_WING: Multiplicative correction factor
52 for the SPL produced by wing.
    %% K_SPL_HTAIL: Multiplicative correction factor(s)
54 for the SPL produced by horizontal tail(s).
    %% K_SPL_VTAIL: Multiplicative correction factor(s)
56 for the SPL produced by vertical tail(s).
    %% K_SPL_SLAT: Multiplicative correction factor for
58 the SPL produced by leading edge slats.
    %% K_SPL_FLAP: Multiplicative correction factor for
60 the SPL produced by flaps.
    %% K_SPL_MLG: Multiplicative correction factor for
62 the SPL produced by main landing gear.
    %% K_SPL_NLG: Multiplicative correction factor for
64 the SPL produced by nose landing gear.
    %% K_SPL_ENGINE: Multiplicative correction factor(s)
66 for the SPL produced by engine(s).
    %% DELTA_SPL_WING: Additive correction factor for
68 the SPL produced by wing.
    %% DELTA_SPL_HTAIL: Additive correction factor(s) for
70 the SPL produced by horizontal tail(s).
    %% DELTA_SPL_VTAIL: Additive correction factor(s) for
72 the SPL produced by vertical tail(s).
    %% DELTA_SPL_SLAT: Additive correction factor for
74 the SPL produced by leading edge slats.
    %% DELTA_SPL_FLAP: Additive correction factor for
76 the SPL produced by flaps.
    %% DELTA_SPL_MLG: Additive correction factor for
78 the SPL produced by main landing gear.
    %% DELTA_SPL_NLG: Additive correction factor for
80 the SPL produced by nose landing gear.
    %% DELTA_SPL_ENGINE: Additive correction factor for
82 the SPL produced by engines.
    %%%%%% OUTPUT
84 %% IOCSV: Output control parameter for generating
    an output file in .csv format.
86 %% IOMAX: Output control parameter for Printing
    the most Critical Result in a separate file.
88 %% IOEW: Output control parameter for Printing the Results
    in all the multiple files will be generated
90 %% IOALL: Output control parameter for Printing
    all the Information of interest.
92 %% IOSEP: Output control parameter for Printing Frames
    %% IOTIT: Output control parameter for Printing Titles
94 %% IOTIME: Output control parameter for Printing an array in-
    cluding calculation Times at beginning of each result's block
96 %% IOPART: Output control parameter for Printing

```

```

each component Contribution and Propagation Effect.
98 %% IOTR: Output control parameter for Printing
Trajectory details
100 %% IOMIC: Output control parameter for Printing
Microphone details
102 %% IOTC: Output control parameter for Printing the Tone
correction contribution associated with the calculated PNLT.
104 %% IOA1: Output control parameter for Printing
Wing contribution separately.
106 %% IOA2: Output control parameter for Printing
Horizontal tail contribution separately.
108 %% IOA3: Output control parameter for Printing
Vertical tail contribution separately.
110 %% IOA4: Output control parameter for Printing
Leading Edge Slat contribution separately.
112 %% IOA5: Output control parameter for Printing
Flap contribution separately.
114 %% IOA6: Output control parameter for Printing
Main landing Gears contribution separately.
116 %% IOA7: Output control parameter for Printing
Nose landing Gears contribution separately.
118 %% IOAIR: Output control parameter for Printing
Airframe contribution separately.
120 %% IOENG: Output control parameter for Printing
Engine contribution separately.
122 %% IOATM: Output control parameter for Printing
Atmospheric attenuation effect separately.
124 %% IOREFL: Output control parameter for Printing
Ground Reflection effect separately.
126 %% IOLAT: Output control parameter for Printing
Lateral attenuation effect separately.
128 %% IOLOG_I: Output control parameter for Writing
Warnings about Input data Reading.
130 %% IOLOG_ICHK: Output control parameter for Writing
Warnings about Input data Correctness.
132 %% IOLOG_CALC: Output control parameter for Writing
Warnings generated during Calculation.
134 %% IOLOG_OCHK: Output control parameter for Writing
Warnings about Output data Correctness.
136 %% IOLOG_ALL: Output control parameter for Writing
All Warnings.
138 %% PREC: Number of Significant Digits after the comma.
%% WIDTH: Number of characters to be used
140 as field width for Numbers.
%% WIDTH_TITLE: Number of characters to be used
142 as field width for Titles.
%% FILLER: Optional symbol for separating values.

```

Listing 3.4: Control Parameters.csv file scheme. [22]

3.3.8 Input Functions

The effective input *.csv* file works on the input parameters, necessary to characterize the aircraft and its components; moreover, in this file the ground properties have been defined. The input function's architecture is similar to the one designed for the receivers and control parameters functions with the only difference about some parameters, that the code will take from the CPACS fixed part and some others, that code will extrapolate from the CPACS fixed part, through the *tigl* function.

In Fig.3.22 the parameters' paths, from the fixed part of CPACS file, have been shown.

```

<cpacs xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xsi:n
<header>
<vehicles>
  <aircraft>
    <model uid="agile_v13_modelID">
      <name>AGILE4_T81_V1.4</name>
      <description>Agile DC2: 2:2 abreast 9180kg, right fuselage
      <reference>
      <fuselages>
      <wings>
      <engines>
      <enginePylons>
      <landingGear>
      <noseGears>
      <mainGears>
        <mainGear symmetry="x-z-plane" uid="mainGear">
          <parentUID isLink="True">MainWing_wingID</parentUID>
          <fuselageAttachment uid="">
          <wingAttachment>
          <global>
          <components>
          <bogie>
          <axles>
            <axle uid="mainAxle">
              <shaft>
                <length>2.01</length>
              </shaft>
              <wheelUID isLink="True">mainWheel</wheelUID>
              <numberOfWheels>2.0</numberOfWheels>
            </axle>
          </axles>
          <wheels>
            <wheel uid="mainWheel">
              <radius>0.7</radius>
              <width>0.20</width>
            </wheel>
          </wheels>
          </components>
        </mainGear>
      </mainGears>
    </landingGear>
  </aircraft>
</vehicles>
</header>

```

```

<cpacs xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xsi:n
<header>
<vehicles>
  <aircraft>
    <model uid="agile_v13_modelID">
      <name>AGILE4_T81_V1.4</name>
      <description>Agile DC2: 2:2 abreast 9180kg, right fuselage
      <reference>
      <fuselages>
      <wings>
      <engines>
      <enginePylons>
      <landingGear>
      <noseGears>
        <noseGear uid="noseGear">
          <parentUID isLink="True">NASA_fuselageID</parentUID>
          <fuselageAttachment uid="">
          <global>
          <components>
            <axles>
              <axle uid="noseAxle">
                <shaft>
                  <length>1.65</length>
                </shaft>
                <wheelUID isLink="True">noseWheel</wheelUID>
                <numberOfWheels>2.0</numberOfWheels>
              </axle>
            </axles>
            <wheels>
              <wheel uid="noseWheel">
                <radius>0.45</radius>
                <width>0.15</width>
              </wheel>
            </wheels>
          </components>
        </noseGear>
      </noseGears>
    </mainGears>
  </landingGear>
</aircraft>
</vehicles>
</header>

```

Figure 3.22: Input parameters from the fixed part of CPACS file.

The *tigl* function [41] is able to exploit the CPACS file data from its fixed part to calculate the main geometric information of the aircraft and of its components. On the basis of this aspect, the input function, that is located in the input class, in the first part acquires from *Toolspecific* some data, from the fixed part some other data in a direct way, and, through the *tigl* function, the remaining data; in Table 3.14 the *Toolspecific* parameters have been shown, while in Table 3.15 the ones from the fixed section have been shown (all variable names are the ones used

in the input code) and in Table 3.16 the ones managed with the *tigl* function (all variable names are the ones used in the input code).

Variable Name	Description
Number_engine	Aircraft's Number of engines
Engine_file	Engine File Name chosen to perform Engines Noise
Position_engine	Engine Position index. [0-Rear mounted engines, 1-Engines mounted below the wing (Default)]
Ground_type	Ground type. [1-Snow, 2-Grass (Default), 3-Sand, 4-Limestone, 5-Wet, 6-Tarmac]
Turbolent_type	Turbolent type. [1-Perfectly still, 2-Nominally still, 3-Moderately still, 4-Turbolent (Default)]
Aircraft_type	Aircraft type index [0-Transport aeroplane wing (Default), 1-Glider]
Wing_type	Wing type index [1-Conventional wing (Default) , 2-Delta wing]
Number_horiz	Number of horizontal surfaces (except wing)
Number_vert	Number of vertical surfaces (except wing)
Number_flap_slot	Number of flap slots
Number_MG	Number of main landing gear
Wings_sequence	Sequence of wing type in CPACS standard file [1-Main Wing, 2-Horizontal Tail, 3-Vertical Tail].

Table 3.14: Input parameters from the CPACS Toolspecific.

Python Variable Name	Description
name	CPACS file name
Num_wheel_MLG	Main landing gears number of wheels
Tyre_diam_MLG	Diameter of main landing gear's tyre (m)
Length_MLG	Main landing gear structure's length (m)
Num_wheel_NLG	Nose landing gears number of wheels
Tyre_diam_NLG	Diameter of nose landing gear's tyre (m)
Length_NLG	Nose landing gear structure's length (m)

Table 3.15: Input parameters from the fixed part of CPACS file.

Python Variable Name	Description
Main_wing_surf	Wing Surface (m^2)
Main_wing_span	Wing Span (m)
number_horiz	Number of Horizontal Tails
Horiz_surf	Horizontal Tail Surface (m^2)
Horiz_span	Horizontal Tail Span (m)
number_vert	Number of Vertical Tails
Vert_surf	Vertical Tail Surface (m^2)
Vert_span	Vertical Tail Span (m)
flap_area	Total Flaps Surface (m^2)
flap_span	Flaps Span (m)

Table 3.16: Input parameters extrapolated from the fixed part of CPACS file.

To better understand the input parameters extrapolation, performed with the *ti gl* function, the pseudo-code of the code's specific section is shown in the listing 3.5. As it is possible to see, the most important parameter in this case is the *wings_sequ*, that is a vector which element define the wings order in the CPACS file (for example, if in the CPACS file the order of the wings is: Main Wing, Vertical Tail and Horizontal Tail; the vector has to be written like "1;3;2", remembering that [1 - Main Wing, 2 - Horizontal Tail, 3 - Vertical Tail]). The importance of this parameter is linked to the fact that the *ti gl* function does not know *a priori* the wings order in CPACS file and, therefore, the code needs to exploit this sequence in such a way that it is able to select the correct wing between all of them and extrapolate its geometric information.

```

1  ## Tigl Attributes
3  ti gl_open_cpacs_file(tixi_function , Aircraft_UID)
   Num_wings = ti gl_wing_count()
5
   # Initialization (Wings)
7  Wing_UID = vector_initialization(Num_wings)
   Wing_Index = vector_initialization(Num_wings)
9  Wing_Surf = vector_initialization(Num_wings)
   Wing_Span = vector_initialization(Num_wings)
11
   # Data aquisition (Wings)
13 for in Num_wings:
       Wing_UID = ti gl_wingGetUID()
15       Wing_Index = ti gl_wingGetIndex(Wing_UID)
       Wing_Surf = ti gl_wingGetSurfaceArea(Wing_Index)
17       Wing_Span = ti gl_wingGetSpan(Wing_UID)

19 ## Horizontal and Vertical wings loading
   wings_sequ = tixi_get_vector
21       (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Wings_sequ_Num")

23 # Data organization
   number_horiz = wing_type_number(Num_wings ,wings_sequ)
25   number_vert = wing_type_number(Num_wings ,wings_sequ)

27   Main_wing_surf =
           wing_type_surf_acquisition(Num_wings ,wings_sequ)
29   Main_wing_span =

```

```

        wing_type_span_acquisition(Num_wings,wings_sequ)
31 Horiz_surf = wing_type_surf_acquisition(Num_wings,wings_sequ)
    Horiz_span = wing_type_span_acquisition(Num_wings,wings_sequ)
33 Vert_surf = wing_type_surf_acquisition(Num_wings,wings_sequ)
    Vert_span = wing_type_span_acquisition(Num_wings,wings_sequ)

```

Listing 3.5: Tigl working pseudo-code

The input code, after uploading all parameters seen in the previous tables, following the several acquisition methods, will update the *input.csv* file with the same approach seen for the others *.csv* input files; naturally, the input file needs a specific scheme to respect, that is shown in the listing 3.6.

```

2  Input file

4  %%%%%% INPUT DATA
   %%%%%% PROJECT NAME
6  %% NAME: Project Name
   %%%%%% AIRCRAFT DATA
8  %% WAT: Aircraft type index
   [0-Transport aeroplane wing (Default), 1-Glider]"
10 %%%%%% WING DATA
   %% WWT: Wing type index
12 [1-Conventional wing (Default), 2-Delta wing]"
   %% SW: Wing area
14 %% BW: Wing span
   %%%%%% HORIZONTAL TAIL DATA
16 %% NH: Number of horizontal surfaces (except wing)
   %% SH: Horizontal tail area
18 %% BH: Horizontal tail span
   %%%%%% VERTICAL TAIL DATA
20 %% NV: Number of vertical surfaces
   %% SV: Vertical tail area
22 %% BV: Vertical tail span
   %%%%%% FLAP DATA
24 %% SF: Flap area
   %% BF: Flap span
26 %% N_SLOT: Number of flap slots
   %%%%%% MAIN LANDING GEAR DATA
28 %% N_MLG: Number of main landing gear
   %% N_WHEEL_MLG: Number of wheels on main landing gear unit
30 %% D_MLG: Tyre diameter of main landing gear wheel
   %% S_MLG: Length of main landing gear strut
32 %%%%%% NOSE LANDING GEAR DATA
   %% N_WHEEL_NLG: Number of wheels on nose landing gear unit
34 %% D_NLG: Tyre diameter of nose landing gear wheel

```

```

%% S_NLG: Lenght of nose landing gear strut
36 %%%ENGINE DATA
%% N_ENG: Number of engines
38 %% ENGINE_FILE: Engine filename.
%% POS_ENG: Engine position index [0-Rear mounted engines,
40 1-Engines mounted below the wing (Default)]"
%%DATA FOR GROUND REFLECTION
42 %% TYPE_GROUND: Ground type [1-Snow, 2-Grass (Default),
3-Sand, 4-Limestone, 5-Wet, 6-Tarmac]
44 %% TYPE_TURB: Turbolent type
[1-Perfectly still, 2-Nominally still,
46 3-Moderately still, 4-Turbolent (Default)]

```

Listing 3.6: Input.csv File scheme. [22]

3.3.9 Flap Function

In the input function, between the parameters extrapolated with the *tigl* function, there are the flap data that come from the independent flap function. This function has been written, due to the fact that the flap data can be extrapolated with the *tigl* function too, but the extrapolation process is more complex than the classic one.

In listing 3.7 this process is shown, while in Table 3.17 the *CPACS Toolspecific* parameters, necessary to run this function, have been described (they are located in the same sub-level of the input parameters). The flap function, first of all, will exploit the *tigl* function to extrapolate the needed wings data up to evaluate the two-dimensional coordinates of the inner and outer positions of all wings segments.

Variable Name	Description
Number_Flap	Number of Flaps (inner and outer flaps), not considering the aileron
Number_TrailingEdge_Device	Number of Trailing Edge Devices
Kink_section_position	Section number of Kink in Main Wing

Table 3.17: Toolspecific Flap parameters.

Then, there is the acquisition of the flap's data, stored in the CPACS file, i.e. the inner and outer section of it in the dimensionless coordinates ξ and η . As it is possible to see in Fig.3.23, the flap's data location is generally defined like trailing edge device; therefore, it is necessary to distinguish the flap from the aileron and, consequently, the code is able to identify the aileron section and overlook them (the only constrain is the necessity to rename the aileron level with the key-words shown in the pseudo-code).

```

<cpacs xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xsi:noNamesp
  <header>
  <vehicles>
    <aircraft>
      <model uID="agile_v13_modelID">
        <name>AGILE4_T81_V1.4</name>
        <description>Agile DC2: 2:2 abreast 9180kg, right fuselage dims,
        <reference>
      <fuselages>
      <wings>
        <wing symmetry="x-z-plane" uID="MainWing_wingID">
          <name>MainWing</name>
          <parentUID>NASA_fuselageID</parentUID>
          <transformation uID="MainWing_wingID_transformation1">
          <sections>
          <positionings>
          <segments>
            <componentSegments>
              <componentSegment uID="wing_Cseg">
                <name>wing_CSeg</name>
                <description>wing_CSeg</description>
                <structure>
                  <controlSurfaces>
                    <leadingEdgeDevices>
                    <trailingEdgeDevices>
                      <trailingEdgeDevice uID="aileronUID">
                      <trailingEdgeDevice uID="innerFlapUID">
                      <trailingEdgeDevice uID="outerFlapUID">
                    </trailingEdgeDevices>
                  </controlSurfaces>
                <wingFuselageAttachments>
                <wingFuelTanks>
                  <fromElementUID isLink="True">MainWing_wingSection1Elemen
                  <toElementUID isLink="True">MainWing_wingSection3Element:
                </componentSegment>
              </componentSegments>
            </wing>
          <wing symmetry="x-z-plane" uID="HorizontalStabiliser_wingID">
          <wing uID="VerticalStabiliser_wingID">

```

Figure 3.23: Flap data location in the fixed part of CPACS file.

After the CPACS flap data acquisition, the calculation of the flap ratio occurs, due to the necessary to calculate, at a later time, the flap section chords; in the final part of flap's function, the interpolation vectors, along the body axes "x" and "y", will be defined in function of the kink position (the kink section location has been defined through the associated tool-specific parameter, described in Table 3.17); therefore, it is possible to create several interpolation functions for every panel of the wing, to estimate the flap chords and position along the "y" axis; in the end, the flap surface and flap span can be calculated.

```

2  ## CPACS Files Reading
   open_file((CPACS_path + "toolInput.xml")
4  Kink_seg_pos =
       tixi_get_element(CPACS_path + "Kink_section_position")
6
   ## Tigl Attributes
8  for in Num_wings:
       Wing_UID = tigl_wingGetUID()
10     Wing_Index = tigl_wingGetIndex(Wing_UID)
       Wing_Surf = tigl_wingGetSurfaceArea(Wing_Index)
12     Wing_Span = tigl_wingGetSpan(Wing_UID)
       wing_SegCount = tigl_wingGetSegmentCount(wing_Index)
14     wing_SegUid = tigl_wingGetSegmentUID()
       wing_SegIndex = tigl_wingGetSegmentIndex(wing_SegUid)
16     wing_IndexPosition =
           tigl_wingGetSegmentIndex(wing_SegUid)
18
   # Range of local coordinates inside CPACS file
20  eta = [0, 1]
       xsi = [0, 1]
22
   ## Main Wing surface
24  for in length(wing_Uid):
       mainWingUID == wing_Uid
26     mainWPos

28  for in Num_wings:
       for in wing_SegCount:
30         wChordPoint = matrix_creation(wing_SegCount)

32  ## Wing taper ratio
       wChordPoint= tigl_wingGetChordPoint
34         (wing_Index, eta, xsi, Num_wings, wing_SegCount)

```



```

84         if CPACS_version at least equal to 3.0:
85             eta_inner_flap =
86                 find_in_innerBorder("etaLE/eta")
87         else:
88             eta_inner_flap =
89                 find_in_innerBorder("etaLE")
90     for outerBorder in root_find_all
91         (CPACS_path + "outerBorder"):
92     if CPACS_version at least equal to 3.0:
93         xsiLE_outer_flap[k] =
94             find_in_outerBorder("xsiLE/xsi")
95     else:
96         xsiLE_outer_flap[k] =
97             find_in_outerBorder("xsiLE")
98
99     if CPACS_version at least equal to 3.0:
100         eta_outer_flap[k] =
101             find_in_outerBorder("etaLE/eta")
102     else:
103         eta_outer_flap[k] =
104             find_in_outerBorder("etaLE")
105
106 for in number_flaps:
107     flap_chord_ratio =
108         1 - (xsiLE_outer_flap + xsiLE_inner_flap) / 2
109     flap_chord_ratio_inner = 1 - xsiLE_inner_flap
110     flap_chord_ratio_outer = 1 - xsiLE_outer_flap
111     flap_non_dimensional_inner_station = eta_inner_flap
112     flap_non_dimensional_outer_station = eta_outer_flap
113
114 # Kink
115 yF1 = vector_creation(Y_inner_LE(Kink_seg_pos - 2),
116                       Y_outer_LE(Kink_seg_pos - 2))
117 yF2 = vector_creation(Y_inner_LE(Kink_seg_pos - 1),
118                       Y_outer_LE(Kink_seg_pos - 1))
119 X_LE_kink = tigl_wingGetChordPoint
120             (wing_Index, mainWPos, Kink_seg_pos)
121 X_TE_kink = tigl_wingGetChordPoint
122             (wing_Index, mainWPos, Kink_seg_pos)
123 Y_LE_kink = tigl_wingGetChordPoint
124             (wing_Index, mainWPos, Kink_seg_pos)
125 eta_kink = Y_LE_kink / (wing_Span(mainWPos) / 2)
126 Ckink_w = X_TE_kink - X_LE_kink
127 x1 = vector_creation(X_inner_TE(Kink_seg_pos - 2)
128                     - X_inner_LE(Kink_seg_pos - 2), Ckink_w)
129
130 chord_wingSegment1 = interpolation_1D(yF1, x1)
131 x2 = [Ckink_w, X_outer_TE[Kink_seg_pos - 1] -

```

```

132             X_outer_LE[Kink_seg_pos - 1]]
chord_wingSegment2 = interpolation_1D(yF2, x2)
134
## FLAPS calculate
136 for in range number_flaps:
    Y_Flap_inner = flap_non_dimensional_inner_station
138                 * wing_Span(mainWPos) / 2
    Y_Flap_outer = flap_non_dimensional_outer_station
140                 * wing_Span(mainWPos) / 2

142 if flap_non_dimensional_inner_station maximum eta_kink:
    chord_innerFlap = chord_wingSegment1
144                 (flap_non_dimensional_inner_station *
                    wing_Span(mainWPos) / 2)
146 else:
    chord_innerFlap = chord_wingSegment2
148                 (flap_non_dimensional_inner_station *
                    wing_Span(mainWPos) / 2)
150 if flap_non_dimensional_outer_station maximum eta_kink:
    chord_outerFlap = chord_wingSegment1
152                 (flap_non_dimensional_outer_station *
                    wing_Span(mainWPos) / 2)
154 else:
    chord_outerFlap = chord_wingSegment2
156                 (flap_non_dimensional_outer_station *
                    wing_Span(mainWPos) / 2)
158
    chord_innerFlap =chord_innerFlap * flap_chord_ratio_inner
160    chord_outerFlap =chord_outerFlap * flap_chord_ratio_outer

162 ## Flap span and area
for in range number_flaps:
164     single_span = (Y_Flap_outer - Y_Flap_inner)
    flap_span = flap_span + single_span
166     single_area = ((chord_outerFlap + chord_innerFlap)
                    * single_span) / 2
168     flap_area = flap_area + single_area

```

Listing 3.7: Flap function pseudo-code.

3.3.10 ATTILA++ Executable

The turning point of the integration code is the ATTILA++ executable that can be launched with the specific Python function, able to run an external executable. The only necessary add to perform this execution is a function able to wait the execution's ending, before resume the integration code running.

Once the executable has completed its running, the integration code will automatically generate a Return Directory to store, not only the complete folder of the Noise Tool's results, but also all the input files in the *.csv* format, storing them in a specific folder, and the trajectory's time-histories and plots.

3.3.11 Output Functions Class

The final part of the integration tool is represented by the output functions, which purpose consists in the extraction from the output files of all significant results, in function of the sound metrics requested from the regulation: for the CS-25 regulation case, the reference sound metric is the EPNL, measured in dB; while for the CS-23 regulation case, the reference sound metric is the OASPL, measured in dBA. For this reason, the output functions are divided, first of all, in the CS-25 and CS-23 categories; moreover, in the CS-25 case, there is another classification based on the analysed flight paths : Approach, Lateral, Fly-Over. This classification can be seen in the CPACS file, where the results will be uploaded in the OUTPUT sub-section of the *Toolspecific* section (see Fig. 3.24).

```

<UNINA_NoiseTool>
  <Description>UNINA_NoiseTool v1.0</Description>
  <INPUT>
  <OUTPUT>
    <description>Tool developed to estimate the 'Certified Noise Levels'. The results has been estimated for:
    The cases' cumulative condition; The single cases and The several contributions.</description>
    <APPROACH>
    <FLYOVER>
    <LATERAL>
    <CUMULATIVE>
  </OUTPUT>
</UNINA_NoiseTool>

```

Figure 3.24: General scheme of the Output section in the CPACS Toolspecific.

In the Output class, two functions have been coded to create certain input necessary to run the other output functions:

- *Vector_cases*;
- *Vector_control_parameters*.

These function extract from the CPACS file certain control parameters that set indirectly the output's management; in fact, the *Vector_cases* function will extract the cases parameters (see Table. 3.3), locating them in a specific vector; instead, the *Vector_control_parameters* function will extract the control parameters, to evaluate

the possible contributions (see Table 3.5), the control parameters, exploited to set the printing condition of possible contributions' results (see Tables 3.10 and 3.11), the sound metrics control parameters, with respect to the EPNL sound metric (see Table 3.6), and other toolspecific parameters ("Filler", "Number_engine") necessary to run the output functions.

In the integration code the output functions' management will exploit the cases' vector, cited before, and the switching parameter, in function of the certification case; in this way, all reference function can be re-called as necessary.

Output Functions CS-25

Regarding the CS-25 regulation, there are three functions that organize the results in function of the test cases seen before. However, all these functions will follow the same basic scheme, exploited to acquire the fundamental results and upload them in the final CPACS file. In the first part, there is the core of the general output function, because, after the input management, the function will take the results from the output file on the basis of the code seen in listing 3.8.

```

1  # Wing contribution
3  if(wing_contribution_printing = 1 and wing_contribution = 1):
4      for line in test_case:
5          riga = line_split(Filler)
6          if("EPNL" in riga[0] and "EPNLnT" not in riga[0]):
7              EPNL_test_case_wing = riga[1]
8
9          elif("EPNLnT" in riga[0]):
10             EPNL_not_tone_test_case_wing = riga[1]
11
12             elif("HORIZONTAL" in riga[0] or "VERTICAL" in riga[0]
13 or "SLAT" in riga[0] or "FLAP" in riga[0] or
14 "MAIN" in riga[0] or "NOSE" in riga[0] or
15 "AIRFRAME" in riga[0] or "ENGINE" in riga[0] or
16 "TOTAL" in riga[0]):
17                 break

```

Listing 3.8: Results general acquisition procedure, applicable to CS-25 functions, for the wing contribution.

The acquisition logic is similar to the one used to manage the engine file; in fact, idea is to read the output file, considering it like a sequence of rows and using an iterative procedure to evaluate every row in function of the first element in it. The first element, generally, contains a key-word to identify the row, in order to acquire the specific data of interest; naturally, in the CS-25 case the data type of interest is the EPNL value and the key-words will be in function of this metric. This procedure, in the end, needs an arrest function to avoid a wrong data acquisition (it is important to remember that in the result file every contribution has the same scheme, as it is possible to see Fig.3.25, and this is the reason why the iterative acquisition procedure needs a control to avoid overwriting of the results).

TOTAL AIRCRAFT (WITH ATMOSPHERIC ATTENUATION, GROUND REFLECTION AND LATERAL ATTENUATION) - CORRECTED										
Time (s);	0.0;	2.2;	3.1;	3.8;	4.4;	4.9;	5.4;	5.8;	6.2;	6.6;
Frequency; SPL (dB);										
50 Hz;	nan;	39.9;	40.0;	40.2;	40.4;	40.5;	40.7;	40.8;	41.0;	41.2;
63 Hz;	nan;	31.3;	31.5;	31.7;	31.9;	32.0;	32.2;	32.4;	32.6;	32.8;
80 Hz;	nan;	16.7;	16.9;	17.1;	17.3;	17.5;	17.7;	17.9;	18.1;	18.3;
100 Hz;	nan;	1.0;	1.2;	1.4;	1.6;	1.8;	2.0;	2.2;	2.5;	2.7;
125 Hz;	nan;	-12.7;	-12.5;	-12.4;	-12.2;	-12.0;	-11.8;	-11.7;	-11.5;	-11.3;
160 Hz;	nan;	-23.1;	-23.0;	-22.9;	-22.8;	-22.6;	-22.5;	-22.3;	-22.1;	-21.9;
200 Hz;	nan;	-27.2;	-27.1;	-27.0;	-27.0;	-26.9;	-26.8;	-26.6;	-26.5;	-26.2;
250 Hz;	nan;	-24.1;	-24.1;	-24.0;	-24.0;	-23.9;	-23.9;	-23.8;	-23.7;	-23.6;
315 Hz;	nan;	-16.2;	-16.1;	-16.1;	-16.1;	-16.1;	-16.0;	-16.0;	-15.9;	-15.9;
400 Hz;	nan;	-7.9;	-7.9;	-7.8;	-7.8;	-7.8;	-7.7;	-7.7;	-7.7;	-7.6;
500 Hz;	nan;	-1.2;	-1.2;	-1.1;	-1.1;	-1.1;	-1.0;	-1.0;	-1.0;	-0.9;
630 Hz;	nan;	5.3;	5.4;	5.4;	5.5;	5.5;	5.5;	5.6;	5.6;	5.7;
800 Hz;	nan;	11.9;	11.9;	12.0;	12.0;	12.1;	12.1;	12.2;	12.2;	12.3;
1000 Hz;	nan;	16.7;	16.8;	16.9;	16.9;	17.0;	17.0;	17.1;	17.2;	17.2;
1250 Hz;	nan;	20.6;	20.7;	20.8;	20.8;	20.9;	21.0;	21.0;	21.1;	21.2;
1600 Hz;	nan;	25.1;	25.2;	25.3;	25.3;	25.4;	25.5;	25.6;	25.6;	25.7;
2000 Hz;	nan;	27.4;	27.5;	27.6;	27.7;	27.8;	27.9;	28.0;	28.1;	28.2;
2500 Hz;	nan;	31.1;	31.2;	31.3;	31.4;	31.5;	31.6;	31.8;	31.9;	32.0;
3150 Hz;	nan;	31.2;	31.4;	31.5;	31.6;	31.8;	31.9;	32.0;	32.2;	32.3;
4000 Hz;	nan;	27.5;	27.6;	27.8;	27.9;	28.1;	28.3;	28.4;	28.6;	28.8;
5000 Hz;	nan;	19.3;	19.5;	19.7;	19.9;	20.1;	20.3;	20.5;	20.8;	21.0;
6300 Hz;	nan;	6.3;	6.6;	6.9;	7.2;	7.5;	7.8;	8.0;	8.3;	8.6;
8000 Hz;	nan;	-21.1;	-20.7;	-20.3;	-19.9;	-19.5;	-19.1;	-18.7;	-18.3;	-17.8;
10000 Hz;	nan;	-65.0;	-64.4;	-63.8;	-63.3;	-62.7;	-62.1;	-61.5;	-60.9;	-60.3;
OASPL (dB);	nan;	41.9;	42.0;	42.2;	42.3;	42.5;	42.6;	42.8;	43.0;	43.1;
PNL (PNdB);	-inf;	48.0;	48.1;	48.3;	48.4;	48.5;	48.7;	48.8;	48.9;	49.1;
PNLT (PNdB);	-inf;	48.2;	48.3;	48.4;	48.6;	48.7;	48.8;	49.0;	49.1;	49.2;
(Tone Corr.);	0.0;	0.2;	0.2;	0.2;	0.2;	0.2;	0.2;	0.2;	0.2;	0.2;
EPNLnT (EPNdB);	103.0									
EPNL (EPNdB);	103.8									

Figure 3.25: General scheme of the Result file for a several contribution.

The control and arrest function will change in function of the contribution to evaluate, due to the fact that there is a precise sequence of all contributions to respect:

1. **WING CONTRIBUTION;**
2. **HORIZONTAL TAIL CONTRIBUTION;**
3. **VERTICAL TAIL CONTRIBUTION;**

4. SLAT CONTRIBUTION;
5. FLAP CONTRIBUTION;
6. MAIN LANDING GEAR CONTRIBUTION;
7. NOSE LANDING GEAR CONTRIBUTION;
8. AIRFRAME CONTRIBUTION;
9. ENGINE(S) CONTRIBUTION;
10. TOTAL AIRCRAFT CONTRIBUTION.

Therefore, everyone of these contributions will be managed considering their successive contributions as stop parameters.

After all code's blocks that perform the output data acquisition for every possible contribution, there is the uploading of the main results in the final CPACS file in the OUTPUT section of the *Toolspecific* part of it. To upload these data in the CPACS file, several *txi* functions will be used.

In conclusion, the difference between the functions for every test case is the reference output file, that is going to be read (to remember the results management see Fig.2.24), and the acquired data location in the CPACS file; in general, the output file to consider is the *.txt* most relevant file, located in the main folder of the specific test case (in this folder there will be the log file, the MAP file and the sub-folder for all microphones files); while the CPACS location can be seen in Fig.3.27.

```
<CUMULATIVE>
  <EPNL>267.600000</EPNL>
  <EPNL_NT>264.900000</EPNL_NT>
  <EPNL_certification_limit>281.486249</EPNL_certification_limit>
  <EPNL_certification_margin>13.886249</EPNL_certification_margin>
  <EPNL_NT_certification_margin>16.586249</EPNL_NT_certification_margin>
</CUMULATIVE>
```

Figure 3.26: Example of the Noise Tool cumulative results sub-folder in the CPACS file.

As it is possible to see in Fig.3.27, there is an extra sub-folder, named "CUMULATIVE", where all total results of every test case (Approach, Lateral, Fly-Over) have been summed in a unique value, due to certification purposes (see Fig.3.26).

```

<OUTPUT>
  <description>Tool developed to estimate the 'Certified Noise Levels'. The results has been estimated for:
  The cases' cumulative condition; The single cases and The several contributions.</description>
  <APPROACH>
    <EPNL>
      <description>Effective Perceived Noise Levels with Tone Correction</description>
      <Total Tone Corr_EPNL>92.800000</Total Tone Corr_EPNL>
      <CONTRIBUTIONS>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_wing_contr>72.500000</EPNL_Tone_Corr_wing_contr>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_horiz_contr>64.600000</EPNL_Tone_Corr_horiz_contr>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_vert_contr>-inf</EPNL_Tone_Corr_vert_contr>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_slats_contr>76.100000</EPNL_Tone_Corr_slats_contr>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_flap_contr>77.500000</EPNL_Tone_Corr_flap_contr>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_Main_Gear_contr>71.400000</EPNL_Tone_Corr_Main_Gear_contr>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_Nose_Gear_contr>65.600000</EPNL_Tone_Corr_Nose_Gear_contr>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_Airframe_contr>81.500000</EPNL_Tone_Corr_Airframe_contr>
        <EPNL_Tone_Corr_Engine_contr mapType="vector">89.200000;89.200000</EPNL_Tone_Corr_Engine_contr>
      </CONTRIBUTIONS>
      <EPNL_certification_limit>98.000000</EPNL_certification_limit>
      <EPNL_certification_margin>5.200000</EPNL_certification_margin>
    </EPNL>
    <EPNL_NT>
      <description>Effective Perceived Noise Levels without Tone Correction</description>
      <Total_EPNL>92.000000</Total_EPNL>
      <CONTRIBUTIONS>
        <EPNL_wing_contr>72.000000</EPNL_wing_contr>
        <EPNL_horiz_contr>64.100000</EPNL_horiz_contr>
        <EPNL_vert_contr>-inf</EPNL_vert_contr>
        <EPNL_slats_contr>75.600000</EPNL_slats_contr>
        <EPNL_flap_contr>77.000000</EPNL_flap_contr>
        <EPNL_Main_Gear_contr>70.900000</EPNL_Main_Gear_contr>
        <EPNL_Nose_Gear_contr>65.000000</EPNL_Nose_Gear_contr>
        <EPNL_Airframe_contr>81.100000</EPNL_Airframe_contr>
        <EPNL_Engine_contr mapType="vector">88.500000;88.500000</EPNL_Engine_contr>
      </CONTRIBUTIONS>
      <EPNL_NT_certification_limit>98.000000</EPNL_NT_certification_limit>
      <EPNL_NT_certification_margin>6.000000</EPNL_NT_certification_margin>
    </EPNL_NT>
  </APPROACH>
  <FLYOVER>
  <LATERAL>
  <CUMULATIVE>
</OUTPUT>

```

Figure 3.27: Example of the Noise Tool results management in the specific test case sub-folder in the CPACS file.

Output Function CS-23

Regarding the CS-23 regulation case, the most important difference with respect to the CS-25 case is the reference sound metric that is the maximum value of the OASPL acquired at different time steps. In function of this aspect, the data acquisition procedure is a bit different because, first of all, the code has to acquire a vector and not directly a numerical value, moreover, after this acquisition, it has to find the maximum value of this vector and this will be the data to acquire. As it is possible to understand, observing the listing 3.9, code will define the OASPL vector and the Tone correction vector, taking from the results' file the number of time steps (the number of time steps corresponds to the vectors length) and, then, it will acquire all OASPL values and tone correction values in the same manner of the previous case, implementing the same control and arrest function, used

before; the only add is the necessity to convert "NaN" values and "-inf" values in the "0" value, because, theoretically, these expressions corresponds to a none value. In the end, Tone correction and OASPL vectors will be summed and the maximum value of this final vector will be calculated.

```

1  # OASPL vector length evaluation
3  for line in lateral:
4      riga = line_split(Filler)
5      if("Time" in riga[0]):
6          OASPL_vector_length = length(riga) - 1
7
8      # Wing contribution
9      if(wing_contribution_printing = 1 and wing_contribution = 1):
10         OASPL_wing_vect =
11             vector_initialization(OASPL_vector_length)
12         Tone_corr_vect =
13             vector_initialization(OASPL_vector_length)
14
15         for line in lateral:
16             riga = line_split(Filler)
17
18             if ("OASPL" in riga[0]):
19                 for i in range(1, OASPL_vector_length + 1):
20                     OASPL_wing_vect[i - 1] = riga[i]
21
22                     if ("NaN" or "-inf" in riga[i]):
23                         OASPL_wing_vect[i - 1] = 0
24
25                     elif ("Tone" in riga[0]):
26                         for i in range(1, OASPL_vector_length+1):
27                             Tone_corr_vect[i - 1] = riga[i]
28
29                             if("NaN" or "-inf" in riga[i]):
30                                 Tone_corr_vect[i - 1] = 0
31
32                     elif ("HORIZONTAL" in riga[0] or
33                         "VERTICAL" in riga[0] or "SLAT" in riga[0]
34                         or "FLAP" in riga[0] or "MAIN" in riga[0] or
35                         "NOSE" in riga[0] or "AIRFRAME" in riga[0] or
36                         "ENGINE" in riga[0] or "TOTAL" in riga[0]):
37                         break
38
39         # Tone correction and OASPL sum
40         OASPL_TC_wing_vect =
41             vector_initialization(OASPL_vector_length)

```

```

43     for j in range(0, OASPL_vector_length):
        OASPL_TC_wing_vect[j] =
            OASPL_wing_vect[j] + Tone_corr_vect[j]
45
        # Find Max value
47     OASPL_lat_wing = maximum_value(OASPL_TC_wing_vect)

```

Listing 3.9: Results general acquisition procedure, applicable to CS-23 function, for the wing contribution.

The updating part of this function is the same used for the CS-25 functions; but, in this case, there is no necessity to evaluate a cumulative case, because in the CS-23 certification case there is the Lateral/Take-Off test case alone.

3.3.12 Margin Calculation Function

The final function, that close the integration tool, is the margin calculation function. The margin calculation consists in the comparing of the total noise emissions of the aircraft, obtained with the tool running and the results management, for every test case and every certification case, with the certification limits defined for the CS-25 and CS-23 regulations. The limits, as it has been described in paragraphs 2.3.1 and 2.3.2, can be calculated in function of the aircraft's MTOW and the engine's number; in function of these, the margin calculation function will, simply, receive, in input, the noise emissions cited before and then, taking from the CPACS file MTOW and engine's number, it is able to calculate the accurate limits and the consequential margin values; in the end, these data will be uploaded in the *CPACS Toolspecific* section, as it can be seen in Figs.3.27 and 3.26. The only differences between the CS-25 and CS-23 cases are:

- **Limits Laws** which depends on the regulation's rules (see Figs.2.12, 2.5 and 2.16);
- **Presence of Cumulative Limit** in the CS-25 regulation and **Absence** of it in the CS-23 regulation.
- **Different Test Cases for the CS-25 Regulation** (Approach, Lateral, Fly-Over), while a **Single Test Case** (Lateral) in the **CS-23 Regulation** (as it happens for the output management).

3.3.13 CPACS Output File

The integration tool will complete its assignment with the update of the CPACS file through the output functions seen previously. It is important to remember and underline that the CPACS output file is the CPACS input file updated with the additions of the Noise Tool's results and the associated limits and margins.

3.4 Noise Tool's Trajectories

3.4.1 Introduction

The Trajectories' class contains all functions necessary to update the *Trajectory.csv* files, exploiting the regulation constrains and procedures, in order to estimate several simplified flight paths for all test cases. The main improvement applied to these functions, so, is the possibility to evaluate automatically simplified trajectories that could be used for other applications which need them; moreover, the trajectories functions are able to plot and print these estimated paths. In function of this aspect, the general architecture of the standard trajectory's function can be divided in four main sections:

1. **CPACS Data Acquisition:** the first actions, that code will perform, are the data acquisitions from the CPACS Input file (see Fig.3.28) and, as it is going to be seen in the following sections, there are several parameters from the *Toolspecific* section, some other from the fixed section and the remaining ones estimated through the *tigl* function;
2. **Performances Estimation:** the core of the trajectory function is this its section, where all main performances and path's data are going to be estimated through the path's relations and constrains, defined by the reference regulation that characterizes the trajectory's calculation (the trajectories' functions, in fact, will be classified in function of the reference regulation between CS-25 and CS-23 in addition to the path's type classification);
3. **Vector Setting and File Updating:** after the path's calculations, code will create and manage several vectors, if it should be necessary, in order

to discretize the path's phases, concerning the parameters to add in the *Trajectory.csv* file; then, the file updating will be processed on the basis of a standard scheme (see listing 3.10);

4. **Results' Printing and Plotting:** the final section of the generic trajectory code concerns the plotting of the specific flight path and, moreover, the plotting of the time-histories of the flight's parameters printed in the *Trajectory.csv* file:

- **Climb Angle;**
- **Throttle Rate;**
- **Aircraft Speed;**

This section is an improvement developed in this thesis work; moreover, a trajectory's smoothing function has been developed to make these graphs more smooth and realistic.

```
<cpacs xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xsi:noNamespaceSchemaLocation="cpacs_sc
| <toolspecific>
|   <UNINA_NoiseTool>
|     <Description>UNINA_NoiseTool v1.0</Description>
|     <INPUT>
|       <Control Parameters>
|       <Inputs>
|       <Receivers>
|       <Trajectory>
|         <Parameter_evaluation>1</Parameter_evaluation>
|         <description>Parameter type. [0-UNINA ToolSpecific; 1-CPACS Vehicle]</description>
|         <CS23>
|           <Lateral>
|         </CS23>
|         <CS25>
|           <Approach>
|           <Lateral>
|           <FlyOver>
|         </CS25>
|       </Trajectory>
|     </INPUT>
|   </UNINA_NoiseTool>
| </toolspecific>
</cpacs>
```

Figure 3.28: Trajectory section in the CPACS Noise Toolspecific.

Examining in depth the previous sections, about the data acquisition, it is important to highlight the usefulness of the *Parameter_evaluation*, that is a CPACS parameter located in the Trajectory's section of the CPACS Toolspecific. In fact, this parameter is a switching command, used to choose the source folder of several CPACS parameters: being more precise, this command permits to take several parameters, or from the fixed part of the CPACS file or from the *UNINA ToolSpecific* (in

particular from the "Perfo_Input" and "RubberEngine_and_MassUpdate_results" sub-levels), as it is going to be seen in the following paragraphs.

Regarding the .csv file update, in the listing 3.10, it is possible to observe the basic scheme to respect; in particular, it is important to underline the possibility to exploit a linear extrapolation to directly discretize the parameters' trend (for the Approach calculation this extrapolation procedure will be exploited).

```

2  %% TRAJECTORY FILE-CASE: xxxxx

4  %%%%%%%%% SOURCE POSITIONS DATA
   %%%%%%%%% POSITIONS
6  %% X: Aircraft position along X axis.
   %% Y: Aircraft position along Y axis.
8  %% Z: Aircraft position along Z axis.
   %% V: Aircraft Velocity.
10 %% THROTTLE_RATE: Rate of throttle.
   %% CLIMB_ANGLE: Climb angle.
12 %% FLAP_DEFL: Flap deflection angle.
   %% SLAT_ON: Slat contribution [0 - Slat Off; 1 - Slat On]
14 %% MLG_ON: Main landing gears contribution
   [0 - Main Landing Gears In; 1 - Main Landing Gears Out]
16 %% NLG_ON: Nose landing gear contribution
   [0 - Nose Landing Gears In; 1 - Nose Landing Gears Out]
18 %%%%%%%%%%% REFERENCE TIMES
   %% TIME: Instant of time
20 %%%%%%%%%%% ATMOSPHERIC PARAMETERS
   %%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE DEFAULT ATMOSPHERIC VALUES
22 ARE CALCULATED USING THE ISA MODEL %%%%%%%%%
   %% T: Ambient temperature at microphone location.
24 %% P: Ambient pressure at microphone location.
   %% RHO: Ambient density at microphone location.
26 %% NU: Ambient kinematic viscosity at microphone location.
   %% GAMMA: Specific heat ratio of air at microphone location.
28 %% C: Ambient sound speed at microphone location.
   %% M: Mach Number
30 %%%%%%%%% INPUT FOR LINEAR TRAJECTORY
   %%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS MUST ALWAYS FOLLOW
32 THE PREVIOUS COORDINATE LIST %%%%%%%%%
   %% NAME: Trajectory name.
34 %% ENG_SETTING: Select the thrust rating.
   [1-Max take-off rating; 2-Cruise rating]
36 %%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS ARE USED ONLY
   IF A LINEAR EXTRAPOLATION IS REQUESTED %%%%%%%%%
38 %% LINEAR:: Use a linear trajectory extrapolated

```

```

from the first row indicated below
40 (under X,Y,Z,THROTTLE_RATE,CLIMB_ANGLE,V labels).
[1-Extrapolate trajectory; 0-Not required (Default)]
42 %% Extrapolation's parameters are N_LIN and DELTA_LIN.
%% The atmospheric conditions are always calculated
44 internally if LINEAR is 1.
%% N_LIN:: Number of source positions that will be calculated
46 if LINEAR is set to 1.
%% DELTA_LIN: Time interval between two consecutive source
48 positions that will be calculated if LINEAR is set to 1.

```

Listing 3.10: General scheme of the Trajectory's input file in *.csv* format

In conclusion, regarding the plotting and printing section, all figures, obtained with plotting functions, will be directly uploaded in a specific folder in the Integration Tool folder (see Fig.3.11).

3.4.2 Approach Case CS-25

CPACS Data Acquisition

The Approach case will work on the base of the CS-25 regulation (see paragraph 2.3.1) and the input data from the CPACS file can be divided in the ones from the Noise *Toolspecific* section (see Table 3.19), in the ones from the *UNINA Toolspecific* section (see Table 3.18) and the ones that depend on the switching parameter, i.e. the *Parameter_evaluation* (see Table 3.20). In addition, in this function is necessary to exploit, aside from the switching parameter discussion, the *tigl* function to extract the slat contribution parameter, in order to evaluate the presence of the slat itself (see listing 3.11). Moreover, the *tigl* function has to be exploited to acquire the main wing surface and span in case of *Parameter_evaluation* assigned to act on the CPACS fixed part (see Table 3.20).

Regarding the switching parameter case, if this one will choose the fixed part source, the data acquisition procedure, based on the *tigl* function, will be the same seen in listing 3.5.

```

1 Slat_check =
    tixi_check_element(CPACS_path + "leadingEdgeDevice")
3
    if (Slat_check = True and Slat_eval = 1):
5         Slat_contr = 1
    else:
7         Slat_contr = 0

```

Listing 3.11: Slat contribution evaluation.

Variable Name	Description
Cd0	CD_0 value
Dcd0_LN	Delta CD_0 due to Flap in Landing
delta_cD0_landing_gears	Delta CD_0 due to Landing Gears in Landing
eLN	Oswald Factor in the Landing phase
CLmaxLN	CL_max in Landing phase
flap_deflection	Flap deflection during Landing

Table 3.18: Approach CS-25 trajectory input parameters from the UNINA Toolspecific section.

Variable Name	Description
X_norm_lenght	Approach distance along X axis from regulations
Y_norm_lenght	Approach distance along Y axis from regulations
Z_norm_lenght	Approach distance along Z axis from regulations
Climb_angle_norm	Approach climb angle from regulations
Slat_contribution	Include Flap action in Approach
Name_Case	Trajectory Name (Recommend - APPROACH TRAJECTORY)
Engine_Setting	Select the thrust rating. [1-Max take-off rating; 2-Cruise rating]
Max_Cruise_Thrust	Max Cruise Thrust of a single Engine
Linear	Use a linear trajectory extrapolated from the first row under POSITIONS [1-Extrapolate trajectory; 0-Not required (Default)]
Number_Linear	Number of source positions that will be calculated if LINEAR is set to 1.
Delta_Linear	Time interval between two consecutive positions that will be calculated if LINEAR is set to 1.

Table 3.19: Approach CS-25 trajectory input parameters from the Noise Toolspecific section.

UNINA ToolSpecific	
mMLM_new	Maximum Landing Mass
Sw	Main wing surface (m^2)
bw	Main wing span (m)
CPACS fixed part	
mMLM	Maximum Landing Mass
Surf_Area	Main wing surface (m^2)
Span	Main wing span (m)

Table 3.20: Trajectory input parameters managed with the *Parameter_evaluation*.

Performances Estimation

With the conclusion of data acquisition, the approach function will start to estimate the flight path exploiting the performances' equations of a generic landing phase, with the specifications from the CS-25 regulation, as they have been described in paragraph 2.3.1. In the listing 3.12, it is possible to understand the logic sequence of equations which lead to the approach distances estimations, in addition to the estimations of the approach speed and the throttle rate.

```

1 # Calculation
3 V_s_lan = sqrt( (2 * Max_Land_mass * 9.81) / (1.225 * CL_max_Land * Surf_Area) )
5 V_appr = 1.23 * V_s_lan
7 CL_land = (Max_Land_mass * 9.81 * cos(|Climb_Ang_norm|)) / (0.5 * 1.225 * (V_appr^2) * Surf_Area)
9 CD_land = (CL_land^2) / (pi * Aspect_Ratio * Oswald_fact_appr) + CD0_appr +
11 Delta_CD0_appr_flap + Delta_CD0_appr_LG

```

```

13 D_land = CD_land * 0.5 * 1.225 * V_appr2 * Surf_Area
15 Trust_land = D_land - Max_Land_mass * 9.81 * sin(|Climb_Ang_norm|)
17 T_max_cruise = Max_Eng_Thrust_cruise * Num_Eng
19 Throttle_rate =  $\frac{Trust\_land}{T\_max\_cruise}$ 

```

Listing 3.12: Approach performances estimation procedure showed in pseudo-code.

Vector Setting and File Updating

The performances data, acquired with the simplified estimation, can be exploited to update the *Trajectory.csv* file, as it can be seen in the listing 3.13. As it has been anticipated, in the Approach case the linear extrapolation tool is going to be exploited and implemented in the Noise Tool; moreover, in function of this aspect, there is no necessity to set vectors for all input parameters, even if, to plot the flight path, some vectors have to be defined.

```

2 # Write CSV file (Trajectory Approach)
  write_file(TrajectoryApproach.csv):
4
   %%%%%%%%%%%%% SOURCE POSITIONS DATA
6   %%%%%%%%%%%%% POSITIONS
   X,Y,Z,V,THROTTLE_RATE,CLIMB_ANGLE,FLAP_DEFL,SLAT_ON,
8   MLG_ON,NLG_ON
10
   X_norm, Y_norm, Z_norm, V_appr, Throttle_rate,
   Climb_Ang_norm, Flap_defl_appr, Slat_contr, 1, 1
12
   %%%%%%%%%%%%% INPUT FOR LINEAR TRAJECTORY
14   %%%%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS MUST ALWAYS FOLLOW
   THE PREVIOUS COORDINATE LIST %%%%%%%%%%
16   NAME, Name_case
   ENG_SETTING, Eng_setting
18   %%%%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS ARE USED ONLY
   IF A LINEAR EXTRAPOLATION IS REQUESTED %%%%%%%%%%
20   LINEAR, Linear
   N_LIN, Num_Lin
22   DELTA_LIN, Delta_lin

```

Listing 3.13: Approach trajectory's file update.

Results' Printing and Plotting

The final part of the approach function concerns the flight path plotting. The reason why there is no plotting of the other parameters' time-histories is that in the Approach case they have constant (engine throttle and climb angle) or linear (velocity) trends. An example of the Approach flight path can be seen in Fig.3.29; it is important to highlight the smooth trend of the flight path between the approach phase and the landing grounding phase, which is due to the smoothing function that is going to be discussed in detail in paragraph 3.4.5.

Figure 3.29: Example of simplified approach trajectory on the base of CS-25 regulation.

3.4.3 Take-Off Case CS-25

CPACS Data Acquisition

The Take-Off case can work for both regulations and, in function of this aspect, it is necessary to distinguish the Take-Off function for the CS-25 case and the CS-23

case; in this paragraph, the function based on the CS-25 regulation (see paragraph 2.3.1) will be discussed. Concerning the data acquisition, the input data from the CPACS file can be divided in the ones from the *Noise Toolspecific* section (see Table 3.21), in the ones from the *UNINA Toolspecific* section (see Table 3.22) and the ones that depend on the switching parameter, i.e. the *Parameter_evaluation* (see Table 3.20).

As it happens for the Approach case, the slat contribution's management follows the procedure seen in listing 3.11 and the *tigl* function has to be exploited to acquire the main wing surface and span in case of *Parameter_evaluation* assigned to act on the CPACS fixed part (see Table 3.20). Moreover, there are some parameters to take from the fixed part of the CPACS file, concerning the main landing gears structure (*MLG_lenght* and *MLG_fus_attach_z*); this is due to the fact that this information will be used to perform the estimation calculations. In conclusion, there are some other parameters, concerning the Thrust and Speed's evolution during Take-Off, which can be taken from the *Noise Toolspecific* section or, alternatively, from the *UNINA Toolspecific*, even if the code will give priority to the *UNINA Toolspecific* ones.

Regarding the switching parameter case, if this one will choose the fixed part source, the data acquisition procedure, based on the *tigl* function, is the same seen in listing 3.5.

Variable Name	Description
Z_Obstacle	Virtual Obstacle from FAR requirement
Z_climb	Vertical distance to define the Climb phase in Take-Off
Z_FlyOver	Vertical distance to define the Fly-Over phase in Take-Off

It will continues in the next page...

Variable Name	Description
Delta_CD0_Flap	Delta CD0 contribution due to Flap deflection
Delta_CD0_LandingGear	Delta CD0 contribution due to Landing Gears
Name_Case	Trajectory Name (Recommend - LATERAL TRAJECTORY)
Engine_Setting	Select the thrust rating. [1-Max take-off rating; 2-Cruise rating]
Slat_contribution	Include Slat action in Take-Off
Max_TakeOff_Thrust	Max Take-Off Thrust of a single Engine
MainGear_contribution	Main Landing Gears setting [0-Retractable Gears; 1-Fixed Gears]
NoseGear_contribution	Nose Landing Gears setting [0-Retractable Gear; 1-Fixed Gear]
Number_Ground	Intervals' number for Grounding discretization
Number_Airborne	Intervals' number for Airborne discretization
Number_Climb	Intervals' number for Climb discretization
Number_FlyOver	Intervals' number for Fly-Over discretization
Speed_vector	VMC vector evolution during Lateral
TO_Thrust_vector	Take-Off Thrust Vector in function of VMC evolution during Lateral

Table 3.21: Take-Off CS-25 trajectory input parameters from the Noise Toolspecific section.

Variable Name	Description
Cd0	CD_0 value
CL_G	CL_g value
mig	Wheel-Runway rolling friction coefficient
eTO	Oswald Factor in the Take-Off phase
CLmaxTO	CL_max in Take-Off phase
nlof	Lift-Off load factor
n2	Virtual obstacle load factor
flap_deflection	Flap deflection during Take-Off
Speed_for_VMC	VMC vector evolution during Lateral
TO_net_thrust_for_VMC	Take-Off Thrust Vector in function of VMC evolution during Lateral

Table 3.22: Take-Off CS-25 trajectory input parameters from the UNINA Toolspecific section.

As anticipated in the data acquisition phase, some parameters, concerning the Thrust and Speed evolution during Take-Off, have been taken from the CPACS file; their usefulness is linked to the necessity to define an interpolation law of the engine's thrust in function of the aircraft's speed, during the Take-Off phase, in order to know the correct engine thrust at a several aircraft's speed condition; its practical application will be seen in the following paragraph, while in the listing 3.14 the interpolation procedure has been showed.

```

1 Speed_vector = tixi_get_vector
3   (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Speed_for_VMC")
Thrust_vector = tixi_get_vector
5   (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "TO_net_thrust_for_VMC")

7 ## Thrust Vector Interpolation

```

```

Thrust_interp =
9     make_interp_spline(Speed_vector , Thrust_vector)

```

Listing 3.14: Engine Thrust interpolation law in function of the aircraft's speed (using UNINA Toolspecific parameters).

Performances Estimation

With the conclusion of data acquisition, the Take-Off function will start to estimate the flight path exploiting the performances' equations of a generic Take-Off phase, with the specifications from the CS-25 regulation, as they have been described in paragraph 2.3.1. In this case, the flight path has to be divided in several sub-paths which correspond to the several phases of a generic Take-Off procedure:

1. **Grounding Phase;**
2. **Airborne Phase;**
3. **Climb Phase;**
4. **Cut-Back Fly-Over Phase;**

The estimation will be performed in different calculation steps, function of the Take-Off's phases. In the listing 3.15, it is possible to understand the logic sequence of equations which lead to the Take-Off distances estimations, in addition to several Speeds, Throttle Rates and Climb Angles.

```

### Calculation
2  ## Grounding
z_ground = MLG_lenght + |MLG_fus_attach_z|
4
z_k = z_ground + z_wing
6
8  K_es =  $\frac{\left(\frac{16*z_k}{Span}\right)^2}{1 + \left(\frac{16*z_k}{Span}\right)^2}$ 
CD_ground =  $\frac{(CL_g)^2 * K_es}{\pi * Aspect\_Ratio * Oswald\_fact\_lat}$  + CD0_gr +
10      Delta_CD0_flap + Delta_CD0_LG
12
V_s_TO =  $\sqrt{\frac{2 * Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81}{1.225 * CL\_max\_TO * Surf\_Area}}$ 

```

```

14 V_lift_off = 1.1 * V_s_TO
16
18 D_gr = CD_ground * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V_lift_off * 0.7)2 * Surf_Area
18 L_gr = CL_g * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V_lift_off * 0.7)2 * Surf_Area
18 Thrust_ground =
20     Thrust_interp(V_lift_off * 0.7) * Num_eng * 1000
22
22 S_ground =  $\frac{\frac{Max\_TO\_mass}{2} * (V\_lift\_off)^2}{Thrust\_ground - D\_gr - mi * (Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81 - L\_gr)}$ 
24
24 ## Airborne
26 V_obs = 1.2 * V_s_TO
28
28 K_es_air =  $\frac{\left(\frac{16 * z_obs}{Span}\right)^2}{1 + \left(\frac{16 * z_obs}{Span}\right)^2}$ 
30
30 CL_air =  $\frac{Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81}{0.5 * 1.225 * (V\_obs)^2 * Surf\_Area}$ 
32
32 CD_air =  $\frac{(CL\_air)^2 * K\_es\_air}{\pi * Aspect\_Ratio * Oswald\_fact\_lat}$  + CD0_gr +
34     Delta_CD0_flap + Delta_CD0_LG
36
36 D_air = CD_air * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V_obs)2 * Surf_Area
38
38 Thrust_air = Thrust_interp(V_obs) * Num_eng * 1000
40
40 gamma_air = arcsin  $\left(\frac{Thrust\_air - D\_air}{Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81}\right)$ 
42
42 gamma_air_deg = math_degrees(gamma_air)
44
44 n_air =  $\frac{n\_loff + n\_obs}{2}$ 
46
46 Air_Radius =  $\frac{(1.15 * V\_s\_TO)^2}{9.81 * (n\_air - 1)}$ 
48
48 Theta_air = arccos  $\left(1 - \frac{z\_obs}{Air\_Radius}\right)$ 
50
50 S_air = Air_Radius * sin(Theta_air)
52
52 ## Take-Off Climb
52 V_TO_climb = V_obs + (15 * 0.514444)

```

```

54

$$CL_{climb} = \frac{Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81}{0.5 * 1.225 * (V\_TO\_climb)^2 * Surf\_Area}$$

56

$$CD_{climb} = \frac{(CL_{climb})^2}{\pi * Aspect\_Ratio * Oswald\_fact\_lat} + CD0\_gr + Delta\_CD0\_flap$$

58

$$D_{climb} = CD_{climb} * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V\_TO\_climb)^2 * Surf\_Area$$

60

$$Thrust_{climb} = Thrust\_interp(V\_TO\_climb) * Num\_eng * 1000$$

62

$$\gamma_{climb} = \arcsin\left(\frac{Thrust_{climb} - D_{climb}}{Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81}\right)$$

64

$$\gamma_{climb\_deg} = \text{math\_degrees}(\gamma_{climb})$$

66

$$z_{climb\_corr} = z_{climb} - z_{obs}$$

68

$$S_{climb} = \frac{z_{climb\_corr}}{\tan(\gamma_{climb})}$$

70 ## Flyover
   climb_grad = 0.04 # rad
72 CD_OEI = 0.005
   CD_CutBack = CD_climb + CD_OEI
74
   D_CutBack =
76     CD_CutBack * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V_TO_climb)^2 * Surf_Area
   Thrust_CutBack_OEI =
78     D_CutBack + Max_TO_mass * 9.81 * sin(climb_grad)
   Thrust_FO = Thrust_climb
80
   Throttle_rate_FO =  $\frac{Thrust\_CutBack\_OEI}{Thrust\_FO}$ 
82
   Thrust_FlyOver =
84     Throttle_rate_FO * Thrust_interp(0) * Num_eng * 1000
86
   CD_FO = CD_climb
   D_FO = CD_FO * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V_TO_climb)^2 * Surf_Area
88
   gamma_FO =  $\arcsin\left(\frac{Thrust\_FlyOver - D\_FO}{Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81}\right)$ 
90
   gamma_FO_deg = math_degrees(gamma_FO)
92
   S_FO = 8000 - (S_ground + S_air + S_climb)
   Z_FO = S_FO * tan(gamma_FO) + z_climb
94
   ## Extended Take-Off Climb
96
   x_extended = S_FO_round - 500

```

```

z_extended = x_extended * tan(gamma_climb)
98 x_extended_vect = vector_creation
    (S_climb_round + S_ground_round + S_air_round,
100     S_climb_round + S_ground_round +
    S_air_round + x_extended)
102 z_extended_vect =
    vector_creation(z_climb, z_climb + z_extended)

```

Listing 3.15: Take-Off CS-25 performances estimation procedure showed in pseudo-code.

In particular, the Cut-Back Fly-Over phase will follow a particular procedure to evaluate the final engine throttle, that is reduced to perform the Cut-Back manoeuvre and the climb angle: this procedure assumes a fixed climb gradient, that should correspond to a one engine inoperative (OEI) flight condition; so, in function of this aspect, it is possible to determine the theoretical engine thrust with OEI; then, the final engine throttle will be calculated in function of this thrust with OEI and the thrust of the previous flight phase; and, consequently, the final climb angle can be estimated. In the end, the extended Take-Off climb phase has been estimated: this phase corresponds to the climb condition without the Cut-Back correction and its evaluation is important to compare these trends, not only on the noise emissions point of view, but also on the practical point of view.

Vector Setting and File Updating

The performances data, acquired with the simplified estimation, can be exploited to update the *Trajectory.csv* files (Lateral and Fly-Over), as it can be seen in the listing 3.17. To update correctly the Lateral and Fly-Over files, it is necessary to define several vectors of the main input parameters, in order to create a discretized sequence of points for all parameters (the linear interpolation function is not going to be used) and in the listing 3.16 this process has been shown.

```

1  ### Vectors Creation
   ## Grounding
3  # X
   N_ground = tixi_get_element
5     (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Number_Ground")
   x_ground_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
7     (0, S_ground, N_ground)
   for in N_ground:

```

```

9     x_ground_vect = x_ground_vect

11  # Velocity
    for in N_ground:
13     v_ground_vect = 2.2918 * x_ground_vect0.4923

15  # Throttle Rate
    Initial_Throttle_ground = 0.1

17
    ## Airborne
19  # X
    N_air = tixi_get_element
21     (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Number_Airborne")
    x_air_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
23     (S_ground, (S_ground + S_air), N_air)
    for in N_air:
25     x_air_vect = x_air_vect

27  # Z
    N_air_z = N_air / 5

29
    for in N_air_z:
31     z_air_vect = z_ground

33  delta_z_air =  $\frac{z_{obs} - z_{ground}}{N_{air} - N_{air_z}}$ 

35  z_air_vect[N_air_z] = z_ground + delta_z_air

37  for i in range(1, N_air - N_air_z):
    z_air_vect[N_air_z + i] =
39     z_air_vect[N_air_z + i - 1] + delta_z_air

41  # Velocity
    v_air_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
43     (v_ground_vect[N_ground - 1], V_obs, N_air)
    for in N_air:
45     v_air_vect = v_air_vect

47  # Climb Angle
    gamma_air_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
49     (0, gamma_air_deg, N_air)
    for in N_air:
51     gamma_air_vect = gamma_air_vect

53  ## Take-Off Climb
    # X
55  N_climb = tixi_get_element
    (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Number_Climb")

```

```
57 x_climb_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
    ((S_ground + S_air),
59     (S_ground + S_air + S_climb), N_climb)

61 for in N_climb:
    x_climb_vect = x_climb_vect
63
    # Z
65 z_climb_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
    (z_obs, z_climb, N_climb)
67 for in N_climb:
    z_climb_vect = z_climb_vect
69
    # Velocity
71 N_climb_v = N_climb / 10
    v_climb_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
73     (V_obs, V_TO_climb, N_climb_v)
    for in N_climb_v:
75     v_climb_vect = v_climb_vect

77 # Climb Angle
    gamma_climb_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
79     (gamma_air_deg, gamma_climb_deg, N_climb_v)
    for in N_climb_v:
81     gamma_climb_vect = gamma_climb_vect

83 ## Flyover
    # X
85 N_FO = tixi_get_element
    (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Number_FlyOver")
87 x_FO_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
    ((S_air + S_ground + S_climb),
89     (S_air + S_ground + S_climb + S_FO), N_FO)
    for in N_FO:
91     x_FO_vect[i] = round(x_FO_vect[i], 2)

93 # Z
    z_FO_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
95     (z_climb, Z_FO, N_FO)
    for in N_FO:
97     z_FO_vect = z_FO_vect

99 # Throttle Rate
    N_FO_T = N_FO / 5
101 T_FO_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
    (1, Throttle_rate_FO, N_FO_T)
103 for in N_FO_T:
    T_FO_vect = T_FO_vect
```

```

105
# Climb Angle
107 gamma_FO_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
      (gamma_climb_deg, gamma_FO_deg, N_FO_T)
109 for in N_FO_T:
      gamma_FO_vect = gamma_FO_vect

```

Listing 3.16: Pseudo-code of vectors' creation of the input parameters for the Take-Off CS-25 condition.

```

1
# Write CSV file (Trajectory Lateral)
3 write_file(TrajectoryLateral.csv):
      %%%%%%%%%%% SOURCE POSITIONS DATA
5      %%%%%%%%%%% POSITIONS
      X, Y, Z, V, THROTTLE_RATE, CLIMB_ANGLE, FLAP_DEFL,
7      SLAT_ON, MLG_ON, NLG_ON

9      x_ground_vect[0], 0, z_ground, v_ground_vect[0],
      Initial_Throttle_ground, 0, Flap_defl_lat,
11     Slat_contr, 1, 1

13     for i_g in range(1, N_ground):
          x_ground_vect[i_g], 0, z_ground, v_ground_vect[i_g],
15         1, 0, Flap_defl_lat, Slat_contr, 1, 1

17     for i_a_in in range(1, N_air_z):
          x_air_vect[i_a_in], 0, z_air_vect[i_a_in],
19         v_air_vect[i_a_in], 1, gamma_air_vect[i_a_in],
          Flap_defl_lat, Slat_contr, 1, 1

21     for i_a in range(1, N_air - N_air_z):
23         x_air_vect[N_air_z + i_a], 0,
          z_air_vect[N_air_z + i_a], v_air_vect[N_air_z + i_a],
25         1, gamma_air_vect[N_air_z + i_a], Flap_defl_lat,
          Slat_contr, 1, 1

27     for i_c_in in range(1, N_climb_v):
29         x_climb_vect[i_c_in], 0, z_climb_vect[i_c_in],
          v_climb_vect[i_c_in], 1, gamma_climb_vect[i_c_in],
31         Flap_defl_lat, Slat_contr, 1, 1

33     for i_c in range(1, N_climb - N_climb_v):
          x_climb_vect[N_climb_v + i_c], 0,
35         z_climb_vect[N_climb_v + i_c], V_TO_climb, 1,
          gamma_climb_deg, Flap_defl_lat, Slat_contr,
37         Main_Gear, Nose_Gear

39     for i_f_in in range(1, N_FO_T):

```

```

41     x_FO_vect[i_f_in], 0, z_FO_vect[i_f_in], V_TO_climb,
      T_FO_vect[i_f_in], gamma_FO_vect[i_f_in],
      Flap_defl_lat, Slat_contr, Main_Gear, Nose_Gear
43
44     for i_f in range(1, N_FO - N_FO_T):
45         x_FO_vect[N_FO_T + i_f], 0, z_FO_vect[N_FO_T + i_f],
46         V_TO_climb, Throttle_rate_FO, gamma_FO_deg,
47         Flap_defl_lat, Slat_contr, Main_Gear, Nose_Gear
49
50         %%%%%%%%% INPUT FOR LINEAR TRAJECTORY
51         %%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS MUST ALWAYS FOLLOW
      THE PREVIOUS COORDINATE LIST %%%%%%%%%
52         NAME, Name_case
53         ENG_SETTING, Eng_setting
54
55     # Write CSV file (Trajectory Fly-Over)
56     write_file(TrajectoryFlyover.csv):
57
58         %%%%%%%%%%%%% SOURCE POSITIONS DATA
59         %%%%%%%%%%%%% POSITIONS
60         X,Y,Z,V,THROTTLE_RATE,CLIMB_ANGLE,FLAP_DEFL,SLAT_ON,
61         MLG_ON,NLG_ON
62
63         for i_f in range(N_flyover, N_FO):
64             x_FO_vect[i_f], 0, z_FO_vect[i_f], V_TO_climb,
65             Throttle_rate_FO, gamma_FO_deg, Flap_defl_lat,
66             Slat_contr, Main_Gear, Nose_Gear
67
68         %%%%%%%%%%%%% INPUT FOR LINEAR TRAJECTORY
69         %%%%%%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS MUST ALWAYS FOLLOW
      THE PREVIOUS COORDINATE LIST %%%%%%%%%
70         NAME, Name_case
71         ENG_SETTING, Eng_setting
72         %%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS ARE USED ONLY
73         IF A LINEAR EXTRAPOLATION IS REQUESTED %%%%%%%%%
74         LINEAR, Linear
75         N_LIN, Num_Lin
76         DELTA_LIN, Delta_lin

```

Listing 3.17: Lateral and Fly-Over in CS-25 trajectory's file update.

Results' Printing and Plotting

The final part of function concerns the flight path plotting and the time-histories plotting of all main input file parameters (Climb Angle, Throttle Rate, Aircraft's Speed). An example of the Take-Off flight path, defined by the CS-25 regulation,

can be seen in Fig.3.33; while, in Figs.3.30 - 3.32, some examples of the time-histories have been shown. The figures, obtained with these plotting, have been smoothed with the smoothing function that is going to be discussed in detail in the paragraph 3.4.5.

Figure 3.30: Example of velocity time-history of Take-Off trajectory on the base of CS-25 regulation.

Figure 3.31: Example of throttle rate time-history of Take-Off trajectory on the base of CS-25 regulation.

Figure 3.32: Example of climb angle time-history of Take-Off trajectory on the base of CS-25 regulation.

Figure 3.33: Example of simplified Take-Off trajectory on the base of CS-25 regulation.

3.4.4 Take-Off Case CS-23

The CS-23 Regulation presents the Take-Off test case alone; in function of this aspect, the final trajectory function to analyse will concern the simplified estimation of the Take-Off flight path in the CS-23 regulation test case. From the computational point of view, this function is quite similar to the one that refers to the CS-25 case and the few differences regard a lower number of input parameters and a different estimation procedure for the climb phase; moreover there is no presence of Fly-Over phase.

CPACS Data Acquisition

Concerning the data acquisition, the input data from the CPACS file can be divided, also in this case, in the ones from the *Noise Toolspecific* section (see Table 3.23), in the ones from the *UNINA Toolspecific* section (see Table 3.24) and the ones that depend on the switching parameter, i.e. the *Parameter_evaluation* (see Table 3.20).

Moreover, the Slat contribution's management, the Main wing surface, the Span calculation and the Thrust interpolation procedure will be same of the CS-25 Take-Off function. Additionally, the data acquisition procedure, applied for the Main landing gears structure, will be the same too.

Variable Name	Description
Z_Obstacle	Virtual Obstacle from FAR 23 requirement
Delta_CD0_Flap	Delta CD0 contribution due to Flap deflection
Delta_CD0_LandingGear	Delta CD0 contribution due to Landing Gears
Name_Case	Trajectory Name (Recommend - LATERAL TRAJECTORY)
Engine_Setting	Select the thrust rating. [1-Max take-off rating; 2-Cruise rating]

It continues in the next page...

Variable Name	Description
Slat_contribution	Include Slat action in Take-Off
Max_TakeOff_Thrust	Max Take-Off Thrust of a single Engine
MainGear_contribution	Main Landing Gears setting [0-Retractable Gears; 1-Fixed Gears]
NoseGear_contribution	Nose Landing Gears setting [0-Retractable Gear; 1-Fixed Gear]
Number_Ground	Intervals' number for Grounding discretization
Number_Airborne	Intervals' number for Airborne discretization
Number_Climb	Intervals' number for Climb discretization
Speed_vector	VMC vector evolution during Lateral
TO_Thrust_vector	Take-Off Thrust Vector in function of VMC evolution during Lateral

Table 3.23: Take-Off CS-23 trajectory input parameters from the Noise Toolspecific section.

Variable Name	Description
Cd0	CD_0 value
CLg	CL_g value
mig	Wheel-Runway rolling friction coefficient

It continues in the next page...

Variable Name	Description
eTO	Oswald Factor in the Take-Off phase
CLmaxTO	CL_max in Take-Off phase
nlof	Lift-Off load factor
n2	Virtual obstacle load factor
n2	Virtual obstacle load factor
VY_Speed_at_Max_ RC_Sea_level	Best rate of climb speed
Speed_for_VMC	VMC vector evolution during Lateral
TO_net_thrust_for_VMC	Take-Off Thrust Vector in function of VMC evolution during Lateral

Table 3.24: Take-Off CS-23 trajectory input parameters from the UNINA Toolspecific section.

Performances Estimation

With the conclusion of data acquisition, the Take-Off function will start to estimate the flight path exploiting the performances' equations of a generic Take-Off phase; but, this time, with the specifications from the CS-23 regulation, as they have been described in paragraph 2.3.2. In this case, the flight path will loose the Fly-Over phase and it can be divided in the remaining Take-Off phases:

1. **Grounding Phase;**
2. **Airborne Phase;**
3. **Climb Phase;**

The estimation, so, will be performed in different calculation steps, function of the Take-Off phases for this test case. In the listing 3.18 it is possible to understand the logic sequence of equations which lead to the Take-Off distances estimations, in addition to several Speeds, Throttle Rates and Climb Angles.

```

1  ### Calculation
   ## Grounding
3  z_ground = MLG_lenght + |MLG_fus_attach_z|

5  z_k = z_ground + z_wing

7  K_es =  $\frac{\left(\frac{16*z_k}{Span}\right)^2}{1 + \left(\frac{16*z_k}{Span}\right)^2}$ 

9  CD_ground =  $\frac{(CL_g)^2 * K_es}{\pi * Aspect\_Ratio * Oswald\_fact\_lat}$  + CD0_gr +
11      Delta_CD0_flap + Delta_CD0_LG

13  V_s_T0 =  $\sqrt{\frac{2 * Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81}{1.225 * CL\_max\_TO * Surf\_Area}}$ 

15  V_lift_off = 1.1 * V_s_T0

17  D_gr = CD_ground * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V_lift_off * 0.7)^2 * Surf_Area
   L_gr = CL_g * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V_lift_off * 0.7)^2 * Surf_Area
19  Thrust_ground =
      Thrust_interp(V_lift_off * 0.7) * Num_eng * 1000

21  S_ground =  $\frac{\frac{Max\_TO\_mass}{2} * (V\_lift\_off)^2}{Thrust\_ground - D\_gr - mi * (Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81 - L\_gr)}$ 

23

25  ## Airborne
   V_obs = 1.2 * V_s_T0

27

   K_es_air =  $\frac{\left(\frac{16*z_obs}{Span}\right)^2}{1 + \left(\frac{16*z_obs}{Span}\right)^2}$ 

29

   CL_air =  $\frac{Max\_TO\_mass * 9.81}{0.5 * 1.225 * (V\_obs)^2 * Surf\_Area}$ 

31

   CD_air =  $\frac{(CL\_air)^2 * K\_es\_air}{\pi * Aspect\_Ratio * Oswald\_fact\_lat}$  + CD0_gr +
33      Delta_CD0_flap + Delta_CD0_LG

35

   D_air = CD_air * 0.5 * 1.225 * (V_obs)^2 * Surf_Area

37

   Thrust_air = Thrust_interp(V_obs) * Num_eng * 1000

```

```

39
gamma_air =arcsin ( ( Thrust_air - D_air )
41                ( Max_TO_mass * 9.81 )
43
gamma_air_deg = math_degrees ( gamma_air )
45
n_air = ( n_loff + n_obs )
47         2
Air_Radius = ( 1.15 * V_s_TO )2
49             9.81 * ( n_air - 1 )
Theta_air = arccos ( 1 - ( z_obs )
51                    ( Air_Radius )
S_air = Air_Radius * sin ( Theta_air )
53
## Take-Off Climb
V_TO_climb = V_y
55
CL_climb = ( Max_TO_mass * 9.81 )
           ( 0.5 * 1.225 * ( V_TO_climb )2 * Surf_Area )
57
CD_climb = ( CL_climb )2
           ( pi * Aspect_Ratio * Oswald_fact_lat ) + CD0_gr + Delta_CD0_flap
59
D_climb = CD_climb * 0.5 * 1.225 * ( V_TO_climb )2 * Surf_Area
61
Thrust_climb = Thrust_interp ( V_TO_climb ) * Num_eng * 1000
63
gamma_climb =arcsin ( ( Thrust_climb - D_climb )
                    ( Max_TO_mass * 9.81 )
65
gamma_climb_deg = math_degrees ( gamma_climb )
S_climb = S_climb_mic - S_ground - S_air + 2000
67
z_climb = tan ( gamma_climb ) * S_climb

```

Listing 3.18: Take-Off CS-23 performances estimation procedure showed in pseudo-code.

The significant change in the CS-23 Take-Off flight path consists in the assumption of the Take-Off climb speed equals to the best rate of climb speed.

Vector Setting and File Updating

The performances data, acquired with the simplified estimation, can be exploited to update the *Trajectory.csv* file (Lateral) as it can be seen in the listing 3.20. To update correctly the Lateral file, it is necessary to define several vectors of the

main input parameters, in order to create a discretized sequence of points for all parameters (the linear interpolation function is not going to be used) and in the listing 3.19 this process has been shown.

```

### Vectors Creation
2  ## Grounding
   # X
4  N_ground = tixi_get_element
           (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Number_Ground")
6  x_ground_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
           (0, S_ground, N_ground)
8  for in N_ground:
           x_ground_vect = x_ground_vect
10
   # Velocity
12 for in N_ground:
           v_ground_vect = 2.2918 * x_ground_vect0.4923
14
   # Throttle Rate
16 Initial_Throttle_ground = 0.1

18 ## Airborne
   # X
20 N_air = tixi_get_element
           (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Number_Airborne")
22 x_air_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
           (S_ground, (S_ground + S_air), N_air)
24 for in N_air:
           x_air_vect = x_air_vect
26
   # Z
28 N_air_z = N_air / 5

30 for in N_air_z:
           z_air_vect = z_ground
32
   delta_z_air =  $\frac{z_{obs} - z_{ground}}{N_{air} - N_{air_z}}$ 
34
   z_air_vect[N_air_z] = z_ground + delta_z_air
36
   for i in range(1, N_air - N_air_z):
38       z_air_vect[N_air_z + i] =
           z_air_vect[N_air_z + i - 1] + delta_z_air
40
   # Velocity
42 v_air_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation

```

```

    (v_ground_vect[N_ground - 1], V_obs, N_air)
44 for in N_air:
    v_air_vect = v_air_vect
46
    # Climb Angle
48 gamma_air_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
    (0, gamma_air_deg, N_air)
50 for in N_air:
    gamma_air_vect = gamma_air_vect
52
    ## Take-Off Climb
54 # X
    N_climb = tixi_get_element
56 (CPACS_path_noise_toolspecific + "Number_Climb")
    x_climb_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
58 ((S_ground + S_air),
    (S_ground + S_air + S_climb), N_climb)
60
    for in N_climb:
62 x_climb_vect = x_climb_vect

64 # Z
    z_climb_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
66 (z_obs, (z_climb + z_obs), N_climb)
    for in N_climb:
68 z_climb_vect = z_climb_vect

70 # Velocity
    N_climb_v = N_climb / 10
72 v_climb_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
    (V_obs, V_TO_climb, N_climb_v)
74 for in N_climb_v:
    v_climb_vect = v_climb_vect
76

    # Climb Angle
78 gamma_climb_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
    (gamma_air_deg, gamma_climb_deg, N_climb_v)
80 for in N_climb_v:
    gamma_climb_vect = gamma_climb_vect
82

    # Flap Deflection
84 flap_defl_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
    (Flap_defl_lat, 0, N_climb_v)
86 for in N_climb_v:
    flap_defl_vect = flap_defl_vect

```

Listing 3.19: Pseudo-code of vectors' creation of the input parameters for the Take-Off CS-23 condition.

```

1  # Write CSV file (Trajectory Lateral)
3  write_file(TrajectoryLateral.csv):
    %%%%%%%%% SOURCE POSITIONS DATA
5  %%%%%%%%% POSITIONS
    X, Y, Z, V, THROTTLE_RATE, CLIMB_ANGLE, FLAP_DEFL,
7  SLAT_ON, MLG_ON, NLG_ON

9  x_ground_vect[0], 0, z_ground, v_ground_vect[0],
    Initial_Throttle_ground, 0, Flap_defl_lat,
11 Slat_contr, 1, 1

13 for i_g in range(1, N_ground):
    x_ground_vect[i_g], 0, z_ground, v_ground_vect[i_g],
15     1, 0, Flap_defl_lat, Slat_contr, 1, 1

17 for i_a_in in range(1, N_air_z):
    x_air_vect[i_a_in], 0, z_air_vect[i_a_in],
19     v_air_vect[i_a_in], 1, gamma_air_vect[i_a_in],
    Flap_defl_lat, Slat_contr, 1, 1

21 for i_a in range(1, N_air - N_air_z):
23     x_air_vect[N_air_z + i_a], 0,
    z_air_vect[N_air_z + i_a], v_air_vect[N_air_z + i_a],
25     1, gamma_air_vect[N_air_z + i_a], Flap_defl_lat,
    Slat_contr, 1, 1

27 for i_c_in in range(1, N_climb_v):
29     x_climb_vect[i_c_in], 0, z_climb_vect[i_c_in],
    v_climb_vect[i_c_in], 1, gamma_climb_vect[i_c_in],
31     flap_defl_vect[i_c_in], Slat_contr, 1, 1

33 for i_c in range(1, N_climb - N_climb_v):
    x_climb_vect[N_climb_v + i_c], 0,
35     z_climb_vect[N_climb_v + i_c], V_TO_climb, 1,
    gamma_climb_deg, 0, 0, Main_Gear, Nose_Gear

37 %%%%%%%%% INPUT FOR LINEAR TRAJECTORY
39 %%%%%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS MUST ALWAYS FOLLOW
    THE PREVIOUS COORDINATE LIST %%%%%%%%%
41 NAME, Name_case
    ENG_SETTING, Eng_setting

```

Listing 3.20: Lateral and Fly-Over in CS-23 trajectory's file update.

Results' Printing and Plotting

The final part of function concerns the flight path plotting and the time-histories plotting of all main input file parameters (Climb angle, Throttle Rate, Aircraft Speed). An example of the Take-Off flight path, defined by the CS-23 regulation, can be seen in Fig.3.34; while in Figs.3.35 - 3.36 some examples of the time-histories have been shown (The engine throttle time-history misses due to the fact that the engine throttle itself is constant during the CS-23 Take-Off case). The figures, obtained with these plotting, have been smoothed with the smoothing function that is going to be discussed in detail in the paragraph 3.4.5.

Figure 3.34: Example of simplified Take-Off trajectory on the base of CS-23 regulation.

Figure 3.35: Example of velocity time-history of Take-Off trajectory on the base of CS-23 regulation.

Figure 3.36: Example of climb angle time-history of Take-Off trajectory on the base of CS-23 regulation.

3.4.5 Trajectory Smoothing Function

The trajectory's functions end their works with the flight path and time-histories plotting, but these figures present several edge connections between the various flight phases (for example the grounding-airborne connection) and/or several edges in the single flight phases. The smoothing function that is going to be discussed is able to make smoother all these connections and/or inner edges, in order to make the flight paths more similar to the real one (the smooths better represent how a real aircraft should follow the flight path).

In function of these differences, the smoothing function has to be split in two functions: the first one will act on the edgy connections (*sep_phases_smooth_func*); while the second one will act on the inner edges (*single_phase_smooth_func*). As it is going to be seen, the main difference between them consists in the different input and output parameters, while the working's logic is the same.

The smoothing logic is based on the idea of defining quadratic interpolation law between three points: the first one will be the starting point, that must be inside the initial part of the edge (being more clear, it is before the edge); the second one will be the medium point, that has to be calculated in function of the first and third one; the third is the closing point, that must be inside the final part of the edge (being more clear, it is after the edge). In Fig.3.37 it is possible to see a scheme of all possible types of edges with the starting and closing points described before (Point 2 is the edge point). In the listing 3.21 the medium point calculation and the smoothing procedure has been explained:

```

2  ## X (GREEN OR BLUE LINES)
3  x_spline_1 = x_vect_initial[N_init_vect] (N°1 POINT)
4  x_spline_2 = x_vect_final[N_final_vect] (N°3 POINT)
5
6  x_spline = [x_spline_1, x_spline_2]
7
8  ## Y (GREEN OR BLUE LINES)
9  y_spline_1 = y_vect_initial[N_init_vect] (N°1 POINT)
10 y_spline_2 = y_vect_final[N_final_vect] (N°3 POINT)
11
12
```

```

y_spline = [y_spline_1, y_spline_2]
14
## Edge point (N°2 POINT)
16 y_med = y_vect_initial[N_init - 1]
x_med = x_vect_initial[N_init - 1]
18
## Linear interpolation parameters (RED LINES)
20 interp_lin_spline = interpolation_1D(x_spline, y_spline)

22  $x\_spline\_med = \frac{x\_spline\_1 + x\_spline\_2}{2}$  (RED POINT)

24 y_interp_med = interp_lin_spline(x_spline_med) (RED POINT)
y_interp_eval = interp_lin_spline(x_med)
26
## Smoothing correction
28 if (|y_interp_eval - y_vect_initial[0]| <
      |y_med - y_vect_initial[0]|): (GREEN LINES)
30
      y_spline_med = y_interp_med +  $\frac{y\_spline\_2 - y\_spline\_1}{smooth\_coeff}$ 
32
      elif (|y_interp_eval - y_vect_initial[0]| >
            |y_med - y_vect_initial[0]|): (BLUE LINES)
34
            y_spline_med = y_interp_med -  $\frac{y\_spline\_2 - y\_spline\_1}{smooth\_coeff}$ 
36
38 else:
      y_spline_med = y_interp_med
40
x_spline = [x_spline_1, x_spline_med, x_spline_2]
42 y_spline = [y_spline_1, y_spline_med, y_spline_2]

44 ## Smoothing
interp_spline = quadratic_interpolation(x_spline, y_spline)
46 x_spline_fine = equally_spaced_vector_creation
      (x_spline_1, x_spline_2, 100)
48 y_spline_fine = interp_spline(x_spline_fine)

```

Listing 3.21: Smoothing pseudo-code procedure.

Figure 3.37: Smoothing logic basic scheme: the green lines represent all edges that in absolute value (with respect to the Y axis) have a concave trend; the blue lines represent all edges that in absolute value (with respect to the Y axis) have a convex trend; the red lines represent the linear connections between the starting (point 1) and closing point (point 3).

In order to edit the smoothing procedure, the function will take from the CPACS file several parameters used to define the starting and closing points and the degree of smooth. As it can be seen in Table 3.25, these parameters will be the same for all possible edges in the figures of interest; but, due to the fact that these coefficients will be different for every edge, it is necessary to define them for all possible edges in the CPACS file and in Fig.3.38 an example of edges' sub-levels location has been shown; while in listing 3.22 all possible edges have been listed.

```

1  ### Plot
   ##### TRAJECTORY CASES PARAMETERS #####
3  ### CS25 ###
   # 1 = CS25 APPROACH PATH SMOOTHING #
5  # 2 = CS25 TAKEOFF PATH AIRBORNE-CLIMB SMOOTHING #
   # 3 = CS25 TAKEOFF PATH CLIMB-FLYOVER SMOOTHING #

```

```

7 # 4 = CS25 TAKEOFF AIRSPEED SMOOTHING #
  # 5 = CS25 TAKEOFF THROTTLE CLIMB-FLYOVER SMOOTHING #
9 # 6 = CS25 TAKEOFF THROTTLE FLYOVER SMOOTHING #
  # 7 = CS25 TAKEOFF CLIMB ANGLE GROUND-AIRBORNE SMOOTHING #
11 # 8 = CS25 TAKEOFF CLIMB ANGLE AIRBORNE-CLIMB SMOOTHING #
   # 9 = CS25 TAKEOFF CLIMB ANGLE CLIMB SMOOTHING #
13 # 10 = CS25 TAKEOFF CLIMB ANGLE CLIMB-FLYOVER SMOOTHING #
   # 11 = CS25 TAKEOFF CLIMB ANGLE FLYOVER SMOOTHING #
15 #### CS23 ###
   # 12 = CS23 TAKEOFF PATH AIRBORNE-CLIMB SMOOTHING #
17 # 13 = CS23 TAKEOFF AIRSPEED SMOOTHING #
   # 14 = CS23 TAKEOFF CLIMB ANGLE GROUND-AIRBORNE SMOOTHING #
19 # 15 = CS23 TAKEOFF CLIMB ANGLE AIRBORNE-CLIMB SMOOTHING #
   # 16 = CS23 TAKEOFF CLIMB ANGLE CLIMB SMOOTHING #
    
```

Listing 3.22: Trajectories' edges listing.

Variable Name	Description
Relative_initial_interp_pos	Initial interpolation position parameter. Higher is this value nearer to intersection point is the initial interpolation position.
Relative_final_interp_pos	Final interpolation position parameter. Higher is this value nearer to intersection point is the initial interpolation position.
Smoothing_coefficient	Coefficient to define smoothness of spline interpolation

Table 3.25: Smoothing parameters.

```

<Smoothing_parameters>
  <description>Setting of smoothing parameters for different Take-Off and Approach graphs for every phase at different certification procedures.</description>
  <Path>
    <From airborne to climb>
    <From climb to flyover>
  </Path>
  <Airspeed>
  <Throttle>
    <From climb to flyover>
    <Inside flyover>
  </Throttle>
  <Climb angle>
    <From ground to airborne>
    <From airborne to climb>
    <Inside climb>
    <From climb to flyover>
    <Inside flyover>
  </Climb angle>
</Smoothing_parameters>
    
```

Figure 3.38: Smoothing parameters' sub-levels for Take-Off CS-25 case (inside every sub-levels there are the smoothing parameters, described in Table3.25).

The edges' listing is managed with a sequence of numbers, that characterize every edge and this is due to the fact that the specific number is one of the input parameters of function *traj_smoothing_case*; in fact, with this parameter the smoothing function is able to choose the right smoothing parameters, as it can be seen in listing 3.23.

```

1  if(traj_smoothing_case = 1):
2
3  # CS25 APPROACH PATH SMOOTHING
4  init_interp_pos = tixi_get_element("/cpacs/toolspecific/
5      UNINA_NoiseTool/INPUT/Trajectory/CS25/Approach/
6      Smoothing_parameters/Relative_initial_interp_pos")
7
8  final_interp_pos = tixi_get_element("/cpacs/toolspecific/
9      UNINA_NoiseTool/INPUT/Trajectory/CS25/Approach/
10     Smoothing_parameters/Relative_final_interp_pos")
11
12 smooth_coeff = tixi_get_element("/cpacs/toolspecific/
13     UNINA_NoiseTool/INPUT/Trajectory/CS25/Approach/
14     Smoothing_parameters/Smoothing_coefficient")

```

Listing 3.23: Smoothing parameters' selection.

In conclusion, the smoothing functions can be applied to perform the graphic optimization procedure and in listing 3.24 it is possible to understand how the functions can be called and how the function's output will be used in the plotting procedure (the Fig.3.31 is the one plotted with the listed procedure).

```

1  ### Spline Interpolation Throttle
2  ## CS25 TAKEOFF THROTTLE CLIMB-FLYOVER SMOOTHING
3  x_spline_TR_1 = sep_phases_smooth_func
4      (x_climb_vect, x_FO_vect, TR_climb_vect, TR_FO_vect, 5)
5
6  TR_spline_1 = sep_phases_smooth_func
7      (x_climb_vect, x_FO_vect, TR_climb_vect, TR_FO_vect, 5)
8
9  Num_climb_v = sep_phases_smooth_func
10     (x_climb_vect, x_FO_vect, TR_climb_vect, TR_FO_vect, 5)
11
12 Num_flyover_v_1 = sep_phases_smooth_func
13     (x_climb_vect, x_FO_vect, TR_climb_vect, TR_FO_vect, 5)
14
15 ## CS25 TAKEOFF THROTTLE FLYOVER SMOOTHING
16 x_spline_TR_2 = single_phase_smooth_func
17     (x_FO_vect, TR_FO_vect, N_FO_T, 6)
18

```

```

TR_spline_2 = single_phase_smooth_funct
20     (x_FO_vect ,TR_FO_vect ,N_FO_T,6)

22 Num_flyover_v_2 = single_phase_smooth_funct
    (x_FO_vect ,TR_FO_vect ,N_FO_T,6)
24
26 Num_flyover_v_3 = single_phase_smooth_funct
    (x_FO_vect ,TR_FO_vect ,N_FO_T,6)

28 plot_figure()
    plot(x_ground_vect , TR_ground_vect , "Grounding Phase")
30 plot(x_air_vect , TR_air_vect , "Airborne Phase")
    plot(x_climb_vect [0:Num_climb_v] ,
32     TR_climb_vect [0:Num_climb_v] ,"Take-Off Climb Phase")

34 plot(x_spline_TR_1 , TR_spline_1) ## CLIMB-FLYOVER SMOOTHING

36 plot(x_FO_vect [Num_flyover_v_1: Num_flyover_v_2 + 1] ,
    TR_FO_vect [Num_flyover_v_1: Num_flyover_v_2 + 1] ,
38     "Fly-Over Phase")

40 plot(x_spline_TR_2 , TR_spline_2) ## FLYOVER SMOOTHING
    plot(x_FO_vect [Num_flyover_v_3:N_FO] ,
42     TR_FO_vect [Num_flyover_v_3:N_FO] ,"Fly-Over Phase")

```

Listing 3.24: Plotting and smoothing procedure of engine throttle time-history.

Connection Edge Case

The smoothing of the edge, when it is due to the connection between different vectors, presents two main difference with respect to the inner edge case:

- The input parameters will be the axial coordinates' vectors for both starting and ending vectors, in addition to the smoothing case parameter;
- Only a part of the smoothing cases can be operated ($N^{\circ}1$, $N^{\circ}2$, $N^{\circ}3$, $N^{\circ}5$, $N^{\circ}7$, $N^{\circ}8$, $N^{\circ}10$, $N^{\circ}12$, $N^{\circ}14$, $N^{\circ}15$);

About the input parameters, this function will be able to find out the starting and closing points following the procedure shown in listing 3.25.

```

1  ## Vector size
    N_init = size_evaluation(x_vect_initial)
3  N_final = size_evaluation(x_vect_final)

5  ## Calculation of interpolation's vector's positions

```

```

7 N_init_vect = N_init -  $\frac{N\_init}{init\_interp\_pos}$  + 1
9 N_final_vect =  $\frac{N\_final}{final\_interp\_pos}$  + 1

```

Listing 3.25: Smoothing parameters' selection(connection edge).

Inner Edge Case

The smoothing of an inner edge, i.e. an edge located in a single vector, instead, will be characterized by two main aspects:

- The input parameters will be the axial coordinates' vectors of the single vector and the number of element in initial part of it (N_init), in addition to the smoothing case parameter;
- Only a part of the smoothing cases can be operated ($N^{\circ}4$, $N^{\circ}6$, $N^{\circ}9$, $N^{\circ}11$, $N^{\circ}13$, $N^{\circ}16$);

In this case, the function will be able to find out the starting and closing points following this alternative procedure shown in listing 3.26; moreover, in the listing 3.21 the initial and final vectors for the axial coordinates will be substituted by the single vector.

```

1 ## Vector size
  N_final = size_evaluation(x_vect)
3
  ## Calculation of interpolation's vector's positions
5
  N_init_vect = N_init -  $\frac{N\_init}{init\_interp\_pos}$  + 1
7
  N_final_vect =  $\frac{N\_final}{final\_interp\_pos}$  + 1

```

Listing 3.26: Smoothing parameters' selection (inner edge).

3.5 Noise's Footprint

The other important new feature, developed in this thesis work, is the Noise's Footprint Tool. This tool, basically, is able to plot the noise estimated emissions' footprint of a certain tested aircraft in a specific test case, between the ones discussed in the regulations paragraphs (see paragraphs 2.3.2 and 2.3.1). The great usefulness of this tool, to better understand the real impact of a certain aircraft in terms of noise emissions on the area near the airport for both Take-Off and Approach cases, is clear.

The basic logic of this tool consists in the iterative running of the ATTILA++ Tool, varying the microphone receiver positions, in order to obtain a mesh of microphones around the runway or near it; in this way, it is possible to evaluate the noise emissions in several points, which will be the input data of a contour function able, in turn, to plot them in an exhaustive footprint, divided in various reference levels, i.e. the contour levels. Naturally, increasing the number of microphones, there will be an improvement of the footprint's quality and precision (an extreme increase of this number could lead to a wrong evaluation and plotting of the contour levels in the Geo-Footprint examples, as it is going to be discussed in the paragraphs 4.2.4 and 4.3.4).

3.5.1 Tool Architecture

The Footprint Tool, on the basis of the introductory discussion, has a standard scheme to follow, even if there will be some modifies in function of the certification flight path to analyse (the distinguish factor will be the reference regulation and/or the test case). This scheme can be divided in three main phases:

1. **ATTILA++ Setting;**
2. **Iterative Data Acquisition;**
3. **Footprint Plotting.**

During the first phase, there will be the update of all input files, used to run the Noise Tool, in the same manner seen in the previous paragraphs:

- **Trajectory Files** (see paragraph 3.4);

- **Input File** (see paragraph 3.3.8);
- **Control Parameters File** (see paragraph 3.3.7);
- **Engine File** (see paragraph 3.3.4);

The only input file that will be updated in a different manner is the receiver file, due to the fact that its management is the main core of the data estimation for the Footprint's evaluation; for this reason, the receiver file's update is located in the second phase of Footprint Tool.

In the first phase, in addition to the input files update, there will be the taken of some *CPACS Toolspecific* data, necessary to perform correctly the Footprint Tool; and in Table 3.26 all of them have been presented.

Variable Name	Description
Approach_footprint	Approach's FootPrint calculation [1-Perform calculation ;0-Not required]
TakeOff_footprint	Take-Off's FootPrint calculation [1-Perform calculation ;0-Not required]
X_number	Number of microphones along X axis for a fixed value of Y
Y_number	Number of microphones along Y axis for a fixed value of X
X_distance	Max distance position along X axis
Y_distance	Max absolute distance position along Y axis
Z_lenght	Microphone position along Z axis from regulations (All microphones are located at same Z)
EPNL_Levels	EPNL FootPrint Iso-Levels Values

Table 3.26: Standard CPACS parameters to set the Footprint Tool.

In particular, the first two parameters will define if tool has to process the Approach and/or Take-Off case, on the base of the certification parameter that, as it has been explained yet, will define the regulation certification to respect. The Footprint Tool, so, will exploit these parameters to distinguish all test cases and their specific estimation procedures, in addition to the control parameters file and trajectory file's updating. In fact, in function of these distinguish factors, Footprint Tool will re-call the specific trajectory and control parameters functions; in particular, there are several control parameters functions in the Control Parameters class, which have been defined especially for the Footprint Tool: the differences with respect to the standard control parameters function, seen in the integration tool, are the fixing of some parameters (Output Control Parameters, Sound Metrics Control Parameters and Cases Selection Control Parameters), in order to reduce the computational time and weight of the ATTILA++ Tool running and avoid useless results, test's cases calculations and printings. On the other side, the remaining parameters have to be associated to all test cases, which scheme in the CPACS file can be seen in Fig.3.39.

```

<Receivers>
  <Main Tool>
    <FootPrint>
      <description>Microphones parameters to set FootPrint evaluation</description>
      <Approach_footprint>1</Approach_footprint>
      <description>Approach's FootPrint calculation [1-Perform calculation ;0-Not required]</description>
      <TakeOff_footprint>1</TakeOff_footprint>
      <description>Take-Off's FootPrint calculation [1-Perform calculation ;0-Not required]</description>
      <Approach CS25>
      <Take Off CS25>
      <Take Off CS23>
    </FootPrint>
  </Receivers>

```

Figure 3.39: CPACS Toolspecific organization for the Footprint section.

The second phase of the Footprint Tool is the main core of it. In this phase, there will be the iterative procedure to acquire all noise results, in function of a certain microphones' grid, made with the CPACS parameters described before. Being more precise, the tool will update the receiver file and it will run the ATTILA++ Tool in an iterative way, in order to obtain noise results on varying of microphones' position; moreover, it will allocate these data in an output vector. The iterative procedure, however, stands out in two ways, in function of the reference regulation: the CS-25 regulation needs the EPNL noise emission, while the CS-23 needs the max value of

the OASPL noise emissions' vector. Due to this aspect, the receiver file's update and the data acquisition procedure will change.

In listing 3.27, the CS-25 iterative procedure has been shown and it is possible to see that with one noise tool's run it is possible to estimate the noise emissions of several microphones along the y axis for a fixed value of the x axis and the data acquisition procedure will be function of this logic.

```

## Initialization
2 X_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
      (x_starting_distance, X_dist, Num_X)
4
Y_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
6      (0, Y_dist, Num_Y)

8 EPNL = [0] * (Num_X * (Num_Y * 2 - 1))

10 for i in range(0, Num_X):
    X = X_vect[i]
12
    ## Write CSV file
14    write_file(receiver_file.csv):
          %%%%%%%%%%% MICROPHONE POSITIONS DATA"]
16          X, Y, Z
          for j in range(0, Num_Y):
18              X, Y_vect[j], Z_lenght

20          %%%%%%%%%%% EXTRA DATA
          %%%%%% WARNING: THE FOLLOWING COMMANDS MUST
22          ALWAYS FOLLOW THE PREVIOUS COORDINATE LIST %%%%%%
          NAME, Name_Case
24          REL_HUM, Rel_hum
          LINEAR,
26          N_LIN,
          DELTA_LIN,

28
    ## Execute Noise Tool

30
    p = executable_running(Attila++.exe)

32
    ## Vector Updating
34    open_file("EPNL_MAP.txt"):

36        for line in test_case:
            riga = line.split(Filler)
38            if ("EPNL" in riga[0]):

```

```

40         for k in range(0, Num_Y - 1):
41             EPNL[k + (i * (Num_Y * 2 - 1))] =
42                 riga[Num_Y - k]
43
44         for k2 in range(0, Num_Y):
45             EPNL[k2 + (Num_Y - 1) +
46                 (i * (Num_Y * 2 - 1))] = riga[k2 + 1]

```

Listing 3.27: Footprint Tool's iterative procedure on the base of the CS-25 regulation.

Instead, in listing 3.28 the CS-23 iterative procedure has been shown; in this case it is evident the double iterative procedure for both x and y axes and it is due to the fact that the noise results to acquire are the maximum values of the OASPL vectors, associated to every receiver. Therefore, it is not possible to estimate with one run a vector of microphones, due to the absence of a summary results' file from which it is possible to take the results themselves. Therefore, the only solution consists in the analyse of a single receiver microphone for every tool's running; even if this solution could led to think to an increase of the computational time, it would be the same more or less for the two procedures, unless the number of microphones reaches a too much elevated value: in this case the "single microphone procedure" spends more time than the "microphones' vector procedure".

```

## Initialization
2 X_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
      (x_starting_distance, X_dist, Num_X)
4
6 Y_vect = equally_spaced_vector_creation
      (0, Y_dist, Num_Y)
8 OASPL = [0] * (Num_X * (Num_Y * 2 - 1))
10 for i in range(0, Num_X):
11     X = X_vect[i]
12     for j in range(0, Num_Y):
13         Y = Y_vect[j]
14
16     ## Write CSV file
17     write_file(receiver_file.csv):
18         %%%%%%%%%%% MICROPHONE POSITIONS DATA %)
19         X, Y, Z
20         X, Y, Z_lenght

```



```

68         Tone_corr_vect[k - 1] = riga[k]
           if("nan" in riga[k] or
70             "-inf" in riga[k]):
               Tone_corr_vect[k - 1] = 0
72
           # Tone correction and OASPL sum
74         OASPL_TC_vect = [0] * OASPL_vector_length
           for w in range(0, OASPL_vector_length):
76             OASPL_TC_vect[w] =
               OASPL_vect[w] + Tone_corr_vect[w]
78
           # Find Max value
80         OASPL_takeoff = max_value(OASPL_TC_vect)
82
           # Allocate value
           OASPL[(Num_Y - 1) + j +
84               (i * (Num_Y * 2 - 1))] = OASPL_takeoff
           OASPL[(Num_Y - 1) - j +
86               (i * (Num_Y * 2 - 1))] = OASPL_takeoff

```

Listing 3.28: Footprint Tool's iterative procedure on the base of the CS-23 regulation.

The final phase consists in the results plotting with the usage of Matlab scripts (one for the Approach case and the other one for the Take-Off case); reason why it is preferred to exploit a Matlab code, instead of the Python one, is that, in Matlab, the plotting's procedure is better in terms of quality and precision; moreover, a Matlab script is able to work more easily with matrices, instead of a Python script (the noise emissions vector has to be considered like a matrix, because it contains noise emissions for every microphone, which position has been defined in two coordinates; therefore, the noise emissions vector should be seen like a matrix which rows and columns have to be the "x" and "y" coordinates of all microphones). Primarily, it is necessary to load the main plot's inputs in several *.csv* input files, due to the fact that it becomes easier to be read in the Matlab script; in Fig.3.40 the input files management is shown (the Matlab scripts folder is included in the ATTILA++ Tool's folder) and it is possible to observe the necessity to distinguish the noise results input files in function of the reference regulation and/or test case (in this way it is possible to save all different results).

Figure 3.40: Matlab input files and matlab scripts to obtain the Footprint's plotting.

In the footprint function, there is, basically, the Matlab input files' update and the Matlab script's calling with the usage of a specific Python function, able to find out the Matlab code to run, through a *.bat* file, that indicate the Matlab script's path. Concerning the Matlab script structure, there is a preliminary part where all inputs will be uploaded from the respective files and, after the noise emissions matrix's creation, there will be the creation of the footprint with the usage of the Matlab's contour function. An example of the final plots for both Approach and Take-Off cases and for both regulation cases have been shown in Figs.3.41, 3.42 and 3.43.

Figure 3.41: Example of Approach Footprint for CS-25 regulation.

Figure 3.42: Example of Take-Off Footprint for CS-25 regulation.

Figure 3.43: Example of Take-Off Footprint for CS-23 regulation.

3.6 Summary

The complete discussion about the integration tool of the ATTILA++ software gives all significant information to perform it in the MDO workflow of the AGILE 4.0 Project. Moreover, the additions, concerning the simplified trajectory's estimation and the Noise Footprint plotting and visualization, increase the understanding of the estimated noise emissions of a certain aircraft in order to improve the aircraft design procedure with respect to the noise problem. In the chapter's discussion, then, the high heterogeneity of employment of the noise tool is understood, even if this is a starting point for future developments to improve further the aircraft's noise emissions studying.

4

Applications and Results of Turbo-Fan and Turbo-Prop Engine Aircrafts

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4.1 Introduction

The final chapter of this thesis work is going to show several results of the noise emissions' estimation for two main aircraft's types:

- **Turbo-Fan engine aircraft;**
- **Turbo-Prop engine aircraft.**

In particular the Turbo-Fan engine aircraft is the WP8-AC6 of the AGILE 4.0 Project, while the Turbo-Prop engine aircraft is the WP7-AC3 of the AGILE 4.0 Project, which has been analysed in four different versions on varying of the on-board systems electrification (Conventional, MEA1, MEA2, AEA).

In function of the Integration and ATTILA++ Tools' working procedures, the main noise results, in terms of the certification limits and the graphic Footprints for both aircraft's types, are going to be described in detail. Moreover, for the Turbo-Fan aircraft, the BPR effect's results is going to be shown with great attention; while, for the Turbo-Prop one, the different noise results, obtained respecting the CS-25 and CS-23 regulations, will be compared (it is possible because the WP7-AC3 aircraft could be certified for both regulations, due to the aircraft's MTOW, which is acceptable for both regulations).

All results obtained and analysed will be the information and instruments, exploited to perform the MDO designing process and, in particular, these results will lead to the retrofiting of a pre-designed aircraft, in order to upgrade it from the emissions, costs and engine' performances point of view.

4.2 WP8-AC6 Turbo-Fan Engine Aircraft

4.2.1 Aircraft's General Overview

The WP8-AC6 is a 90 passengers regional platform Turbo-Fan aircraft that is equipped with an engine based on the *Pratt & Whitney PW1000G* engine's family [43](engine with a BPR equals to 12), and in Fig.4.1 it is possible to see the 3-D virtual model of the aircraft.

Figure 4.1: WP8-AC6 3D aircraft's model with highlighting on the engines and a portion of the internal design.

To better understand the aircraft's type, it is possible to compare it with the *Embraer E-Jets* family [45]. The *Embraer E-Jets* family is a series of narrow-body short - to medium-range twin-engine jet airliners and the series has been a commercial success, primarily due to its ability to serve lower-demand routes, while offering many of the same features of larger jets. Historically, this family was introduced at the *Paris Air Show* in 1999 and entered production in 2002 (the main feature of this aircraft's family is the engine's type equipped on it, i.e. the *General Electric CF34-8E* [46]); however, in November 2011, *Embraer* announced that it would develop revamped versions of the E-Jets, arranged in the *E-Jet E2* family (the most important improvement will be the introduction of the *Pratt & Whitney PW1000G* engine's family [43]). The engine's improvement will be discussed, in detail, at the end of this chapter from the point of view of the BPR's effect on the noise emissions.

Figure 4.2: Basic classification of the E-Jets E2 with respect to the E-Jets from the number of passengers point of view.

[45]

4.2.2 Input Data Definition

In order to perform the noise estimation, all needed information and data of the tested aircraft have to be taken from the CPACS file, in direct or indirect way, in order to update all input files, as it has been described, in detail, in the previous chapter. In this paragraph, all data are going to be described and defined, in order to better understand the starting conditions for this test case.

Input File Data

Regarding the main input data and information, in the following Tables all the aircraft's features and geometric data have been defined: in Table 4.1 all CPACS data from the *Toolspecific* section have been described; in Table 4.2 all CPACS data, directly taken from the fixed part of CPACS file, have been described; and in Table 4.3 all data, acquired indirectly from the CPACS file, have been described.

Variable Name (file.csv)	Description	Value
N_ENG	Aircraft's Number of engines	2
ENGINE_FILE	Engine File Name	PW1524G.csv
POS_ENG	Engine Position index	1-Engines mounted below the wing
TYPE_GROUND	Ground type	2-Grass (Default)
TYPE_TURB	Turbolent type	4-Turbolent (Default)
WAT	Aircraft type index	0-Transport aeroplane wing (Default)
WWT	Wing type index	1-Conventional wing (Default)
NH	Number of horizontal surfaces	1

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Variable Name (file.csv)	Description	Value
NV	Number of vertical surfaces	1
N_SLOT	Number of flap slots	1
N_MLG	Number of main landing gear	2
Wings_sequence	Sequence of wing type in CPACS standard file	1;2;3

Table 4.1: Input parameters from the CPACS Toolspecific for the WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Variable Name (file.csv)	Description	Value
name	CPACS file name	AGILE4_T81_ REFERENCE
N_WHEEL_MLG	Main landing gears number of wheels	2
D_MLG	Diameter of main landing gear's tyre (m)	1.4
S_MLG	Main landing gear structure's length (m)	2.01
N_WHEEL_NLG	Nose landing gears number of wheels	2
D_NLG	Diameter of nose landing gear's tyre (m)	0.9
S_NLG	Nose landing gear structure's length (m)	1.65

Table 4.2: Input parameters from the fixed part of CPACS file for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Variable Name (file.csv)	Description	Value
SW	Wing Surface (m^2)	81.41
BW	Wing Span (m)	27.19
NH	Number of Horizontal Tails	1
SH	Horizontal Tail Surface (m^2)	20.64
BH	Horizontal Tail Span (m)	8.72
NV	Number of Vertical Tails	1
SV	Vertical Tail Surface (m^2)	27.66
BV	Vertical Tail Span (m)	4.55
SF	Total Flaps Surface (m^2)	7.70
BF	Flaps Span (m)	8.56

Table 4.3: Input parameters extrapolated from the fixed part of CPACS file for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Receiver Files Data

The receiver files have to be updated for all possible test cases available in the CS-25 regulation: Approach, Lateral, Fly-Over. As it have been discussed in paragraph 2.3.1, the receiver microphones' positions have to be defined in function of the regulation constrains; therefore, in Table 4.4 the Approach microphone's position has been defined, in Table 4.5 the Lateral microphones' positions have been defined, and in Table 4.6 the Fly-Over microphone's position has been defined. It is important to underline that for the Approach and Fly-Over cases the linear extrapolation procedure is not exploited due to the fact that, for both cases, there is a fixed and known, from regulation, microphones' position; instead, for the Lateral test case it is necessary to exploit it due to the absence of a precise microphone's

position to analyse; in fact, contrary to the previous cases, the regulation establishes a microphone's position range, as it has been defined in Table 4.5 and the certification position will be the most significant one in the established range.

Variable Name	Description	Value
Humidity	Relative Humidity (%)	70
X	Microphone position along X (m)	-2000
Y	Microphone position along Y (m)	0
Z	Microphone position along Z (m)	1.2
LINEAR	Linear array extrapolation command	0
N_LIN	Calculated number of source positions	0
DELTA_LIN	Time interval between two positions	0

Table 4.4: Approach's microphone's position data and set parameters for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Variable Name	Description	Value
Humidity	Relative Humidity (%)	70
X	Microphone position along X (m)	0
Y	Microphone position along Y (m)	450
Z	Microphone position along Z (m)	1.2
LINEAR	Linear array extrapolation command	1
N_LIN	Calculated number of source positions	81
DELTA_LIN	Time interval between two positions	50

Table 4.5: Lateral's microphone's position data and set parameters for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Variable Name	Description	Value
Humidity	Relative Humidity (%)	70
X	Microphone position along X (m)	6500
Y	Microphone position along Y (m)	0
Z	Microphone position along Z (m)	1.2
LINEAR	Linear array extrapolation command	0
N_LIN	Calculated number of source positions	0
DELTA_LIN	Time interval between two positions	0

Table 4.6: Fly-Over's microphone's position data and set parameters for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Trajectory Files Data

The Trajectory files, exploited for the WP8 aircraft's analyses, refers to all test cases, defined respecting the CS-25 regulation's constrains. On the basis of this aspect, it is necessary to characterize the Approach, Lateral and Fly-Over files through the simplified trajectory's estimation.

As it has been seen in paragraph 3.4, there are several input data and information to define, of which someones come from the *Noise Toolspecific* section, while some other ones come from the other *UNINA Toolspecific* sections; therefore, in the following tables all data are going to be defined for the test cases to evaluate.

Regarding the approach case, in Table 4.7 all data taken from the *Noise Toolspecific* have been defined; in Table 4.8 all other *Toolspecific* data have been assigned and in Table 4.9 the smoothing parameters, assigned to obtain the best approach path in terms of similarity to reality, have been assumed. As it is possible to observe, in order to estimate the approach flight path, the linear extrapolation functionality has been chosen, due to the linear trend of the simplified path.

Variable Name	Description	Value
X	X Approach distance (m)	-3200
Y	Y Approach distance (m)	0
Z	Z Approach distance (m)	167.705
CLIMB_ANGLE	Approach climb angle from regulations (°)	-3
Slat_contribution	Include Flap action	1
NAME	Trajectory Name	APPROACH TRAJECTORY
ENG_SETTING	Select the thrust rating.	2
Max_Cruise_Thrust	Max Cruise Thrust of a single Engine (N)	40 000
LINEAR	Linear array extrapolation command	1
N_LIN	Calculated number of source positions	500
DELTA_LIN	Time interval between two position	0.5

Table 4.7: Approach CS-25 trajectory input parameters from the Noise Tools specific section for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Variable Name	Description	
Cd0	CD_0 value	0.019549
Dcd0_LN	Landing Delta CD_0 due to Flap	0.08
Dcd0_landing	Landing Delta CD_0 due to Landing Gears	0.015
eLN	Oswald Factor in the Landing phase	0.75
CLmaxLN	CL_max in Landing phase	2.8
FLAP_DEFL	Flap deflection during Landing (°)	40
mMLM	Maximum Landing Mass (Kg)	33 615.80

Table 4.8: Approach CS-25 trajectory input parameters from the UNINA Toolspecific section for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Variable Name	Description	Value
Relative_initial_interp_pos	Initial interpolation position parameter.	10
Relative_final_interp_pos	Final interpolation position parameter.	10
Smoothing_coefficient	Coefficient to define smoothness of spline interpolation	5

Table 4.9: Smoothing parameters for the CS-25 Approach flight path.

Concerning the Lateral case, in Table 4.11 all data taken from the *Noise Toolspecific* have been defined; in Table 4.10 all other *Toolspecific* data have been assigned, and in Table 4.12 the smoothing parameters, assigned to obtain the best Take-Off path and time-histories in terms of similarity to reality, have been assumed.

Variable Name	Description	
Cd0	CD_0 value	0.019549
CL_g	CL_g value	1.0
μ_g	Wheel-Runway rolling friction coefficient	0.015
eTO	Take-Off's Oswald Factor	0.75
CLmaxTO	CL_max in Take-Off phase	2.8
FLAP_DEFL	Take-Off flap deflection($^{\circ}$)	40
nlof	Lift-Off load factor	1.13
n2	Virtual obstacle load factor	1.18
mTOM	Maximum Take-Off Mass (Kg)	40 177.227
Speed_vector	VMC vector evolution during Lateral	0;17.015;34.03;51.044; 68.06;85.0735;102.09; 119.10;136.12;153.13
TO_Thrust_vect	Take-Off Thrust Vector in function of VMC	78.26;70;65.08;62.66 60.24;58.47;56.70; 55.57;54.29;52.904;

Table 4.10: Take-Off CS-25 trajectory input parameters from the UNINA *Toolspecific* section for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Variable Name	Description	Value
Z_obstacle	Virtual Obstacle Height (ft)	35
Z_climb	Climb phase's vertical distance (m)	300
Z_FlyOver	Fly-Over phase's vertical distance (m)	600
DCD0_Flap	Take-Off Delta CD_0 due to Flap	0.0128
DCD0_LandingGear	Take-Off Delta CD_0 due to Landing Gears	0.015
Slat_contribution	Include Flap action	1
NAME	Trajectory Name	LATERAL TRAJECTORY
ENG_SETTING	Select the thrust rating.	1
Max_Cruise_Thrust	Max Cruise Thrust of a single Engine (N)	78 216
MLG_ON	Fixed or Retractable Main Landing Gears	0
NLG_ON	Fixed or Retractable Nose Landing Gears	0

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Variable Name	Description	Value
Number_Ground	Intervals' number for Ground discretization	70
Number_Airborne	Intervals' number for Airborne discretization	40
Number_Climb	Intervals' number for Climb discretization	60
Number_FlyOver	Intervals' number for Fly-Over discretization	70

Table 4.11: Take-Off CS-25 trajectory input parameters from the Noise Tools specific section for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

PATH

Edge Name	Relative_initial_interp_pos	Relative_final_interp_pos	Smoothing_coefficient
Airborne/ Climb	5	40	10
Climb/ Fly-Over	5	40	5

AIRSPEED

Edge Name	Relative_initial_interp_pos	Relative_final_interp_pos	Smoothing_coefficient
Inside Climb	3	10	4

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THROTTLE

Edge Name	Relative_initial_ interp_pos	Relative_final_ interp_pos	Smoothing_ coefficient
Climb/ Fly-Over	4	40	4
Inside Fly-Over	4	15	4

CLIMB ANGLE

Edge Name	Relative_initial_ interp_pos	Relative_final_ interp_pos	Smoothing_ coefficient
Ground/ Airborne	5	60	4
Airborne/ Climb	20	40	10
Inside Climb	5	20	3
Climb/ Fly-Over	3	40	4
Inside Fly-Over	4	15	4

Table 4.12: Smoothing parameters for WP8-AC6 aircraft's Take-Off flight path and time-histories.

In the end, regarding the Fly-Over case, the input data, necessary to perform its trajectory, are the same exploited to estimate the Lateral trajectory; the only difference is the trajectory name in the specific *.csv* file. However, the Lateral/Fly-Over case has to be estimated without the linear extrapolation procedure, rather there is a precise estimation procedure to follow, that is based on the performances

parameters and on the number of intervals necessary to discretize the various phases of the flight path.

Control Parameters File Data

The Control Parameters file has to be differently updated in function of the noise tool's use: being more precise, there will be the main file setting, if this file will refer to the certification analyse; while, there will be a specific file setting to perform the Footprint calculation, due to the fact that it is necessary to reduce the computational weight and time. In function of this aspect, in Table 4.13 all data, necessary to update the certification control parameters file, have been defined. As it is possible to notice, all control parameters have been set, in order to consider as much as possible effects and contributions in such a way as to obtain the estimation as complete as possible.

Variable Name	Description	Value
U	Unit reference system	1
Certification_Type	Certification choice	0
ICAPP	Run Approach case	1
ICLAT	Run Lateral case	1
ICFLY	Run Fly-Over case	1
APPROACH_T_FILE	Trajectory Approach File Name	TrajectoryApproach.csv
FLYOVER_T_FILE	Trajectory Fly-Over File Name	TrajectoryFlyover.csv
LATERAL_T_FILE	Trajectory Lateral File Name	TrajectoryLateral.csv

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Variable Name	Description	Value
APPROACH_R_FILE	Receivers Approach File Name	Receivers_Approach.csv
FLYOVER_R_FILE	Receivers FlyOver File Name	Receivers_Flyover.csv
LATERAL_R_FILE	Receivers Lateral File Name	Receivers_Lateral.csv
IA1	Wing contribution	1
IA2	Horizontal tail contribution	1
IA3	Vertical tail contribution	1
IA4	Slat contribution	1
IA5	Flap contribution	1
IA6	Main Landing Gears contribution	1
IA7	Nose Landing Gears contribution	1
IAIR	Airframe contribution	1
IENG	Engine contribution	1
IATM	Atmospheric attenuation effect	1
IREFL	Ground reflection effect	1
ILAT	Lateral attenuation effect	1

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Variable Name	Description	Value
ISPL	Sound pressure level calculation	1
IOASPL	Overall Sound pressure level calculation	1
ISEL	Sound exposure level calculation	1
IPNL	Perceived noise level calculation	1
IPNLT	Tone corrected Perceived noise level calculation	1
IEPNL_NT	Effective Perceived noise level calculation	1
IEPNL	Tone corrected Effective Perceived noise level calculation	1
WDB	Weighted Sound pressure level calculation	0
K_SPL_WING	Wing multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_HTAIL	Horizontal tail(s) multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_VTAIL	Vertical tail(s) multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_SLAT	Slat multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_FLAP	Flap multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_MLG	Main Landing Gears multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_NLG	Nose Landing Gears multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_ENGINE	Engine(s) multiplicative factor(s)	1.0
Δ_SPL_WING	Wing additive factor	0.0
Δ_SPL_HTAIL	Horizontal tail(s) additive factor	0.0
Δ_SPL_VTAIL	Vertical tail(s) additive factor	0.0

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Variable Name	Description	
Δ_SPL_SLAT	Slat additive factor	1.0
Δ_SPL_FLAP	Flap additive factor	1.0
Δ_SPL_MLG	Main Landing Gears additive factor	1.0
Δ_SPL_NLG	Nose Landing Gears additive factor	1.0
Δ_SPL_ENGINE	Engine(s) additive factor(s)	1.0
IOCSV	Output file in .csv format generation	0
IOMAX	Print the most Critical Result in a separate file	1
IOEW	Print the Results in all the multiple files	1
IOALL	Print all the Information of interest	1
IOSEP	Print Frames	1
IOTIT	Print Titles	1
IOTIME	Print an array containing calculation Times	1
IOPART	Print each component Contribution and Propagation Effect	1
IOTR	Print trajectory details	1
IOMIC	Print microphone details	1
IOTC	Print the correction of the the calculated PNLT	1
IOA1	Print Wing contribution separately	1
IOA2	Print horizontal tail contribution separately	1

It continues in the next page...

Variable Name	Description	Value
IOA3	Print vertical tail contribution separately	1
IOA4	Print Slat contribution separately	1
IOA5	Print Flap contribution separately	1
IOA6	Print Main landing Gears contribution separately	1
IOA7	Print Nose landing Gears contribution separately	1
IOAIR	Print Airframe contribution separately	1
IOENG	Print Engine contribution separately	1
IOATM	Print Atmospheric attenuation effect separately	1
IOREFL	Print Ground Reflection effect separately	1
IOLAT	Print Lateral attenuation effect separately	1
IOLOG_I	Write warnings about Input data Reading	1
IOLOG_ICHK	Write warnings about Input data Correctness	1
IOLOG_CALC	Write warnings generated during Calculation	1
IOLOG_OCHK	Write warnings about Output data Correctness	1
IOLOG_ALL	Write all Warnings	1
PREC	Number of Digits after the comma	1
WIDTH	Number of digits for Numbers' field width	10
WIDTH_TITLE	Number of digits for titles' field width	16
FILLER	Optional symbol for separating values	;

Table 4.13: Control parameters set to perform the noise certification estimation for WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Concerning the Footprint calculation, there are several parameters neglected, in order to improve the calculation itself (these parameters are going to be set on 0):

- **Concerning the Test Cases**, in order to evaluate the Approach Footprint, the Approach case's command alone will be considered ($ICAPP = 1$); while for the Take-Off Footprint, the Lateral case's command alone will be considered ($ICLAT = 1$);
- **Concerning the Sound Metrics**, the only metric to evaluate is the one defined by the CS-25 regulation and it is valid for both Footprints ($ISPL = 1$ and $IEPNL = 1$);
- **Concerning the Output and Printing Conditions**, all parameters are going to be neglected, with the exception of the Map's command, the Most significant results files' command ($IOMAX = 1$ and $IOMAP = 1$), the Frames Evaluation command ($IOSEP = 1$) and all Log commands ($IOLOG_I$, $IOLOG_ICLK$, $IOLOG_CALC$, $IOLOG_OCHK$, $IOLOG_ALL = 1$).

4.2.3 Noise Certification Results

The reference aircraft has been totally described and the needed input data and parameters have been set; therefore, it is possible to run the Integration Tool and, consequently, the Noise Tool ATTILA++ to obtain the certification results to compare with the regulation constrains and limits, as it has been discussed in paragraph 2.3.1. Several test cases are going to be discussed in separated sections, in order to highlight the specific results and evaluations.

Approach Test Case

Concerning the Approach case, it is possible to compare the estimated total noise emission with the certification limit from the CS-25 regulation, remembering that this limit is function of the aircraft's weight and it has been evaluated with the margin calculation function (see paragraph 3.3.12). In Table 4.14 these values have been compared, defining the noise emission's margin (this margin will be useful to evaluate

the noise airport's charges and revenues); it is possible to notice that this result is consistent with the typical noise emissions of similar certified aircraft (see Fig.2.14).

Estimated Value(dB)	Certification Limit(dB)	Noise Margin(dB)
92.3 dB	98 dB	5.7 dB

Table 4.14: Total noise emissions (expressed in EPNLdB) compared with the regulation limit from CS-25 for the WP8-AC6 aircraft in the Approach test case.

Examining in depth the noise estimation procedure, in Table 4.15 all contributions and effects, assigned in the input data definition section, have been shown: remembering the logarithmic law that links noise values, the first aspect to highlight is the absence of emissions from the Vertical Tail (due to its relative position with respect to the flight path and the microphone position, it does not produce significant noise emissions, therefore, they can be assumed like none).

Contribution	EPNL Value with Tone Correction(dB)	EPNL Value without Tone Correction(dB)
Wing	71.7 dB	71.4 dB
Horizontal Tail	64 dB	63.4 dB
Vertical Tail	-inf	-inf
Slat	75.6 dB	75.1 dB
Flap	76.8 dB	76.3 dB
Main Gears	68.7 dB	68.0 dB
Nose Gears	63.8 dB	62.8 dB
Airframe	80.6 dB	80.2 dB
Engine	88.9 dB	88.2 dB

Table 4.15: Noise results from all selected contributions of the WP8-AC6 aircraft with and without the Tone Correction effect, in the Approach test case.

Moreover, it is clear that the main airframe's sources are all lifting surfaces located on the main wing; but the most important and obvious aspect to underline is the majority effect due to the engines: in fact, comparing the single engine emissions with the total emissions and the airframe emissions, it is evident that the engine ones represents more or less the quasi-totality of the total aircraft's emissions; while the airframe's contributions should represent more or less +1dB in the total value, even if during the Approach phase the engine setting would be at its minimum, due to its "inactivity" in this phase.

The Integration Tool's execution returns also the trajectory's plotting that in this specific test case restricts itself to the flight path showing, as it is possible to see in Fig.4.3.

Figure 4.3: Simplified and smoothed approach flight path performed by the WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Lateral Test Case

Concerning the Lateral case, it is possible to compare the estimated total noise emission with the certification limit from the CS-25 regulation, remembering that this limit is function of the aircraft's weight and it has been evaluated with the margin calculation function (see paragraph 3.3.12). In Table 4.16 these values have been compared, defining the noise emission's margin; it is possible to notice that this result is consistent with the typical noise emissions of similar certified aircraft (see Fig.2.8), as it happens for the approach results.

Estimated Value(dB)	Certification Limit(dB)	Noise Margin(dB)
86.3 dB	94.418 dB	8.118 dB

Table 4.16: Total noise emissions (expressed in EPNLdB) compared with the regulation limit from CS-25 for the WP8-AC6 aircraft in the Lateral test case.

Contribution	EPNL Value with Tone Correction(dB)	EPNL Value without Tone Correction(dB)
Wing	56.0 dB	55.2 dB
Horizontal Tail	44.8 dB	44.6 dB
Vertical Tail	51.7 dB	51.3 dB
Slat	58.3 dB	57.5 dB
Flap	56.7 dB	56.0 dB
Main Gears	46.4 dB	46.4 dB
Nose Gears	41.2 dB	41.2 dB
Airframe	63.6 dB	62.8 dB
Engine	84.1 dB	83.0 dB

Table 4.17: Noise results from all selected contributions of the WP8-AC6 aircraft with and without the Tone Correction effect, in the Lateral test case.

Examining in depth the noise estimation procedure, in Table 4.17 all contributions and effects, assigned in the input data definition section, have been shown: remembering the logarithmic law that links noise values, the first aspect to highlight, in this case, is the presence of emissions from the Vertical Tail, because, this time, this emissions can be measured, due to the relative position between the microphones and the flight path (microphones have been located at a defined "y" distance; so, they are not along the flight path and they can "see" the Vertical Tail).

Moreover, it is clear that the main airframe's sources are, still, all lifting surfaces located on the main wing. The important difference with respect to the Approach case is the total prevalence of the engine's emissions: in the Lateral case, the aircraft's configuration is less aggressive with respect the Approach one (lower deflection of the movable surfaces that leads to lower aerodynamic forces and effects), and this aspect leads to a lower structure-flow's interaction, that causes a significant noise emissions' reduction; but, on the other side, the engine exploiting is more consistent and this leads to an increase of the noise emissions. In conclusion, the reduction on the airframe's emissions causes an overall reduction of noise emissions, which normally have a value lower than 5/6 dB order of magnitude (considering the logarithmic laws, this means a difference of four times in noise emissions), despite a louder engine.

The integration tool's execution returns, in addition, the trajectory's plotting and time-histories, as it is possible to see in Figs.4.4-4.7.

Figure 4.4: Simplified and smoothed take-off flight path performed by the WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Figure 4.5: Simplified and smoothed climb angle's time-history for the take-off phase performed by the WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Figure 4.6: Simplified and smoothed speed's time-history for the take-off phase performed by the WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Figure 4.7: Simplified and smoothed throttle rate's time-history for the take-off phase performed by the WP8-AC6 aircraft.

Fly-Over Test Case

Concerning the Fly-Over case, it is possible to compare the estimated total noise emission with the certification limit from the CS-25 regulation, remembering that this limit is function of the aircraft's weight and it has been evaluated with the margin calculation function (see paragraph 3.3.12). In Table 4.18 these values have been compared, defining the noise emission's margin; it is possible to notice that this result is consistent with the typical noise emissions of similar certified aircraft (see Fig.2.10), as it happens for the Approach and Lateral results.

Estimated Value(dB)	Certification Limit(dB)	Noise Margin(dB)
80.1 dB	89.0 dB	8.9 dB

Table 4.18: Total noise emissions (expressed in EPNLdB) compared with the regulation limit from CS-25 for the WP8-AC6 aircraft in the Fly-Over test case.

Contribution	EPNL Value with Tone Correction(dB)	EPNL Value without Tone Correction(dB)
Wing	65.7 dB	65.1 dB
Horizontal Tail	58.7 dB	58.1 dB
Vertical Tail	-inf	-inf
Slat	68.9 dB	68.4 dB
Flap	66.7 dB	66.1 dB
Main Gears	-inf	-inf
Nose Gears	-inf	-inf
Airframe	72.5 dB	72.0 dB
Engine	75.9 dB	75.2 dB

Table 4.19: Noise results from all selected contributions of the WP8-AC6 aircraft with and without the Tone Correction effect, in the Fly-Over test case.

Examining in depth the noise estimation procedure, in Table 4.19 all contributions and effects, assigned in the input data definition section, have been shown: remembering the logarithmic law that links noise values, the first aspect to highlight is the "comeback" of the absence of emissions from the Vertical Tail, like the Approach case, and this happens because of the microphone position along the flight path (being aligned with the flight path, the microphone does not "see" the Vertical Tail).

Moreover, it is clear that the main airframe's sources are, still, all lifting surfaces located on the main wing. The singular result, obtained in the Fly-Over analyse, is the no contributions due to the Landing Gears, even if it is due to the fact that they have been retracted at the beginning of the climb phase, so during the Lateral test case. In terms of engine-airframe's comparison, the engine contribution is, always, the main one, even if, due to the Cut-Back manoeuvre, the engine effect's is lowered; but, on the other side, the airframe's contribution has been lowered too (it is due to the increase of the relative distance between microphone and airframe itself). In function of this aspects, the Fly-Over test case is the one with the lowest noise emissions (main improvement comes from the Cut-Back correction): there is a reduction of more or less 6 dB order of magnitude, with respect to the Lateral case, and even 10 dB order of magnitude, with respect to the Approach condition. The integration tool's execution returns the trajectory's plotting and time-histories, as it is possible to see in Figs.4.4-4.7, that contains both Lateral and Fly-Over plots.

4.2.4 Footprint

The Footprint Tool is able to plot an estimated two-dimensions contour of the total noise emissions in the hypothesis of locating a dense mesh of microphones, distributed homogeneously along the "x" and "y" axes. In Fig.4.8 it is possible to observe the Approach Footprint in a local reference frame, which center corresponds to the beginning of the runway from the approaching point of view; the characteristic trend of this footprint is the "shell" trend, because there is an increase of the noise emissions going inside the contour with the highest values in the inner layer of plot;

moreover, this increase tends to move toward the runway, due to the reduction of the relative distance between microphones and aircraft.

Figure 4.8: Approach test case Footprint, divided in several contour levels [75; 80; 85; 87; 90; 95]. The Footprint refers to the AC6-WP8 aircraft and it has been estimated through a 61x81 microphones' matrix.

In Fig.4.9, instead, it is possible to observe the Take-Off Footprint, that include both Lateral and Fly-Over phases, in the same previous reference frame with the only difference in the moving direction of the aircraft and of the contour, which is perfectly opposite to the Approach case (it corresponds to the take-offing point of view). For the Take-Off case, the "shell" analogy is valid too and the highest value have been measured near the runway, also in this case (the relative distance's reduction occurs with the same logic of the previous case); the only difference is the more particular shape that finds out a localized increase of the noise emissions along the "y" axis in the x distance's range at the end of the runway and immediately after (this trend can be associated to the increase of aircraft's speed and, consequently,

the engine's thrust during the lift-off phase, that balances and dominates the microphones' relative distances' increase).

Figure 4.9: Take-Off test case Footprint, divided in several contour levels [75; 80; 85; 90; 95]. The Footprint refers to the AC6-WP8 aircraft and it has been estimated through a 102x90 microphones' matrix.

The estimated results, achieved with the Footprint Tool, have been exploited to try to clarify the real impact of the aircraft's action on the local environment, in terms of noise emissions and noise pollution. Several studies have been done in the last decades on the psychological impact of the acoustic emissions, produced by the aircraft during the take-offs and landings in the environment near the airport. In function of this aspect, the previous contours have been overlapped on several geographic images, acquired from the satellites' geo-localization system, better known as *Google Earth* [47]. In Fig.4.10 it is possible to observe the noise footprint impact in the Take-Off case on the local environment, near the *Naples-Capodichino International Airport* [48]; instead in Fig.4.11 it is possible to observe the noise footprint impact in the Approach case in the same environment. It is

evident, in these plots, how significant is the noise impact on people living near the airport, considering, above all, that the Naples' airport has been located in a quite dense residential zone.

Figure 4.10: Take-Off test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Naples-Capodichino International Airport's local environment.

Figure 4.11: Approach test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Naples-Capodichino International Airport's local environment.

A completely different discussion can be made on the Frankfurt Airport "*Flughafen Frankfurt am Main*" [49] which location is far from the residential zones; in this way, the noise emissions effects on the local population can be mitigated and they will impact less. In Fig.4.13 it is possible to notice the really low impact of the noise emissions due to the Approach phase of the AC6-WP8 aircraft, while in Fig.4.12 it is possible to notice the same positive effect for the Take-Off phase performed by the same aircraft.

Figure 4.12: Take-Off test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Frankfurt Airport's local environment.

Figure 4.13: Approach test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Frankfurt Airport's local environment.

4.2.5 BPR Effect Evaluation

The final analyse that is possible to perform on the tested Turbo-Fan engine aircraft is the evaluation of the BPR effect on the noise emissions. As it has been seen in the previous paragraphs, the most significant contribution is the engine one and this is the reason why the main improvements to reduce the noise emissions have been applied to the engine (see paragraph 1.2.4). Concerning the main goal of the WP8, a significant improvement to achieve the noise reduction, acting on the engine, consists in the increase of the BPR of the Turbo-Fan engine: the working line of the WP8 project is the retrofiting of the aircraft on which has been performed the previous analyses and the BPR's change can be an important solution for this process. Initially, in fact, the tested aircraft exploited an engine with a BPR equals to 5.4 (similar to the *CF34* engine's type [46]); while the actual exploited improved engine is the one similar to the *Pratt & Whitney PW1000G* family's engines [43], which BPR is equal to 12. In Table 4.20 it is possible to compare the several noise results, achieved with different BPR (it has been exploited

the engine function able to correct the engine input data in order to adapt them to a different assigned BPR value), and the reduction trend, on increasing of the engine’s BPR, is evident: in particular, the most evident effect can be observed in the Lateral case, where normally the engine’s contribution finds its maximum, and, in general, in the Take-Off phase (Lateral and Fly-Over); instead, during the Approach case, the reduction is more restrained.

BPR	Approach(dB)	Lateral(dB)	Fly-Over(dB)	Cumulative(dB)
5.4	93.4	91.4	84.3	269.1
9	93.0	88.9	82.1	264.0
12	92.3	86.3	80.1	258.7
15	92.0	83.8	78.2	254.0

Table 4.20: BPR effect on the total noise emission for all test cases, achieved by the analyse of the AC6-WP8 aircraft.

The Footprint Tool can be exploited, also in this case, to clarify the BPR effect, considering a specific contour level as reference value, in order to compare the several contour lines at this level on varying of engine’s BPR. In Fig.4.15 it is possible to compare the contour lines in the Take-Off phase (considering the assigned contour level, it has been referring to the Fly-Over case), while in Fig.4.14 it is possible to make the same comparison for the Approach phase.

Figure 4.14: Approach Footprint’s contour lines comparison on varying of engine’s BPR at reference noise level equals to 90 dB.

Figure 4.15: Take-Off Footprint's contour lines comparison on varying of engine's BPR at reference noise level equals to 80 dB.

The contour lines' comparisons confirm the stronger BPR effect in the Take-Off phase (there is a clear distance between the various contour lines) with respect the Approach phase, which trend is less varied.

4.3 WP7-AC3 Turbo-Prop Engine Aircraft

4.3.1 Aircraft's General Overview

The WP7-AC3 is a 19 passengers small twin turboprop commuter aircraft that is equipped with an engine based on the *Pratt & Whitney Canada PW100* engine's family [50], or, being more precise, the PW127 engine, and in Fig.4.16 it is possible to see the 3D virtual model of the aircraft.

To better understand the aircraft's type, it is possible to compare it with the *ATR-42* and/or *ATR-72* [51]. The ATR 42 is a regional airliner produced by ATR in the 80s, that is equipped with two turboprop engines *Pratt & Whitney Canada PW120s* (it belongs to the *Pratt & Whitney Canada PW100* engine's family); instead the ATR 72 is a twin-engine turboprop, short-haul regional airliner and it is the retrofitted version of the ATR 42, in fact it is equipped with the *Pratt & Whitney Canada PW127* and, moreover, it presents several improvements on the avionics and other on-board systems.

Figure 4.16: WP7-AC3 3D aircraft's model with highlighting on the engines and a portion of the internal design. [52]

4.3.2 Input Data Definition

In order to perform the noise estimation, all needed information and data of the tested aircraft have to be taken from the CPACS file in direct or indirect way to update all input files, as it has been described in detail in previous chapter. In this paragraph, all data are going to be described and defined, in order to better understand the starting conditions for this test case.

Input File Data

Regarding the main input data and information, in the following Tables all the aircraft's features and geometric data have been defined: in Table 4.23 all CPACS data from the *Toolspecific* section have been described; in Table 4.22 all CPACS data, directly taken from the fixed part of CPACS file, have been described; and in Table 4.21 all data, acquired indirectly from the CPACS file, have been described.

Variable Name (file.csv)	Description	Value
SW	Wing Surface (m^2)	32.91
BW	Wing Span (m)	17.54
NH	Number of Horizontal Tails	1
SH	Horizontal Tail Surface (m^2)	6.22
BH	Horizontal Tail Span (m)	5.36
NV	Number of Vertical Tails	1
SV	Vertical Tail Surface (m^2)	9.19
BV	Vertical Tail Span (m)	2.40
SF	Total Flaps Surface (m^2)	3.59
BF	Flaps Span (m)	5.18

Table 4.21: Input parameters extrapolated from the fixed part of CPACS file for WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Variable Name (file.csv)	Description	Value
name	CPACS file name	openAD
N_WHEEL_MLG	Main landing gears number of wheels	2
D_MLG	Diameter of main landing gear's tyre (m)	0.77
S_MLG	Main landing gear structure's length (m)	1.25
N_WHEEL_NLG	Nose landing gears number of wheels	2
D_NLG	Diameter of nose landing gear's tyre (m)	0.44
S_NLG	Nose landing gear structure's length (m)	0.746

Table 4.22: Input parameters from the fixed part of CPACS file for WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Variable Name (file.csv)	Description	Value
N_ENG	Aircraft's Number of engines	2
ENGINE_FILE	Engine File Name	NoiseTP_PW127.csv
POS_ENG	Engine Position index	1-Engines mounted below the wing
TYPE_GROUND	Ground type	2-Grass (Default)
TYPE_TURB	Turbolent type	4-Turbolent (Default)
WAT	Aircraft type index	0-Transport aeroplane wing (Default)
WWT	Wing type index	1-Conventional wing (Default)
NH	Number of horizontal surfaces	1
NV	Number of vertical surfaces	1
N_SLOT	Number of flap slots	1
N_MLG	Number of main landing gear	2
Wings_sequence	Sequence of wing type in CPACS standard file	2;3;1

Table 4.23: Input parameters from the CPACS Toolspecific for the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Receiver Files Data

The receiver files have to be updated for the test case available in the CS-23 regulation, that is the Lateral/Take-Off case. As it have been discussed in paragraph 2.3.2, the receiver microphones' positions have to be defined in function of the regulation constrains and in Table 4.24 the Lateral microphone's position has been defined.

It is important to underline that, for the test case, the linear extrapolation procedure is not exploited, due to the fact that there is a fixed and known from regulation microphone's position.

Variable Name	Description	Value
Humidity	Relative Humidity (%)	70
X	Microphone position along X (m)	2500
Y	Microphone position along Y (m)	0
Z	Microphone position along Z (m)	1.2
LINEAR	Linear array extrapolation command	0
N_LIN	Calculated number of source positions	0
DELTA_LIN	Time interval between two positions	0

Table 4.24: Lateral's microphone's position data and set parameters for WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Trajectory Files Data

The Trajectory file exploited for the WP7 aircraft's analyse refers to the test case, defined respecting the CS-23 regulation's constrains. On the base of this aspect, it is necessary to characterize the Lateral file through the simplified trajectory's estimation.

As it has been seen in paragraph 3.4, there are several input data and information to define, of which someones come from the *Noise Toolspecific* section, while some

other ones from the other *UNINA Toolspecific* sections; therefore, in the following tables, all data are going to be defined for the test case to evaluate.

Going in detail, in Table 4.27 all data taken from the *Noise Toolspecific* have been defined; in Table 4.10 all other *Toolspecific* data have been assigned and in Table 4.25 the smoothing parameters, assigned to obtain the best Take-Off path, in terms of similarity to reality, have been assumed.

PATH

Edge Name	Relative_initial_ interp_pos	Relative_final_ interp_pos	Smoothing_ coefficient
Airborne/ Climb	10	30	5

AIRSPEED

Edge Name	Relative_initial_ interp_pos	Relative_final_ interp_pos	Smoothing_ coefficient
Inside Climb	2	40	4

CLIMB ANGLE

Edge Name	Relative_initial_ interp_pos	Relative_final_ interp_pos	Smoothing_ coefficient
Ground/ Airborne	3	40	4
Airborne/ Climb	3	17	3
Inside Climb	5	30	2

Table 4.25: Smoothing parameters for WP7-AC3 aircraft’s Take-Off flight path and time-histories.

Variable Name	Description	
Cd0	CD_0 value	0.0331
CL_g	CL_g value	1
μ_g	Wheel-Runway rolling friction coefficient	0.03
eTO	Take-Off's Oswald Factor	0.8
CLmaxTO	CL_max in Take-Off phase	1.9
FLAP_DEFL	Take-Off flap deflection($^{\circ}$)	40
nlof	Lift-Off load factor	1.13
n2	Virtual obstacle load factor	1.18
mTOM	Maximum Take-Off Mass (Kg)	8 648.098
V_y	Aircraft's speed at Maximum Rate of Climb (m/s)	63.67
Speed_vector	VMC vector evolution during Lateral	0;17.015;34.03;51.044; 68.06;85.0735;102.09; 119.10;136.12;153.13
TO_Thrust_vect	Take-Off Thrust Vector in function of VMC	18.67;17.64;16.12;14 11.86;10.19;8.82; 7.63;6.64;5.67;

Table 4.26: Take-Off CS-23 trajectory input parameters from the UNINA Toolspecific section for WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Variable Name	Description	Value
Z_obstacle	Virtual Obstacle Height (ft)	50
DCD0_Flap	Take-Off Delta CD ₀ due to Flap	0.0128
DCD0_LandingGear	Take-Off Delta CD ₀ due to Landing Gears	0.015
Slat_contribution	Include Flap action	1
NAME	Trajectory Name	LATERAL TRAJECTORY
ENG_SETTING	Select the thrust rating.	1
Max_TakeOff_Thrust	Max Take-Off Thrust of a single Engine (N)	18 670
MLG_ON	Fixed or Retractable Main Landing Gears	0
NLG_ON	Fixed or Retractable Nose Landing Gears	0
Number_Ground	Intervals' number for Ground discretization	70
Number_Airborne	Intervals' number for Airborne discretization	40
Number_Climb	Intervals' number for Climb discretization	60

Table 4.27: Take-Off CS-23 trajectory input parameters from the Noise Tools specific section for WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Control Parameters File Data

The control parameters file has to be differently updated in function of the Noise Tool's use: being more precise, there will be the main file setting, if this file will refer to the Certification analyse; while, there will be a specific file setting to perform the Footprint calculation, due to the fact that it is necessary to reduce the computational weight and time. In function of this aspect, in Table 4.28 data, necessary to update the certification Control Parameters file, have been defined. As it is possible to notice, all control parameters have been set to consider as much as possible effects and contributions in order to obtain the estimation as complete as possible, even if the test case represents the Take-Off phase without the Cut-Back manoeuvre.

Variable Name	Description	Value
U	Unit reference system	1
Certification_Type	Certification choice	1
ICAPP	Run Approach case	0
ICLAT	Run Lateral case	1
ICFLY	Run Fly-Over case	0
LATERAL_T_FILE	Trajectory Lateral File Name	TrajectoryLateral.csv

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Variable Name	Description	Value
LATERAL_R_FILE	Receivers Lateral File Name	Receivers_Lateral.csv
IA1	Wing contribution	1
IA2	Horizontal tail contribution	1
IA3	Vertical tail contribution	1
IA4	Slat contribution	1
IA5	Flap contribution	1
IA6	Main Landing Gears contribution	1
IA7	Nose Landing Gears contribution	1
IAIR	Airframe contribution	1
IENG	Engine contribution	1
IATM	Atmospheric attenuation effect	1
IREFL	Ground reflection effect	1
ILAT	Lateral attenuation effect	1

It continues in the next page...

Variable Name	Description	Value
ISPL	Sound pressure level calculation	1
IOASPL	Overall Sound pressure level calculation	1
ISEL	Sound exposure level calculation	1
IPNL	Perceived noise level calculation	1
IPNLT	Tone corrected Perceived noise level calculation	1
IEPNL_NT	Effective Perceived noise level calculation	1
IEPNL	Tone corrected Effective Perceived noise level calculation	1
WDB	Weighted Sound pressure level calculation	1
K_SPL_WING	Wing multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_HTAIL	Horizontal tail(s) multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_VTAIL	Vertical tail(s) multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_SLAT	Slat multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_FLAP	Flap multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_MLG	Main Landing Gears multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_NLG	Nose Landing Gears multiplicative factor	1.0
K_SPL_ENGINE	Engine(s) multiplicative factor(s)	1.0
Δ_SPL_WING	Wing additive factor	0.0
Δ_SPL_HTAIL	Horizontal tail(s) additive factor	0.0
Δ_SPL_VTAIL	Vertical tail(s) additive factor	0.0

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Variable Name	Description	
Δ_SPL_SLAT	Slat additive factor	1.0
Δ_SPL_FLAP	Flap additive factor	1.0
Δ_SPL_MLG	Main Landing Gears additive factor	1.0
Δ_SPL_NLG	Nose Landing Gears additive factor	1.0
Δ_SPL_ENGINE	Engine(s) additive factor(s)	1.0
IOCSV	Output file in .csv format generation	0
IOMAX	Print the most Critical Result in a separate file	1
IOEW	Print the Results in all the multiple files	1
IOALL	Print all the Information of interest	1
IOSEP	Print Frames	1
IOTIT	Print Titles	1
IOTIME	Print an array containing calculation Times	1
IOPART	Print each component Contribution and Propagation Effect	1
IOTR	Print trajectory details	1
IOMIC	Print microphone details	1
IOTC	Print the correction of the the calculated PNLT	1
IOA1	Print Wing contribution separately	1
IOA2	Print horizontal tail contribution separately	1

It continues in the next page...

Variable Name	Description	Value
IOA3	Print vertical tail contribution separately	1
IOA4	Print Slat contribution separately	1
IOA5	Print Flap contribution separately	1
IOA6	Print Main landing Gears contribution separately	1
IOA7	Print Nose landing Gears contribution separately	1
IOAIR	Print Airframe contribution separately	1
IOENG	Print Engine contribution separately	1
IOATM	Print Atmospheric attenuation effect separately	1
IOREFL	Print Ground Reflection effect separately	1
IOLAT	Print Lateral attenuation effect separately	1
IOLOG_I	Write warnings about Input data Reading	1
IOLOG_ICHK	Write warnings about Input data Correctness	1
IOLOG_CALC	Write warnings generated during Calculation	1
IOLOG_OCHK	Write warnings about Output data Correctness	1
IOLOG_ALL	Write all Warnings	1
PREC	Number of Digits after the comma	1
WIDTH	Number of digits for Numbers' field width	10
WIDTH_TITLE	Number of digits for titles' field width	16
FILLER	Optional symbol for separating values	;

Table 4.28: Control parameters set to perform the noise certification estimation for WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Concerning the Footprint calculation, there are several parameters neglected in order to improve the calculation itself (these parameters are going to be set on 0):

- **Concerning the Sound Metrics**, the only metric to evaluate is the one defined by the CS-23 regulation ($IOASPL = 1$ and $WDB = 1$);
- **Concerning the Output and Printing conditions**, all parameters are going to be neglected, with the exception of the Map file's command, the Most significant results files' command ($IOMAX = 1$ and $IOMAP = 1$), the Frames Evaluation command ($IOSEP = 1$) and the Log commands ($IOLOG_I$, $IOLOG_ICLK$, $IOLOG_CALC$, $IOLOG_OCHK$, $IOLOG_ALL = 1$).

4.3.3 Noise Certification Results

The reference aircraft has been totally described and the needed input data and parameters have been set; so, it is possible to run the integration tool and, consequently, the Noise Tool ATTILA++, in order to obtain the certification results to compare with the regulation constrains and limits, discussed in paragraph 2.3.2.

Take-Off Test Case

Concerning the Take-Off case, it is possible to compare the estimated total noise emission with the certification limit from the CS-23 regulation, remembering that this limit is function of the aircraft's weight and it has been evaluated with the margin calculation function (see paragraph 3.3.12). In Table 4.29 these values have been compared, defining the noise emission's margin, and it is possible to observe the underrated values with respect the typical noise emissions of similar certified aircraft (see Fig.2.18); the reason why this underrating occurs is linked to the fact that the input engine file does not simulate with great accuracy the engine noise's emissions and this is due to the fact that these input data have been estimated with methodologies not able to evaluate correctly all noise's contributions and, moreover, they are not able to evaluate some secondary contributions at all (contributions concerning the burning chamber and the engine's case); in particular, the noise

input data suffer the filtering procedure applied by the A-Weighted correction, that leads to the evident underrating.

Estimated Value(dBA)	Certification Limit (dBA)	Noise Margin(dBA)
68.8 dBA	88.0 dBA	19.2 dBA

Table 4.29: Total noise emissions (expressed in OASPLdBA) compared with the regulation limit from CS-23 for the WP7-AC3 aircraft in the Take-Off test case.

In order to align the noise results with the typical ones of the same category's aircraft, a correction factor of the order of 25% of starting value on the engine contribution has been added (this solution is a simple and rough way to adjust the estimation results, even if the right way to correct them should be the exploiting of a precise input engine file and, mainly, the application of a valid estimation methodology to evaluate it); in Table 4.30 the corrected total emissions have been compared with the regulation limit, in order to evaluate the new noise margin.

Estimated Value(dBA)	Certification Limit (dBA)	Noise Margin(dBA)
83.6 dBA	88.0 dBA	4.4 dBA

Table 4.30: Corrected total noise emissions (expressed in OASPLdBA) compared with the regulation limit from CS-23 for the WP7-AC3 aircraft in the Take-Off test case.

Examining in depth the noise estimation procedure, in Table 4.31 all contributions and effects, assigned in the input data definition section, have been shown: remembering the logarithmic law that links noise values, the first aspect to highlight is the absence of emissions from the Vertical Tail, because of the relative position between the microphone and the flight path; moreover, there is no contribution from the Slats due to the fact that the tested aircraft does not provide for them.

Contribution	OASPL Value without Correction (dBA)	OASPL Value with Correction (dBA)
Wing	54.3 dBA	54.3 dBA
Horizontal Tail	46.3 dBA	46.3 dBA
Vertical Tail	0.0 dBA	0.0 dBA
Slat	0.0 dBA	0.0 dBA
Flap	52.1 dBA	52.1 dBA
Main Gears	33.3 dBA	33.3 dBA
Nose Gears	24.4 dBA	24.4 dBA
Airframe	56.7 dBA	56.7 dBA
Engine	65.8 dBA	80.1 dBA

Table 4.31: Noise results from all selected contributions of the WP7-AC3 aircraft in the Take-Off test case (the only difference can be seen in the engine contribution on which has been applied the correction factor).

Moreover, it is clear that the main airframe's sources are the lifting surfaces located on the main wing, while the gear contribution is significantly lower than the others. The prevalence of the engine contribution on the total emissions is confirmed, like the fact that during the Take-Off manoeuvre this contribution is quasi totalitarian (there is the maximum setting for the engines during the Take-Off phase).

The Integration Tool's execution returns the trajectory's plotting and time-histories, as it is possible to see in Figs.4.17-4.19.

Figure 4.17: Simplified and smoothed climb angle's time-history for the Take-Off phase performed by the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Figure 4.18: Simplified and smoothed speed's time-history for the Take-Off phase performed by the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Figure 4.19: Simplified and smoothed Take-Off flight path performed by the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

The certification calculation method, moreover, has been exploited to compare the several noise results on varying of the on-board systems electrification, as it has been anticipated in the paragraph's introduction. The important aspect to highlight is how a modify on the on-board systems can acts and changes the noise emissions of the aircraft; this is due to the weight's increase in addition to some modifies on the aircraft's airframe. In Table 4.32 it is possible to compare these results (the correction factor is not considered) and it is possible to observe a low but important noise reduction with an increase of the on-board electrical systems.

Contribution	Estimated Value (dBA)	Certification Limit (dBA)	Noise Margin (dBA)
Conventional	68.8 dBA	88.0 dB	19.2 dBA
AEA	68.5 dBA	88.0 dB	19.5 dBA
MEA1	68.5 dBA	88.0 dB	19.5 dBA
MEA2	68.7 dBA	88.0 dB	19.3 dBA

Table 4.32: Total Noise emissions and margins on varying of the on-board systems electrification of the tested aircraft (AEA = All Electric Aircraft; MEA1 = More Electric Aircraft 1; MEA2 = More Electric Aircraft 2).

4.3.4 Footprint

The Footprint Tool is able to plot an estimated two-dimensions contour of the total noise emissions in the hypothesis of locating a dense mesh of microphones, distributed along the "x" and "y" axes. In Fig.4.20 it is possible to observe the Take-Off Footprint in a local reference frame, which center corresponds to the beginning of the runway from the take-offing point of view; the characteristic trend of this footprint is the "shell" trend, because there is an increase of the noise emissions going inside the contour with the highest values in the inner layer of plot; moreover, the evident particularity is the local sudden decrease of the noise emissions around the x location equals to 1500 m, moving along the y axis; with the exception of this aspect, the footprint's trend follows the "shell" model with the only difference of the widening along the y axes in the range along x axes that goes from the runway's ending to the initial part of the climb section.

The estimated results, achieved with the Footprint Tool, have been exploited to try to clarify the real impact of the aircraft's action on the local environment, in terms of noise emissions and noise pollution. Several studies have been done in the last decades on the psychological impact of the acoustic emissions, produced by the aircraft during the take-offs and landings, in the environment near the airport.

Figure 4.20: Take-Off test case Footprint, divided in several contour levels [72; 75; 80; 83; 87]. The Footprint refers to the AC3-WP7 aircraft and it has been estimated through a 81x102 microphones' matrix.

In function of this aspect, the previous contours have been overlapped on several geographic images, acquired from the satellites' geo-localization system, better known as *Google Earth* [47]. In Fig.4.21 it is possible to observe the noise footprint impact in the Take-Off case on the local environment, near the *Naples-Capodichino International Airport* [48](the overlapped footprint is a simplified version of the previous one, seen in Fig.4.20, because of the impossibility to obtain the contours levels in the linear form necessary to perform the overlapping itself). It is evident how significant is the noise impact on people living near the airport, considering, above all, that the Naples' airport has been located in a quite dense residential zone.

Figure 4.21: Take-Off test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Naples-Capodichino International Airport's local environment.

Figure 4.22: Approach test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Frankfurt Airport's local environment.

A completely different discussion can be made on the Frankfurt Airport "*Flughafen Frankfurt am Main*" [49] which location is far from the residential zones; in this

way the noise emissions effects on the local population can be mitigated and they will impact less. In Fig.4.22 it is possible to notice the really low impact of the noise emissions due to the Take-Off phase of the AC3-WP7 aircraft(the overlapped footprint is a simplified version of the one in Fig.4.20 due to the same difficulty discussed for the Naples case).

4.3.5 Alternative CS-25 Certification Procedure

The tested aircraft possesses a particular trait, linked to its MTOW: the AC3-WP7 aircraft has a MTOW equals to 8 620 Kg and this aspect makes the aircraft testable with both regulations CS-23 and CS-25 (the aircraft can be located in a weight's range that is in the upper limit of the CS-23 regulation's category and, at the same time, in the lower limit of the CS-25 regulation's category). It is possible, so, to test the AC3-WP7 on the base of the CS-25 regulation, as it happens for the AC6-WP8 aircraft (see paragraph 4.2).

To perform the alternative certification procedure it is sufficient to switch the certification parameter on the CS-25 case (*Certification_Type* = 0) and the Integration Tool will automatically update the input files to respect the CS-25 regulation's constrains.

Approach Test Case

Concerning the Approach case, it is possible to compare the estimated total noise emission with the certification limit from the CS-25 regulation, remembering that this limit is function of the aircraft's weight and it has been evaluated with the margin calculation function (see paragraph 3.3.12). In Table 4.33 these values have been compared, defining the noise emission's margin (this margin will be useful to evaluate the noise airport's charges and revenues); it is possible to observe how this results respect the typical experimental results of same category's aircraft (see Fig.2.15).

Estimated Value(dB)	Certification Limit(dB)	Noise Margin(dB)
91.9 dB	98 dB	6.1 dB

Table 4.33: Total noise emissions (expressed in EPNLdB) compared with the regulation limit from CS-25 for the WP7-AC3 aircraft in the Approach test case.

Examining in depth the noise estimation procedure, in Table 4.34 all contributions and effects, assigned in the input data definition section, have been shown: remembering the logarithmic law that links noise values, the first aspect to highlight is the absence of emissions from the Vertical Tail (due to its relative position with respect to the flight path and the microphone position, it does not produce significant noise emissions which can be assumed like none).

Contribution	EPNL Value with Tone Correction(dB)	EPNL Value without Tone Correction(dB)
Wing	67.2 dB	66.7 dB
Horizontal Tail	59.2 dB	58.6 dB
Vertical Tail	-inf	-inf
Slat	-inf	-inf
Flap	71.4 dB	70.9 dB
Main Gears	64.8 dB	64.0 dB
Nose Gears	58.4 dB	58.0 dB
Airframe	73.9 dB	73.5 dB
Engine	88.3 dB	87.7 dB

Table 4.34: Noise results from all selected contributions of the WP7-AC3 aircraft with and without the Tone Correction effect, in the Approach test case.

Moreover, it is clear that the main airframe's sources are the lifting surfaces located on the main wing, even if there is no contribution from the Slats due to

their absence on the tested aircraft; but the most important and obvious aspect to underline is the majority effect due to the engines: in fact, comparing the single engine emissions with the total emissions and the airframe ones, it is evident that the engine emissions represents more or less the quasi-totality of the total aircraft's emissions, while the airframe's contributions should represent more or less +1dB in the total value, even if during the Approach phase the engine setting would be at its minimum, due to its uselessness in this phase.

The integration tool's execution returns also the trajectory's plotting that in this specific test case restricts itself to the flight path showing, as it is possible to see in Fig.4.23.

Figure 4.23: Simplified and smoothed approach flight path performed by the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Lateral Test Case

Concerning the Lateral case, it is possible to compare the estimated total noise emission with the certification limit from the CS-25 regulation, remembering that this limit is function of the aircraft's weight and it has been evaluated with the margin calculation function (see paragraph 3.3.12). In Table 4.35 these values have been compared, defining the noise emission's margin; it is possible to observe how this results respect the typical experimental results of same category's aircraft (see Fig.2.9).

Estimated Value(dB)	Certification Limit(dB)	Noise Margin(dB)
82.5 dB	94 dB	12.3 dB

Table 4.35: Total noise emissions (expressed in EPNLdB) compared with the regulation limit from CS-25 for the WP7-AC3 aircraft in the Lateral test case.

Contribution	EPNL Value with Tone Correction(dB)	EPNL Value without Tone Correction(dB)
Wing	50.5 dB	49.3 dB
Horizontal Tail	39.0 dB	39.0 dB
Vertical Tail	45.0 dB	44.9 dB
Slat	-inf	-inf
Flap	50.8 dB	49.9 dB
Main Gears	30.3 dB	30.3 dB
Nose Gears	20.9 dB	20.9 dB
Airframe	55.8 dB	55.1 dB
Engine	78.2 dB	77.4 dB

Table 4.36: Noise results from all selected contributions of the WP7-AC3 aircraft with and without the Tone Correction effect, in the Lateral test case.

Examining in depth the noise estimation procedure, in Table 4.36 all contributions and effects, assigned in the input data definition section, have been shown: remembering the logarithmic law that links noise values, the first aspect to highlight, with respect to the Approach case, is the presence of emissions from the Vertical Tail, because in this case this emissions can be measured due to the relative position between the microphones and the flight path (microphones have been located at a defined y distance, so, they are not along the flight path and they can "see" the Vertical Tail).

Moreover, it is clear that the main airframe's sources are, still, the lifting surfaces located on the main wing. The important difference with respect to the Approach case is the total prevalence of the engine's emissions: in the Lateral case the aircraft's configuration is less aggressive with respect the Approach one (lower deflection of the movable surfaces that leads to lower aerodynamic forces and effects) and this aspect leads to a lower structure-flow's interaction that causes a significant noise emissions' reduction; on the other side the engine exploiting is more consistent and this leads to an increase of the noise emissions. In conclusion, the reduction of airframe's emissions causes an overall reduction of noise emissions that normally have a value lower than 10 dB order of magnitude (considering the logarithmic laws, this means a difference of more than eight times in noise emissions).

The integration tool's execution returns also the trajectory's plotting and time-histories, as it is possible to see in Figs.4.24-4.27.

Figure 4.24: Simplified and smoothed Take-Off flight path performed by the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Figure 4.25: Simplified and smoothed climb angle's time-history for the take-off phase performed by the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Figure 4.26: Simplified and smoothed speed's time-history for the take-off phase performed by the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Figure 4.27: Simplified and smoothed throttle rate's time-history for the take-off phase performed by the WP7-AC3 aircraft.

Fly-Over Test Case

Concerning the Fly-Over case, it is possible to compare the estimated total noise emission with the certification limit from the CS-25 regulation, remembering that this limit is function of the aircraft's weight and it has been evaluated with the margin calculation function (see paragraph 3.3.12). In Table 4.37 these values have been compared, defining the noise emission's margin; it is possible to notice that this result is quite underrated with respect the noise emissions from aircraft of the same weight and engine's category. A possible reason for this singular trend could be the not good definition of the input engine file, which data could be underrated if considered in the Fly-Over test case (see Fig.2.11); moreover, another possible reason could be the high relative distance between the certification microphone and the aircraft during the flight path.

Estimated Value(dB)	Certification Limit(dB)	Noise Margin(dB)
76.1 dB	89.0 dB	12.9 dB

Table 4.37: Total noise emissions (expressed in EPNLdB) compared with the regulation limit from CS-25 for the WP7-AC3 aircraft in the Fly-Over test case.

Examining in depth the noise estimation procedure, in Table 4.38 all contributions and effects, assigned in the input data definition section, have been shown: remembering the logarithmic law that links noise values, the first aspect to highlight is the absence of emissions from the Vertical Tail, like the Approach case and this happens because of the microphone position along the flight path (being aligned with the flight path, the microphone does not "see" the Vertical Tail from the noise point of view).

Contribution	EPNL Value with Tone Correction(dB)	EPNL Value without Tone Correction(dB)
Wing	56.1 dB	55.4 dB
Horizontal Tail	47.5 dB	47.1 dB
Vertical Tail	-inf	-inf
Slat	-inf	-inf dB
Flap	56.9 dB	56.2 dB
Main Gears	-inf	-inf
Nose Gears	-inf	-inf
Airframe	60.6 dB	59.9 dB
Engine	71.4 dB	71.1 dB

Table 4.38: Noise results from all selected contributions of the WP7-AC3 aircraft with and without the Tone Correction effect, in the Fly-Over test case.

Moreover, it is clear that the main airframe's sources are the lifting surfaces located on the main wing. The singular result, obtained in the Fly-Over analyse, is the no contributions due to the Landing Gears, even if it is due to the fact that they have been retracted at the beginning of the climb phase, so during the Lateral test case. In terms of engine-airframe's comparison, the engine contribution is, always, the main one even if, due to the Cut-Back manoeuvre, the engine effect's is lowered but on the other side the airframe contribution has been lowered too (it is due to the increase of the relative distance between microphone and airframe itself). In function of this aspects, the Fly-Over test case is the one with the lowest noise emissions (main improvement comes from the cut-back correction): there is a reduction of more or less 6 dB order of magnitude, with respect to the Lateral case, and even 16 dB order of magnitude, with respect to the Approach condition. The integration tool's execution returns also the trajectory's plotting and time-

histories, as it is possible to see in Figs.4.24-4.27, that contains both Lateral and Fly-Over plots.

Footprint

The Footprint Tool is able to plot an estimated two-dimensions contour of the total noise emissions in the hypothesis of locating a dense mesh of microphones, distributed along the x and y axes. In Fig.4.28 it is possible to observe the Approach Footprint in a local reference frame which center corresponds to the beginning of the runway from the approaching point of view; the characteristic trend of this footprint is the "shell" trend, because there is an increase of the noise emissions going inside the contour with the highest values in the inner layer of plot; moreover this increase tends to move toward the runway, due to the reduction of the relative distance between microphones and aircraft.

Figure 4.28: Approach test case Footprint, divided in several contour levels [80; 83; 86; 89; 92; 95]. The Footprint refers to the AC7-WP3 aircraft and it has been estimated through a 61x81 microphones' matrix.

In Fig.4.29, instead, it is possible to observe the Take-Off Footprint, that include both Lateral and Fly-Over phases, in the same previous reference frame with the only difference in the moving direction of the aircraft and so the contour, which is perfectly opposite to the Approach case (it corresponds to the take-offing point of view). For the Take-Off case the "shell" analogy is valid too and the highest value have been measured near the runway also in this case (the relative distance's reduction occurs with the same logic of the previous case); the only difference is the more particular shape that finds out a localized increase of the noise emissions along the "y" axis in the "x" distance's range at the end of the runway and immediately after (this trend can be associated to the increase of aircraft's speed and, consequently, the engine's thrust during the Lift-Off phase that balances and dominates the microphones' relative distances' increase).

Figure 4.29: Take-Off test case Footprint, divided in several contour levels [75; 80; 85; 87; 90]. The Footprint refers to the AC7-WP3 aircraft and it has been estimated through a 102x90 microphones' matrix.

The estimated results, achieved with the Footprint Tool, have been exploited to try to clarify the real impact of the aircraft's action on the local environment, in terms of noise emissions and noise pollution. Several studies have been done in the last decades on the psychological impact of the acoustic emissions, produced by the aircraft during the take-offs and landings, in the environment near the airport. In function of this aspect, the previous contours have been overlapped on several geographic images, acquired from the satellites' geo-localization system, better known as *Google Earth* [47]. In Fig.4.30 it is possible to observe the noise footprint impact in the Take-Off case on the local environment, near the *Naples-Capodichino International Airport* [48]; instead, in Fig.4.31 it is possible to observe the noise footprint impact in the Approach case in the same environment. It is evident in these plots how significant is the noise impact on people living near the airport, considering, above all, that the Naples' airport has been located in a residential zone quite dense.

Figure 4.30: Take-Off test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Naples-Capodichino International Airport's local environment.

Figure 4.31: Approach test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Naples-Capodichino International Airport's local environment.

A completely different discussion can be made on the Frankfurt Airport "*Flughafen Frankfurt am Main*" [49] which location is far from the residential zones; in this way the noise emissions effects on the local population can be mitigated and they will impact less. In Fig.4.33 it is possible to notice the really low impact of the noise emissions due to the Approach phase of the AC3-WP7 aircraft, while in Fig.4.32 it is possible to notice the same positive effect for the Take-Off phase performed by the same aircraft.

Figure 4.32: Take-Off test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Frankfurt Airport's local environment.

Figure 4.33: Approach test case Footprint overlapped on the satellite image of the Frankfurt Airport's local environment.

Conclusions and Future Developments

The Integration Tool finds its usefulness in the MDO logic inasmuch it gives the possibility to exploit the Integrated Tool of ATTILA++ in a easier way and in a real time application, performed by the specific user of the tool itself. In function of this, the integration tool, not only improves the Noise Tool performing from the input/output files' updating point of view, but also introduces several features able to increase the understanding on the noise results achieved with the tool itself: first of all, the trajectory functions increase the degree of precision of the noise's estimation due to the fact that they are able to estimate simplified but precise trajectories for all possible test cases on the base of the regulation's constrains and rules; moreover, the Footprint Tool adds the capability to evaluate the noise's results, achieved with the Noise Tool, through graphic representations of the noise impact on a local area near the runway of the airport. This improvement is a key resource to better understand the psychological impact of the aircraft's noise on the local environment and on the living of people settled in that area affected by the noise emissions themselves (the comparison between the noise impact on the Naples and Frankfurt airports demonstrates how significant could be the noise effect of a certain aircraft on two different residential zones). In fact, the subsequent employment of the noise results, achieved with the Integration Tool, consists in the calculation of the noise revenues of an aircraft in function of the regulation's constrains and in function of the airport charges, that differ from airport to airport (this aspect confirms the great importance of the MDO logic and how it reduces the time's costs). The airport revenues and limits have been defined, in order to restrict the noise emissions in such a way to reduce the negative effects on people living near the airport.

The future improvements for the Integration Tool could be the possibility to overlap directly the noise footprint of a certain aircraft on a geo-located picture of the surrounding area of an assigned airport runway, taken from a previously assigned list of airports; while, nowadays, this procedure can be conducted in a manual way

in an independent preliminary tool. In the end, another future improvement should be the more precise calculation of the engine noise emissions of a Light Turbo-Prop aircraft, certified on the base of the CS-23 regulation: as it has been seen, the noise results of a Turbo-Prop aircraft, certified CS-23, looks like underestimated with respect the typical experimental results due to a not correct methodology to evaluate the A-Weighting filtering in the dBA sound metric.

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